

NFDI for Catalysis-Related Sciences

NFDI4Cat

Proposal submitted to the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft on 15 October 2019

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10829858](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10829858)

Table of contents

1	General information	4
	Summary	4
	Zusammenfassung	5
2	Consortium	11
	2.1 Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium, objectives	11
	2.2 Research composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest	14
	2.3 The consortium within the NFDI.....	21
	2.4 International networking.....	22
	2.5 Organisational structure and viability	25
	2.6 Operating model.....	27
3	Research Data Management Strategy.....	28
	3.1 Current state and specific expertise	28
	3.2 Overview of envisaged RDM implementation	33
	3.3 Data Quality Management.....	36
	3.4 Metadata standards.....	37
	3.5 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance	46
	3.6 Service provides by the consortium	48
4	Work Programme	50
	4.1 Overview of task areas	50
	4.2 Ontology development and metadata standards (TA1)	52
	4.3 Data Standards, Data Collection and Interfaces (TA2)	56
	4.4 Data Analysis, Quality Management and Re-Use (TA3)	67
	4.5 Linked Extensible Infrastructure and Access Management (TA4).....	72
	4.6 Dissemination and Outreach/Training (TA5)	82
	4.7 Networking with NFDIs, SFBs und international (TA6).....	86
	4.8 Intellectual Property and Confidentiality, Licences and Reward models (TA7)	

4.9	Management (TA8)	97
4.10	Overview of activities by co-applicant	102
5	Overall Funding Request	108
6	General Compliance	116
7	Appendix	117
7.1	Bibliography and list of references	117
7.2	Curricula vitae and lists of publications	123
7.3	Letter of commitment by the participants	169
7.4	Letter of support	174

1 General information

Name of the consortium

English: NFDI for Catalysis-Related Sciences (NFDI4Cat)

German: NFDI für Wissenschaften mit Bezug zur Katalyse (NFDI4Cat)

Summary

The overall strategy for the transformation of catalysis research across all relevant disciplines in catalysis and chemical engineering is structured as a stepwise approach as outlined in the Whitepaper: “The Digitalization of Catalysis-Related Sciences” published by GeCatS – German Catalysis Society in March 2019.¹ It follows the path of transforming catalysis related sciences into a branch of digital sciences. In order to turn this strategy into a tangible plan and align it with the targets of the NFDI² a structure of task areas and measures will be pursued in working groups covering technical, organizational and educational aspects. The approach of NFDI4Cat targets at an early stage validation of the core functionalities developed by the construction of a pilot allowing assembly and integrated view of data libraries of both experimental and calculated data from theoretical assessment. The purpose of this pilot is the early phase demonstration of successful development of data and metadata standards as well as a functionality test of the infrastructure, so that the data and metadata standards can be validated, as well as the performance of the infrastructure employed.

A roadmap towards institutionalization of these elements is also required for assuring continuous existence beyond the communicated framework of funding of the NFDI. The whole process should be user-driven and follow the principles of stakeholder participation. Catalysis and chemical engineering have a massive socio-economic impact related to climate change and the environment as well as to the development of sustainable industrial production. The academic and industrial perspective in intense dialogue have a proven track record both in producing excellence in science and technical realization - this dialogue is aspired to and will be fostered. In conjunction with this initiative it is also vital to work on models for an implementation plan in the national academic education system, so that future generations of scientists working in the field of catalysis do have a smooth start regarding the skill sets acquired during their education and will be able to further develop the field of digital catalysis science. From a current point of view, it is also important to emphasize that the time scale, until a full implementation and the final goal of a fully digitalized national scene in catalysis can be reached, is expected to be on the order of a decade. It is anticipated that

¹ [GeCats Whitepaper 2019](#) (Accessed on 15th Oct. 2019).

² [Stellungnahme NFDI](#) (Accessed on 15th Oct. 2019).

ultimately the information architecture will become an indispensable tool of a digitalized community in catalysis on a national and international basis and therefore has to be built on a sustainable basis. The core topics that will be addressed by the consortium are covered by the following workstreams, which all follow the value chain “from molecules to chemical processes”.

- Workstream (A) Data and Meta-Data Standards
- Workstream (B) Data Science and Information Infrastructure Design
- Workstream (C) Community and User related Aspects

Zusammenfassung

Wie im Whitepaper beschrieben, ist die langfristige Strategie für die Transformation der Katalyseforschung über alle relevanten Disziplinen der Katalyse und Chemieingenieurwesen hinweg als schrittweiser Ansatz strukturiert: "The Digitalization of Catalysis-Related Sciences", veröffentlicht von GeCatS - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Katalyse im März 2019.³ . Es beschreibt den Weg der Transformation der katalysenahen Wissenschaften in einen Zweig der digitalen Wissenschaften. Um diese Strategie in einen konkreten Plan umzusetzen und mit den Zielen der NFDI⁴ in Einklang zu bringen, wird eine Struktur von Aufgabenbereichen und Maßnahmen in Arbeitsgruppen zu technischen, organisatorischen und pädagogischen Aspekten verfolgt. Der Ansatz von NFDI4Cat zielt auf eine frühzeitige Validierung der Kernfunktionalitäten ab, die durch den Aufbau eines Piloten oder mehrerer Pilotstrukturen entwickelt wurden, die eine Zusammenstellung und integrierte Ansicht von Datensammlungen sowohl experimenteller als auch berechneter Daten aus der theoretischen Bewertung ermöglichen. Ziel dieses Pilotprojekts ist die frühzeitige Demonstration der erfolgreichen Entwicklung von Daten- und Metadatenstandards sowie ein Funktionstest der Infrastruktur, damit die Daten- und Metadatenstandards sowie die Leistung der eingesetzten Infrastruktur validiert werden können.

Ein Aktionsplan zur Institutionalisierung dieser Elemente ist zudem erforderlich, um die Kontinuität über den kommunizierten Förderrahmen der NFDI hinaus zu gewährleisten. Der gesamte Prozess wird benutzerorientiert sein und dem Prinzip der Beteiligung aller Interessengruppen folgen. Da die Katalyse und die Verfahrenstechnik massive sozioökonomische Auswirkungen haben und die akademische und industrielle Perspektive in einem intensiven Dialog nachweislich hervorragende Leistungen in der Wissenschaft und der technischen Umsetzung erbringen, ist ein fruchtbarer Dialog mit der Industrie gefragt und wird gefördert.

³ [GeCats Whitepaper 2019](#) (Accessed on 15th Oct. 2019).

⁴ [Stellungnahme NFDI](#) (Accessed on 15th Oct. 2019).

Im Zusammenhang mit dieser Initiative ist es auch wichtig, an Modellen für einen Umsetzungsplan im nationalen Bildungssystem zu arbeiten, damit zukünftige Generationen von Wissenschaftlern im Bereich der Katalyse einen reibungslosen Start in Bezug auf die während ihrer Ausbildung erworbenen Kompetenzen haben und den Bereich der digitalen Katalysewissenschaft weiter entwickeln können. Aus aktueller Sicht ist es zudem wichtig zu betonen, dass die Zeitspanne bis zur vollständigen Umsetzung einer durchgängig digitalisierten nationalen Struktur in der Katalyse voraussichtlich etwa ein Jahrzehnt, möglicherweise länger, betragen wird. Es wird erwartet, dass die Informationsarchitektur letztendlich zu einem unverzichtbaren Instrument einer digitalisierten Gemeinschaft in der Katalyse auf nationaler und internationaler Ebene wird und daher nachhaltig aufgebaut werden muss. Die Kernthemen, die vom Konsortium bearbeitet werden, werden in den folgenden Workstreams behandelt, die alle entlang der Wertschöpfungskette "von Molekülen zu chemischen Prozessen" entwickelt wurden.

- Workstream (A) Data and Meta-Data Standards
- Workstream (B) Data Science and Information Infrastructure Design
- Workstream (C) Community and User related Aspects

- Applicant institution

Applicant institution	Location
DECHEMA e.V.	Theodor-Heuss-Allee 25, 60486 Frankfurt

- Name of consortium spokesperson

Spokesperson	Institution, location
Prof. Dr. Kurt Wagemann	DECHEMA e.V., Theodor-Heuss-Allee 25, 60486 Frankfurt

- Co-applicant institutions

Co-applicant institutions	Location
Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse e.V. (LIKAT)	Albert-Einstein-Str. 29, 18059 Rostock
Max-Planck-Institut für Dynamik komplexer technischer Systeme (MPI-DCTS)	Sandtorstraße 1, 39106 Magdeburg
Universität Greifswald (UHGW)	Institut für Biochemie, Felix-Hausdorff-Str. 4, 17487 Greifswald
Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT)	Kaiserstraße 12, 76131 Karlsruhe
Universität Leipzig (UL)	Institut für Technische Chemie, Linnéstraße 3-4, 04103 Leipzig
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)	Egerlandstr. 3, 91058 Erlangen
Technische Universität Dortmund (TUDO)	Fakultät für Bio - und Chemieingenieurwesen, Emil-Figge-Str. 68, 44227 Dortmund
Universität Rostock (UHRO)	Institut für Chemie, Albert-Einstein-Str. 3a, 18059 Rostock
Technische Universität Berlin (TUB)	Technische Universität Berlin, Insitut für Chemie, Sek. EW-K-01 (BasCat), Hardenbergstr. 36, 10623 Berlin
Technische Universität München (TUM)	Department Chemie, Lichtenbergstr. 4, 85748 Garching
Max-Planck-Institut für Chemische Energiekonversion (MPI-CEC)	Stiftstraße 34-36, 45470 Mülheim an der Ruhr

Technische Universität Braunschweig(TUBS)	Institut für Technische Chemie, Hagenring 30, 38106 Braunschweig
Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule) WTH Aachen (RWTH)	Worringerweg 1, 52074 Aachen
Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems (FOKUS)	Kaiserin-Augusta-Allee 31, 10589 Berlin
Universität Stuttgart, High Performance Computing Center Stuttgart (HLRS)	Nobelstr. 19, 70569 Stuttgart

- Names of Co-spokespersons

Co-spokesperson	Institution, Location	Task area(s)
Prof. Dr. Matthias Beller	Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse e.V. (LIKAT), Albert-Einstein-Str. 29, 18059 Rostock	TA1, TA2, TA3
Prof. Dr. Peter Benner	Max-Planck-Institut für Dynamik komplexer technischer Systeme, Sandtorstraße 1, 39106 Magdeburg	TA1, TA2, TA3
Prof. Dr. Uwe Bornscheuer	Universität Greifswald, Institut für Institut für Biochemie, Felix-Hausdorff-Str. 4, 17487 Greifswald	TA1, TA2
Prof. Dr. Olaf Deutschmann	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, Kaiserstraße 12, 76131 Karlsruhe	TA1, TA2, TA3
Prof. Dr. Roger Gläser	Universität Leipzig, Institut für Technische Chemie, Linnéstraße 3-4, 04103 Leipzig	TA5, TA6, TA7
Dr. Marco Haumann	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Egerlandstr. 3, 91058 Erlangen	TA1; TA2
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Norbert Kockmann	Technische Universität Dortmund, Faculty of	TA1, TA2

	Biochemical- und Chemical Engineering, Emil-Figge-Str. 68, 44227 Dortmund	
Prof. Dr. Udo Kragl	Universität Rostock, Institut für Chemie, Albert-Einstein-Str. 3, 18059 Rostock	TA2, TA5
Dr.-Ing. habil. Ralph Krähnert	Technische Universität Berlin, BasCat - UniCat BASF Joint Lab, Hardenbergstraße 36, 10623 Berlin	TA2, TA3
Prof. Dr. Johannes Lercher	Technische Universität München, Department Chemie, Lichtenbergstr. 4, 85748 Garching	TA1, TA2, TA5
Prof. Dr. Walter Leitner	Max-Planck-Institut für Chemische Energiekonversion, Stiftstraße 34-36, 45470 Mülheim an der Ruhr	TA1, TA2, TA3
Prof. Dr. Mehtap Özaslan	Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institut für Technische Chemie, Hagenring 30, 38106 Braunschweig	TA1, TA2
Prof. Dr. Regina Palkovits	RWTH Aachen, Worringerweg 1, 52074 Aachen	TA1, TA2, TA3
Dr. Sonja Schimmler	Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems FOKUS Kaiserin-Augusta-Allee 31, 10589 Berlin	TA2; TA4
Prof. Dr. Michael Resch	Universität Stuttgart, High Performance Computing Center Stuttgart, Nobelstr. 19, 70569 Stuttgart	TA1, TA2, TA4, TA6

- Participants

Participants	Institution (where applicable), location
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Bastian Etzold	Technische Universität Darmstadt, Alarich-Weiss-Str. 8, 64287 Darmstadt
Prof. Dr. Klaus-Robert Müller	TU Berlin (BBDC) Berlin Big Data Center und (BZML) Berlin Zentrum für Maschinelles Lernen, Marchstr. 23, 10587 Berlin
Prof. Dr. Marcus Rose	Technische Universität Darmstadt, Alarich-Weiss-Str. 8, 64287 Darmstadt

- Names and numbers of the DFG review boards

Research area of the proposed consortium (according to the DFG classification system)

201 Biochemie

3 Natural Sciences; 31 Chemistry; 301 Molecular Chemistry; 302 Chemical Solid State and Surface Research; 303 Physical and Theoretical Chemistry; 304 Analytical Chemistry, Method Development (Chemistry); 305 Biological Chemistry and Food Chemistry; 33 Mathematics; 312 Mathematics

4 Engineering Sciences; 42 Thermal Engineering/ Process Engineering; Computer Science, Systems and Electrical Engineering; 403 Process Engineering, Technical Chemistry; 404 Heat Energy Technology, Thermal Machines, Fluid Mechanics; 406 Materials Science; 407 Systems Engineering; 409 Computer Science

2 Consortium

2.1 Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium, objectives

Catalysis and chemical engineering are disciplines in science and technology which are highly interdisciplinary in nature. Both catalysis and chemical engineering are fields of high strategic importance for the economy and the society as a whole. Undoubtedly, catalysis and chemical engineering are the most important core technologies with the potential of solving pressing challenges concerning climate change and fight against air, water and soil pollution, supply of sustainable energy of sustainable materials and of sustainable chemicals production at the same time.⁵ NFDI4Cat embraces a holistic view and approach in which both catalysis and chemical engineering are core enablers paving the path from “molecule to process”. Concrete examples of global pressing issues are the reduction or complete avoidance of CO₂ emissions, the valorisation of plastic waste and biomass in chemical production, sustainable hydrogen generation, or sustainable fertilizer production for more than 7 billion people on this planet – all of these aspects require break-through advances in catalysis science and technology.

Figure 2-1 illustrates the complexity faced in catalysis and its sub-disciplines. Catalysis is a multi-scale science and technology. Covalent chemicals and non-covalent bonding determine the interaction of molecules with catalytically active surface. So far many concepts are of empirical or phenomenological nature. An improved understanding of reaction mechanisms and kinetics requires theory and experiments to work with model systems of sufficient complexity. If data analysis guides the elucidation of fundamental principles, a rational catalyst design as well as predictive searches can be enabled much more straight forward. The derived information can be used to engineer appropriate reactors and respective process concepts.

⁵ [Technology Roadmap Energy and GHG Reductions in the Chemical Industry via Catalytic Processes](#) (Accessed on 15th Oct. 2019).

Figure 2-1: Multitude aspects of catalysis research

To solve these pressing global issues and challenges by the help of catalysis and chemical engineering, a fundamental change is required in catalysis research, chemical engineering and process technology. One key challenge is to bring together the different disciplines in catalysis science and technology. The consortium aims to redefine catalysis research in the digital age and add new facets of digital empowerment. Core challenge is a fundamentally improved understanding in catalysis sciences, the creation of workflows in catalysis that build a bridge between theory/simulation and experimental studies in design, characterization and kinetics of catalysts and the related engineering aspects. This challenge requires also a unified view on all catalysis disciplines to reveal universal guiding principles common to homogenous, bio, heterogeneous and electro-catalysis. This unification can only be successful if the full potential of the emerging data science technology is made accessible to each catalysis researcher. Vital elements of this strategy are the unification and standardization of data and metadata formats and the understanding of the requirements for the creation of high-performance information architectures that allow storage, exchange and analysis of data utilizing the latest state of the art tools of artificial intelligence. However, data science requires high quality data based on unified formats in the first place. The enabling of all members of the community to produce and work with high quality data using unified formats based on a common ontology and semantics will be a key aspect of the consortiums endeavour. Other critical issues that need to be solved concern e.g. an information infrastructure accessible and accepted by the community, reward models, legal aspects like

confidentiality, licenses and intellectual property The consortium embarks on the endeavour of realizing “digital catalysis” along a value chain of data oriented from “molecules to chemical processes”. This data-based value chain has a non-virtual analogue and is therefore seen as ambitious but of high intrinsic value allowing for a high degree of sustainability.

Key objectives that are considered essential for the success of the consortium have been identified:

Catalysis community-related

- a) Enable and support cross-disciplinary research in fundamental and applied catalysis to realise the vision from molecule to process
- b) Improve digital and RDM skills in community, consolidating and uniting existing efforts
- c) Establish, foster, and incentivise use of open well-defined data structures and metadata standards designed for interdisciplinary use
- d) Facilitate collaboration on data level (across institutional boundaries)
- e) Provide education and training in applied research data management and data science for catalysis in chemistry and chemical engineering

Technical

- f) Provide software to establish a distributed and hierarchical repository structure for experimental and theoretical data based on FAIR principles that balances privacy/confidentiality and open data sharing
- g) Connect this repository network to NFDI- as well as European- and world-wide services (e.g. ORCID, OpenAIRE, Crossref, Datacite)
- h) Provide a platform that allows seamless transition between private/local data, group/project/NFDI data and finally published data.
- i) Provide tools/software that automatically check data consistency, correctness and reproducibility

Objectives with respect to NFDI / special role of NFDI4Cat in NFDI

- j) Represent a stakeholder that can show case cross-NFDI consortia success due the strongly interdisciplinary and multi-scale nature of NFDI4Cat

As measures of success are considered: The number of already published as well as of new papers and publications that are accessible over the research data infrastructure, the number of new studies/publications which make use of the data in NFDI4CAT and the tools developed, the number of contributors to the NFDI4Cat infrastructure, increasing knowledge and adaptation of RDM monitored by regular user surveys, the degree of compatibility with

other research data infrastructure from chemistry, material science, engineering, and other (natural) sciences. Success criteria that most prominent are the active use of the information infrastructure and can directly be related to the number of users working with the system developed and the amount of data stored in the system and the frequency of use of the information infrastructure can be taken.

2.2 Research composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest

NFDI4Cat addresses catalytic phenomena occurring on surfaces (heterogeneous and electro catalysis), at molecular structures (homogeneous catalysis) as well as in biological systems (bio-catalysis) and chemical engineering as enabling science and technology. The main aim of research is a fundamental understanding of all processes that occur on the "catalytically active sites" and an understanding of all the processes that create, modify and destroy active sites, of heat and transport processes related to the transport of reactants, and the implementation of such coupled processes up to the length scale of reactors and processes, which finally links catalysis science into chemical and process engineering. Methods essentially required in this research are the synthesis of materials, the characterization of materials, interfaces and reactors - if possible during the catalytic cycle, and the modelling of such phenomena at all length scales ranging from individual atoms and molecules to reactors and chemical processes as a whole.

Figure 2-2: Types of Data within NFDI4Cat consortium and partners for realisation of the vision "From Molecules to Process"

Also the environment of the catalyst has to be taken into account: gas phase reaction with or without addition of inert gas or reactions in liquid phases as with homogeneously soluble organometallic catalysts or enzymes. The latter may be immobilised on a support leading to mass transport phenomena. Combinations may be found as well. To cover these various aspects experts for all areas are part of the consortium representing the community active in the field of catalysis as a whole. In order to identify the specific needs of the catalysis and engineering community the consortium of GeCatS initiated a national dialogue in 2017 by interviews and developed an action plan with the goal of a) capturing the needs of the community and b) development of a plan for digitalization of the catalysis scene. Based on the discussion in March 2018 the board of GeCatS suggested the formation of a "Task Force Digitalization" which actively discussed with experts in the scene what important steps could be taken. Two were identified as vital I), a team of experts and authors united and analysed in discussion with the community the detailed needs in the transition into "digital catalysis"; II) to reflect the identified needs with the community and discuss them with an international panel in this process in autumn 2018 an international symposium was held to inform and discuss with experts renowned both in catalysis and data analysis and to collect and share opinions and views. The event and the resulting position paper were reviewed in the GeCatS annual member assembly in March 2019, the decision to form NFDI4Cat including the analysis published in the position paper was welcomed by the member assembly and the board of GeCatS. The activities and results of the NFDI4Cat will be disseminated by presentations in the upcoming annual meetings, the GeCatS-Newsletter and publications in scientific journals. Recommendations and guidelines for research data management in all areas of the catalysis disciplines will be elaborated and made available to the scientific community both via a web-portal and in print. NFDI4Cat provides an open platform and, as an initiative of the German Catalysis Society (GeCatS), will reach out to the scientific community on multiple levels. It will invite researchers from the broader catalysis community to participate as well as build and contribute to a nationwide and beyond research data infrastructure. It will therefore, be imbedded in other research data management initiatives within DECHEMA as well as communities and societies (GDCh, DGMK, VDI, ProcessNet). The specific needs of the community were identified using many different ways. This formation process was accompanied by intense discussion with related consortia, e.g. FAIRmat, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Ing and, DAPHNE. It will be in exchange not only with the German Catalysis Society, e.g., during the Annual GeCatS conference, but also with catalysis-related collaborative research consortia supported by the German Science Foundation (DFG), the German ministries and the European Commission. A close collaboration with the European Federation of Catalysis Societies (EFCATS) is envisaged as

stated by the Lol by the EFCATS President Bert Weckhuysen. Joint workshops and international conferences, e.g., on research data standards or management, are planned.

Moreover, the collaboration was sought with data experts and infrastructure providers, resulting in HLRS, Fraunhofer FOKUS, Berlin Big Data Center and (BBDC) and Berlin Center for Machine Learning (BZML) joining the team.

The user needs and requirements are the key driving force for forming NFDI4Cat and for all its current and future actions. Users (domain experts from all areas of catalysis) as well as data experts and providers (HLRS, FOKUS) are well represented in the co-applicant institutions. Moreover, a close interaction with the whole community is facilitated and organized via DECHEMA and its relevant sections and numerous conferences and workshops. Based on this existing network a user forum will be established. Right now, there are hardly any training opportunities to develop data science skills that are well suited for natural scientists. Unfortunately, an actual consecutive Bachelor and Master curriculum has not much space left to teach Chemistry and Biotechnology students modern ways to handle the diverse data types available today. On the other hand, there is a multitude of skills that need to be developed in the future that deviate from the “traditional” use of MS Word and Excel.

Several Graduate Academies and Research Schools at universities have started to or already offer training modules in research data management. However, these are often not specific for a certain research area and do not respond to the particular needs and the complexity of the catalysis-related sciences. Besides presentation on major conferences and fairs a transportable exhibition will be created in year two which can be ordered by groups or consortia interested. Different levels of expert advice can be booked together with the material in order to teach possible users or setup individual solutions.

For training students and young researchers in research data management and the generation and use of research data infrastructures in the catalysis-related sciences, NFDI4Cat will establish the *Research Data Management School of Catalysis*. With strong involvement of YoungGeCatS, the German platform of Young Catalysis Scientists from Academia and Industry, the training of students on the graduate and postgraduate level will be supported at an early stage of their education and research careers. The *Research Data Management School of Catalysis* will provide workshops, courses, lectures and materials (presentations, booklets) in a structured and modular manner covering all aspects of research data infrastructure and management in the catalysis-related sciences. These teaching modules and materials will be used in courses of the German Catalysis Institutes (*Katalyse-Lehrverbände*), for study curricula of chemistry, chemical and process engineering and for user workshops in the fields of catalysis. The students have to learn how to plot their

data, make proper fit on data, up to the simulation of differential equations and more. The lecture could have programming exercises in groups to train the skills of students. Machine Learning will also be included in some lectures. In addition, training of both postgraduate researchers and postdocs as organized by Research Schools and Research Academies at Universities will directly benefit from the opportunities offered by the *Research Data Management School of Catalysis* and other events, e.g. Summer Schools. Data-science-related concepts of the past like lectures in universities (e.g. Scientific Computing in Chemical Reaction Engineering – RWTH Aachen), nationwide cooperation (Katalyse-Lehrverbände, Helmholtz-Kolleg Energy-Related Catalysis, or the recently started Leibniz "Wissenschaftscampus" ChemBioCat between Rostock and Greifswald on the combination of chemo- and biocatalysis) and international events (European Summer School on Multiscale Modelling in Chemical Engineering) can be included in the Research Data Management School of Catalysis.

The consortium NFDI4Cat consists of experts from the field of homogeneous, heterogeneous, photo-, bio- and electro catalysis. The disciplines of reaction and process engineering are also represented in the consortium. The catalysis and engineering competences are complemented by expertise in the field of applied mathematics, data science, high-performance computing and machine learning. NFDI4Cat will collaborate with the relevant partners in the fields of chemistry, materials science and engineering. Consulting with respect to future use of the results will be provided by a panel of representatives of the chemical industry.

FAU. The Chair of Chemical Reaction Engineering from the **FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg** has a long standing expertise in development of catalytic materials in the field of homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis as well as hybrid combinations thereof, their operation in dedicated reactors for both batch and continuous mode and kinetic evaluation of the collected data.

Fraunhofer **FOKUS** is focusing on applied research, and has many years of experience in strategic data management and data platforms. In the context of the Weizenbaum Institute, they focus on the digitalization of science, and especially on Open Science and research data infrastructures.

Greifswald University has an outstanding expertise in the discovery, improvement (by rational design and directed evolution including an automated robotic platform for high-throughput screening) of enzymes for bio-catalytic applications in organic synthesis and for chiral pharmaceutical intermediates.

HLRS has 23 years of experience in providing high performance computing systems and services for users in Germany and Europe. It is working in the field of RDM for several years already. It has experience in developing metadata ontologies, tool development and repository deployment as well as distributed data management.

The **KIT** has a long and internationally recognized expertise in in synthesis (Behrens, Grunwaldt), in situ and operando characterization (Grunwaldt, Wöll), and multi-scale modeling of heterogeneous catalytic systems reaching from the molecular scale (Studt, Deutschmann) to the reactor and process engineering scale (Deutschmann, Dittmeyer, Sauer) with the current focus on energy-related catalysis for the development of green, climate-friendly, and emission-free products and processes. Several software tools have been developed in Karlsruhe that bring digitalization into research and application related to these topics such as TURBOMOLE, DETCHEM, and CaRMEn.

Leipzig University has, since the days of Wilhelm Ostwald, long-standing expertise in catalysis-related sciences which are now reflected in the strategic research profile areas of “sustainable systems and biodiversity” as well as “complex matter” and which is included in research data management structures from digital humanities to natural sciences.

The research activities of the Leibniz Institute for Catalysis - **LIKAT** are currently focused on three main areas: applied sustainable catalysis processes, innovative catalysis methods and technologies, and special (metal)organic syntheses and catalysis. Its areas of expertise are arranged both according to the various methods employed and according to the materials being studied. The scientists from LIKAT generate knowledge and innovation in the ongoing interactions that link basic research and applied research. The institute is constantly adjusting the focus of our research topics in order to address topics relevant to society.

The **MPI CEC** is generating fundamental knowledge to design, master, and control catalytic systems at the interface of energy and chemistry. A central focus is on small molecule activation using transition metal catalysts to convert renewable energy in chemical bonds for storage and utilization in energy carriers and chemical products.

MPI DCTS focuses on new process and systems engineering approaches, both theoretically and experimentally, for chemical and energy systems engineering, biotechnology as well as synthetic biology.

The Chair for Heterogeneous Catalysis and Chemical Technology of Prof. Regina Palkovits at **RWTH Aachen** (RWTH-Het) focuses on the derivation of structure activity relationships in heterogeneous catalysis mainly in sustainable and environmental chemistry but also data science approaches gather now more importance. This work is supplemented by the work of the Chair of Chemical Process Engineering of Prof. Wessling (RWTH-CVT) which contributes experience in implementing and using research data management and data driven research in practice (RDM-Spin-Off: FURTHResearch), as well as expertise and infrastructure for the translation of electrocatalytic processes from lab into technical scale - including instrumentation for automated data acquisition and analysis at industrial relevant process conditions. (ELECTRA, Competence Center for Electrochemical Process Engineering in cooperation with Forschungszentrum Jülich IEK-9).

TUB BasCat as a joint research center of the Cluster of excellence UNICAT and BASF at **TU Berlin** has proven expertise in the field of heterogeneous catalysis, material characterization and the development of data-driven research methods in catalysis.

Since its creation in 2014, the Berlin Big Data Center (**BBDC**) has significantly advanced the state of the art in big data through the combination of scalable data management and machine learning (ML). The center explores scalable technologies that can organize massive amounts of heterogeneous data and intelligently derive well-founded information for data-driven decision making.

The Berliner Zentrum für Maschinelles Lernen (**BZML**) further develops methods along the entire ML process by closely interlinking basic and applied research, while at the same time demonstrating the potential to use these ML methods to fuel the scientific process in various disciplines and lead to new insights.

Technical University of Braunschweig has a strong focus on renewable energy conversion and energy storage systems which is highlighted by Cluster of Excellence “SE²A – Sustainable and Energy Efficient Aviation” and BatteryLabFactory (BLB) to allow preparing, testing and characterizing electrochemical units (fuel cells, batteries, electrolyzers) at different length and time scales.

At the **TU Darmstadt** the laboratories of Prof. Marcus Rose and Prof. Bastian Etzold are focused on catalysis with topics ranging from catalyst synthesis and characterization, kinetic and mechanistic investigations towards application-related chemical reaction engineering. In heterogeneous catalysis as also in electrocatalysis the synthesis of energy carriers, base chemicals as also platform chemicals are covered

At the **TU Dortmund** the Laboratory of Equipment Design of Prof. Norbert Kockmann focused on advanced reactor design, particularly microreactors, with related separation steps such as distillation, liquid-liquid extraction or crystallization. Various catalytic reactions were investigated in different small-scale reactor setups. The work will be supported by the expertise in homogeneous catalysis and biocatalysis by Prof. Dr. Dieter Vogt and Dr. Kathrin Rosenthal, respectively.

The **Chair of Technical Chemistry II at TU München** addresses fundamental aspects of catalysts and catalyzed reactions that enable catalysis to lower the carbon footprint via radically new approaches to synthesize energy carriers and chemical intermediates. The research is focused to enable catalyzed conversions at significantly lower reaction temperatures and with higher selectivity than possible today. Two aspects of enzyme sites, i.e., the tight fit of the space around the active site and the chemical functionality of this space, are used as guideline to synthesize novel catalysts. The in-depth characterization of the nature and structure of such catalytically active sites, of their chemical functionality and of the space around it, as well as of the molecules populating this space is the key to the

successful realization of this strategy. The dynamic evolution of these catalysts is studied throughout their lifespan and spectroscopically monitored during catalyst synthesis, sorption and reactions, exploring possible operation conditions and their limitations. This work combines advanced physicochemical methods to characterize reactions on surfaces including IR, Raman, and solid state NMR spectroscopy with X-ray absorption spectroscopy to characterize the structure and electronic state of these materials during sorption and catalysis.

Besides the outstanding expertise in process development for chemo- and biocatalysis including downstream processing for complex molecules **Rostock University** is actively pursuing the implementation of a Research Data Infrastructure. The Central Library and the IT and Media centre play an essential role in this process, which is supported by the Rectorate. An expert group is currently setting up a strategy for handling research data. This is supported by central project of the Collaborative Research Centre 1270 Elaine to establish a common research data infrastructure. As a first outcome now an expert advice is available for the members of the CRC to set up a data management plan. This is supported by a web based tool. Electronic lab journals have been introduced for the scientists working within the CRC. The Rectorate of University of Rostock is supporting this initiative by additional funding to make these tools available to all faculties and scientists and install this permanently.

Figure 2-3: NFDI4Cat consortium and partners

An Advisory Council will allow for the utilisation of industrial experiences. These experiences are related to:

- the early adoption of LIMS-systems in the laboratories of the chemical industry,
- the handling of huge amounts of data produced by high throughput technologies developed about 25 years ago in the pharmaceutical sector and following adopted to the development of new catalysts
- and the large amount of data available from process management and control technologies in the context of large scale chemical manufacturing.

The activities and results of the NFDI4Cat will be disseminated by publications in scientific journals. Recommendations and guidelines for research data management in all areas of the catalysis disciplines will be elaborated and made available to the scientific community in the annual meetings and both via a web-portal and in print.

2.3 The consortium within the NFDI

In order to express the deep connection with other consortia, NFDI4Cat has signed and supports the intention of the Berlin Declaration ⁶

Current and planned collaborations include NFDI initiatives focus on more general aspects of material science, chemistry and engineering. The chemical physics of surfaces of materials, chemical reactions at surfaces, and multi-scale modelling of heterogeneous catalysis will be explored in collaboration with FAIRmat. Together with NFDI4Chem, the digital approaches towards the digital representation of the chemistry of molecular compounds as well as standards, formats of analytical data and cross-cutting topics like ontologies, metadata

formats will be discussed. Furthermore, the application of electronic laboratory notebooks (ELN) and the cross-linking of data repositories will be important intersections for NFDI4Chem and NFDI4Cat.

NFDI4Cat and NFDI4Chem share common interests in the following topics that will be addressed: in cooperation in the development of ontologies, meta-data formats and the cross-linking of data repositories. While NFDI4Chem focusses more on fundamental aspects in chemistry NFDI4Cat also covers the areas of technical chemistry and chemical engineering sciences.

Engineering aspects of catalysis, equipment characterisation and multiscale modelling will be approached within NFDI4Cat in close dialogue with NFDI4Ing. NFDI4Cat and NFDI4Ing will cooperate in the field of ontology development and metadata formats in order to harmonize the efforts in neighboring fields.

NFDI4Cat addresses all fundamental and applied aspects of with its associated fields of technical chemistry and chemical engineering and enables and supports cross-disciplinary research to realise the vision from molecule to process. Special emphasis is placed on the cross-disciplinary nature of catalysis linking homogeneous, heterogeneous and bio-catalysis, building upon the chemical physics of surfaces of materials and chemical reactions at surfaces, a focus of FAIRmat.

NFDI4Cat and DAPHNE share common interests in characterization data on catalysts and therefore will develop joined schemes for connecting them to the functionality of materials. DAPHNE focusses on data at large scale facilities which are of tremendous importance for operando and tomographic characterization of catalysts. IP-sensitive data are also relevant in DAPHNE and joint discussion will transfer experience from NFDI4Cat to DAPHNE. Joint workshops with the goal of establishing common examples, policies, best practice and guides for metadata catalogues, data repositories are planned.

Building strong connections in respect to the catalysis-related aspects of these consortia will further the success of NFDI4Cat. TIB as institutional library for science and technology can act as mediator for several planned initiatives in the area of chemistry related sciences. Together with other consortia like NFDI4Chem, a harmonization between the initiatives will be pursued; mutual learning through exchange will be fostered. In addition, the TIB within the consortium NFDI4Chem and in the same role FAIRmat are regarded as important discussion partners for ontology engineering, vocabulary development and conceptual development for association of metadata in suitable formats.

2.4 International networking

The proposed initiative aims primarily at improving catalysis science on a national level within the framework of NFDI; nevertheless, through active engagement within the Research Data

Alliance it will be ensured that developed standards within the consortium will be compatible with international standards. It will therefore create a lasting impact and assure the ability to compete in both science and applications also internationally. International collaborations within and beyond the catalysis community will be pursued. Collaboration and discussion between parties with experience in infrastructure management and “users” within the catalysis community will be a core element. Beyond the expertise assembled within the consortium in the field of high-performance computing, data science and machine learning, further collaborations are aimed for, e.g. Research Data Alliance, publication of results (standards, recommendations) in discipline-relevant journals (e.g. ChemCatChem) and others.

The common interests with these consortia circulate around the development of common ontologies, harmonized metadata structures, a common interest in tools for data analysis, a common interest in the connection of existing and to be established repository structures.

Several SFB's in the field of catalysis and chemical or process engineering are also important discussion and development partners for NFDI4Cat. These initiatives have a natural interest in using infrastructure and tools developed by NFDI4Cat and are willing to share their data.

The TU Berlin, Otto-von-Guericke University Magdeburg and TU Dortmund are participating on the collaboration research centre SFB/TRR 63 “InPrompt – Integrated Chemical Processes in Liquid Multiphase Systems”.

The collaboration research centre SFB/TRR 247 (Heterogeneous Oxidation Catalysis in Liquid Phase, speaker Malte Behrens, co-speaker: Martin Muhler) and the DFG priority programs SPP2080 („Catalysts and reactors under dynamic reaction conditions for energy storage and conversion“, coordinator: Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt, co-speaker: Roger Gläser) have communicated their strong interest and support.

International networking is also a vital part of the work of NFDI4Cat, as any effort in the long run can only be sustained, if it also finds resonance in the international catalysis and engineering scene. Contact has been established with EFCATS, the European catalysis association, NACS, the North American catalysis society, the Boreskov Institute of Catalysis in Russia and RDA, the research data alliance.

To allow for a maximized convenience regarding data exchange in between different platforms, it is also vital to offer a range of different data conversion tools, which can convert information from one data format into another. This capability will ease the adaption of already existing systems like for example the NIST or the NOMAD databases.

Massive synergies are expected from common and accepted data formats and common information architecture following the requirements set by the community:

- The building of strong ties between groups working in modelling and theory and groups and individuals working experimentally and putting these two groups on eyesight level can induce a complete new scientific dialogue.
- Scientific dialogue is enabled and simplified in between the different disciplines in catalysis, as clearly defined data formats will allow a holistic view beyond each single field.
- Better link to engineering sciences will be established as data exchange formats can be better defined and lead to clarity in communication.

The FAIR concept for the treatment of data must be respected on all levels as major design criterion. The catalysis community must be convinced that FAIR is an umbrella definition and scope for dealing with data.

The German Catalysis Society (GeCatS) is the platform for the entire German catalysis community in the area of research and application and has close links with many scientific European, North-American and Asian-Pacific catalysis and chemical engineering organisations via DECHEMA. Currently it has about 1100 members from industry and academia at every career level. It promotes the scientific and technical dialogue between industry, universities, non-university research institutes and research policy institutions and represents the interests of the catalysis community on a national and international level. GeCatS was founded in 2008, integrating the existing catalysis committees in Germany. It is administered by DECHEMA and supported by VDI-GVC, GDCh, DGMK und DBG. As a result of the active partnership of scientific and technical societies, the German Catalysis Society appeals to the whole catalysis community across disciplinary and institutional borders. From scientists investigating catalysis mechanisms on the atomic level to engineers developing large-scale industrial catalytic processes, it spans the whole range of catalysis research and application, resulting in a powerful and dynamic network.

GeCatS is one of the biggest catalysis societies in the world and as such, it is involved in several international activities in the area of catalysis. The German Catalysis Society gave input for the development of the "Science and Technology Roadmap on Catalysis for Europe". It is member of EFCATS (European Federation of Catalysis Research - Delegates Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt, Dieter Vogt) and IACS (International Association of Classification Societies - Delegates Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt, Dieter Vogt) and has hosted and will host international catalysis conferences. The last highlight was the EuropaCat 2019 in Aachen that was organized together with colleagues from the Netherlands and Belgium.

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) is an international hub for competence in research data management efforts. NFDI4Cat will actively get involved with the RDA and be engaged in

working groups and/or interest groups as well as participate in plenary meetings. This makes an international top level networking possible.

2.5 Organisational structure and viability

The consortium NFDI4Cat is organised under the structure of DECHEMA e.V., which is a non-profit professional society. DECHEMA e.V. consolidates the know-how of more than 5,800 individual and sustaining members. The wealth of topics addressed in their scientific bodies, events and projects enables them to work and cooperate across disciplines. In their network, future trends in research and technology are identified, debated in-depth and promptly translated into recommendations for action.

DECHEMA e.V. is the expert network for chemical engineering and biotechnology in Germany since 1926. This non-profit professional society represents these fields in science, industry, politics and society. Around 100 subject divisions and working parties including the German Catalysis Society (GeCatS) offer a forum for knowledge exchange among experts, based on trust. DECHEMA is the coordinator of various national and EU projects, organizes around 50 conferences with over 10000 participants per year, and offers more than 20 training courses on different topics. Coordination and support of DECHEMA's activities is carried out by about 120 employees. DECHEMA therefore has the experience and expertise to professionally and reliably manage and distribute funding for NFDI4Cat as well as to verify its intended use.

Underpinned by the DECHEMA, NFDI4Cat has created its own internal structure that will enable top-class project work (Figure 2-4). The coordination group, consisting of the organisations representing the greatest possible scientific excellence in Germany in the respective core topics of NFDI4Cat, forms the committee that deals primarily with coordination tasks, strategic decisions, budget planning and representative tasks. It is closely linked to the Steering Group of the TAs, which consists of the heads of each TA and one member per partner organization. The steering group is supposed to support the TA leaders and the coordination group as well as to represent and further develop the task areas. The project itself is based on the work of all project partners, who define the tasks, execute the actual project work and ensure proper documentation and analysis. The internal structure is flanked by DECHEMA's project management and the Advisory Council. The Advisory Council is formed by industry representatives of the largest German catalysis companies. This construct is highly useful because research in catalysis is always closely linked to reactions and methods used in industrial processes. The industry can therefore provide very high quality data sets for beta testing of the research data infrastructure as well as give valuable advice on the needs of users. A person with long-term experiences in industrial

catalysis incl. the relevant data management and a lectureship at the University of Leipzig acts as bridge between the academic consortium and the Industrial Advisory Council.

Figure 2-4: Organisational structure of NFDI4Cat

New project partners and associated organisations can be continuously integrated into this structure as they can be assigned to a task area. Close communication within the consortium, but also with external structures, is ensured by tools provided by DECHEMA. This includes the website with a communication area, the scheduling of regular meetings or web meetings and the holding of physical meetings in the form of status conferences and workshops. In addition, the TA leaders will ensure their own forms of communication with the partners.

2.6 Operating model

NFDI4Cat operates as a classical project consortium in which the partners regulate their cooperation by means of a cooperation agreement. DECHEMA e.V. as coordinator secures the non-profit/public benefit nature of the consortium by representing this legal status itself. The co-applicants, and thus all beneficiaries, also represent this status. Through this operating model, the consortium is also prepared to be integrated into a NFDI e.V. that will be founded later as a subunit.

The consortium has got a variety of existing know-how, hardware, repositories and software tools available on which can be built-on and which will be used to ensure a targeted and efficient work on new tools, infrastructures and interfaces to connect existing and new developed data bases, repositories and ontologies. More details can be found in the following paragraphs of the proposal:

- 2.2 Research Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest
- 3.1B Current state and specific expertise, Expertise of information technology partners in NFDI4Cat
- 3.4 Metadata standards
- 3.5 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance
- 5 Overall Funding Request, (Co-) Applicant Contributions

3 Research Data Management Strategy

3.1 Current state and specific expertise

A. Current state of RDM in Catalysis Groups in NFDI4Cat

Catalysis research data is produced in a sequence of steps. In a typical work flow in e.g. heterogeneous catalysis the catalyst materials are first synthesized (often from molecular compounds called precursors) and subsequently treated for performance testing. For catalytic tests the materials are mounted in a reactor and then exposed to the reactants (gases, liquids) in a sequence of reaction conditions (temperature, pressure, flow rates ...). The resulting products or product streams are then analysed with respect to the formed species and their quantity using e.g. GC, MS or other analysis methods. Subsequently the obtained data is processed to calculate or estimate aggregated numbers as a measure of catalyst performance. Such values can be computed and expressed in different ways, e.g. as concentrations, conversion, selectivity, yield, rates, or turnover numbers. These data serve as an input for kinetic and reactor simulations. Based on such simulations catalytic reactors and processes can be designed.

Catalysis research typically aims to elucidate fundamental relationships between the structure of a working catalyst and its activity. Such structure - activity relationships are often indicated by correlations between different data as the result from the described work flow. Structural properties can be obtained either from material analytics before, during or after catalysis via e.g. spectroscopic, diffraction or sorption measurements, or via quantum chemical calculations (bulk and surface structure, active sites, adsorption sites, transition states, energy barriers etc). Activity is typically assessed experimentally via catalytic tests.

While the overall work flow and fundamental concepts are similar in heterogeneous, homogeneous, electro and bio catalysis, each of the disciplines uses slightly different approaches, different nomenclatures, experimental methods as well as property and performance descriptors. Uniting these approaches among all catalysis disciplines will be a part of the challenge of NFDI4Cat.

More and more high-throughput experimentation technologies are available for biocatalytic experiments leading to a vast amount of data that is rapidly growing. In order to avoid complex and unstructured data collection a systematic research data management is required. The comparability, transferability and reproducibility between research groups is often a bottle neck. Open repositories and supporting options such as Data in Brief (Elsevier) are available but still used rather rarely. Guidelines for managing metadata is missing, completeness and also the method of publishing data is dependent on authors, editors and reviewers of scientific journals. Data is only shared with others when they are published and even then only a small fraction publishes a complete set of (meta)data. A valuable metadata

exchange is usually not possible because of time-consuming searches for comparable results and decisive information are often omitted in publications.

Presently, there are some individual guidelines available, e.g., from STRENDA (Standards for Reporting Enzymology Data) or ESAB (European Federation of Biotechnology Section of Applied Biocatalysis) that covers enzymology and biocatalysis data. STRENDA was founded 2004, developed a continuously improving web-based storage and search platform and is recommended by more than 50 international Biochemistry Journals. For enzyme research, the STRENDA Commission has established standards for data reporting with the aim to improve the quality of data published in the scientific literature and to ensure that data sets are complete and validated, allowing scientists to review, reuse and verify them. The emphasis is on providing useful and reliable information. [www.beilstein-institut.de/en/projects/strenda].

Many of the mentioned parameters along the whole workflow are highly interconnected and influence each other. For every step data and metadata are generated and have to be processed and stored. Many measurements also alter the catalyst material; hence a history of the treatment of a catalyst is vital for profound understanding of its properties and behaviour. All mentioned experimental and computational methods require assumptions to be fulfilled, and all measured and computed values are subject to errors and error propagation. High quality data and known error margins are therefore needed in order to enable reliable reactor and process simulations, and to identify fundamental structure-activity relationships.

Experiment data are stored and generated on different levels of complexity and aggregation

- raw data directly obtained from the instrument during an experiment
- processed and aggregated property and performance data
- metadata that describes experimental procedures, conditions and setups
- metadata that describes the data processing
- published data (so far typically a small subset of the above data and metadata categories)

Typical raw data are generated by analytical devices in either open or vendor specific formats. Depending on the data, either open or vendor specific software is used to process the data (e.g. "MestReNova", "Athena"). Often the raw data is processed and converted into common software formats (often Excel or text files). Common software for further processing and plotting of the data includes e.g., Matlab, Origin and SigmaPlot.

In the catalysis community several regional infrastructures for data exchange (DEXPI initiative for the German chemical industry,⁷ in DIN/ISO15926, or SFIHOS activities in the oil

⁷ <https://dexpi.org>

and gas industry.^{8]} bwDataArchive from KIT⁹ and OntoCAPE (Ontology in Process Engineering from RWTH Aachen)¹⁰ were developed and used independently.

The computational scientists in catalysis are more advanced with respect to a proper storage of their respective data. Several databases exist to store especially the results of DFT calculation on solid materials, e.g. the Materials Project¹¹ or NOMAD. There is only a limited variety of DFT codes for solids available and most of the time especially the input files of the respective codes are interchangeable via suitable converters. Storing also the input files leads to a reproducible workflow as information like the surface/molecule geometries is retained, and version control tools (git, subversion) can be used. Some DFT databases are searchable by a programming interface (API) making it possible to re-use the data for example to look for structure with Machine Learning tools. Unfortunately, similar data bases, tools and interfaces do not exist yet for experimental catalysis research.

Exploring the full potential of combined theoretical and experimental catalysis research therefore requires a new level of research data management in catalysis research. It would be of great benefit if experimentalists and theoretically oriented scientist work together more closely to speed up the learning process in natural science. High-throughput experimentation in catalysis (see e.g. Schüth et al.)¹² already necessitates some kind of data management, however, often with locally developed and non-interoperable software of limited functionality, such systems being in place e.g. at LIKAT, BasCat and other applicant labs. Case studies within NFDI4Cat of related data science approaches include e.g. work by the group of Palkovits on CO₂ methanation,¹³ performance predictions using artificial neural networks at LIKAT and the identification of property - performance correlations via meta-analysis of literature data for the oxidative coupling of methane by Kraehnert and co-workers.¹⁴

Data science in catalysis therefore faces many obstacles, many of them related to the current practise of data and metadata management. Challenges include data collected in proprietary formats, a lack of standardized nomenclature and ontology, a lack of open software tools and repositories, ways of linking data and publications consistently and permanently as well as paths to retrieve published data for re-use. Beyond such technical issues, also a change in research culture, RDM literacy and community education and training are required.

⁸ <https://uspi.nl/index.php/projects/frameworks-methodologies/136-cfihos>
⁹ <https://www.rda.kit.edu/>
¹⁰ www.avt.rwth-aachen.de/cms/AVT/Forschung/Software/~ipts/OntoCape
¹¹ *APL Mater* **2013**, *1*, 011002.
¹² *J. Catal.* **2007**, *252*, 205–214.
¹³ *PhD Thesis*, Florian Krebs, Aachen, **2018**.
¹⁴ *Nature Commun.* **2019**, *10*, 441.
¹⁵ *Catal. Sci. Technol.*, *9* (2019) 5111-5121

B. Expertise of information technology partners in NFDI4Cat

HLRS has a strong expertise in data management in the context of high-performance computing. The first High Performance Storage System (HPSS) in Germany was installed in 2008, storing the simulation output files. Since then, the data managed by the system has grown to 22 Petabytes in 11 million files. Design and operation of large-scale compute and data management systems is one of the key skills of the HLRS.

HLRS is task leader for data management within the PRACE project, a pan-European partnership for high-performance computing.

From March 2017 to June 2019, HLRS has been part of the DIPL-ING project, a project for research data management in computational engineering. The main outcomes of this project were the metadata model EngMeta [EngMeta], a prototypical research data repository as well as the automated metadata extraction ExtractIng.

Moreover, the HLRS was involved in the bwDataArchive project (running from 2014-2016) and has gained experience in the design, implementation and deployment in a state-wide archival system.¹⁶

Currently, HLRS is leading the data management effort in the project InHPC-DE, where the three German national HPC centers are working together on the advancement of HPC services in Germany.

Fraunhofer FOKUS develops and maintains **Piveau**¹⁷ an open source data management ecosystem. Piveau is modular, scalable, and already tested in many scenarios. One of its main strengths is that it supports Linked Data for (meta-) data management. Piveau is already used in a variety of different sectors, mostly in the energy, the administration and the science sector. Piveau serves as a basis for the European Data Portal (EDP),¹⁸ which is a central access point for metadata of heterogeneous Open Data published by public authorities in Europe with close to 900.000 datasets, 60 million RDF triples in total, from 77 data providers. In the science sector, Piveau is a platform solution to make scientific data available in a manner that is open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, re-usable). Piveau offers a flexible, modular solution to common challenges. For the envisioned project, most importantly, Piveau offers generic functionality to import, process, and store (meta-)data, that could be implemented in the domain of catalysis.

KIT, O. Deutschmann, CaRMen

NFDI4Cat applicants from KIT have already developed a software tool that addresses a small subset of these challenges in the area of kinetics and reactor simulation in catalysis.

¹⁶ <https://www.rda.kit.edu/>

¹⁷ <https://www.piveau.de/en/>

¹⁸ a) Fabian Kirstein, Benjamin Dittwald, Simon Dutkowski, Yury Glikman, Sonja Schimmler, Manfred Hauswirth: Linked Data in the European Data Portal: A Comprehensive Platform for Applying DCAT-AP. EGOV **2019**: 192-204; b) <https://www.europeandataportal.eu> (Accessed 15th Okt. 2019).

CaRMeN (CAlytic Reaction MEchanisms Network)¹⁹ is designed for the rapid analysis of physical and chemical models against experimental data. It combines tools to archive and package various forms of data with simulation codes in a graphical user interface. It improves the manual workflow of testing various models against experimental data by automating time-consuming and error-prone tasks such as setting up problems (simulations) and post-processing the resulting data. Within the user interface, experimental data can be conveniently compared with the results of any simulation code under the matching experimental conditions in a plug-and-play fashion. CaRMeN can also be used to assess the quality of physical models. Examples include various transport models for porous media (dusty gas vs. Thiele-modulus approach), or different flow models (laminar/plug flow). False measurements in experimental data can be recognized more easily. Critical computer software issues due to programming errors and wrongly-implemented and inadequately used sub models become more obvious, even by users not-so familiar with computing. CaRMeN has been used also in the areas of homogeneous gas-phase reactions (combustion, pyrolysis, engines), chemical and steel industry, fuel and electrolysis cells. Along these lines CaRMeN serves as link between microkinetics and reactor and process engineering. CaRMeN can be extended to work with any simulation code. It has been recently chosen as Research Data Management system for the collaborative DFG projects SFB/TRR 150 and FOR 1993. Extension of the toolbox to links with DFT data and catalyst characterization data from microscopy and spectroscopy would be highly desirable.

At **RWTH Aachen** OntoCAPE has been developed as ontology in process engineering. The principle is described later as example for existing metadata standards.

¹⁹ <https://www.detchem.de/carmen>

3.2 Overview of envisaged RDM implementation

Research data management has to be designed specifically for each discipline in order to address the respective user needs as previously demonstrated by HLRS for the field of computational engineering²⁰ A repository can serve as the centre of all research data management efforts. A repository should enrich the data with metadata for proper curation and therefore make the research data findable, accessible, inter-operable and reusable (FAIR).²¹ Moreover, repositories can reduce the amount of "dark data", i.e. data which is either not curated or forgotten.²²

The current proposal aims for a change in research culture facilitated and supported by technological tools and organizational measures. A hierarchical approach is proposed with a central as well as local confederated repository. The hierarchy is built bottom via individual researchers and work groups, institutions, NFDI4Cat and finally collaborating consortia as well as the overall NFDI structure. A strong focus is placed on local tools that enable users to easily bring research data into the systems, use the data and control the data flow. Clearly defined pathways for the publication of quality-controlled data and full control of the individual users over how, when and to which extend data are published, shared and re-used are part of the proposed concept.

The repository infrastructure for NFDI4Cat is envisioned as layered distributed approach (Figure 3-1). First, it has to integrate existing repository systems. Second, it has to provide a solution for distributed data sources where data is bound to specific storage devices e.g. within an institution. And third, it has to provide a new repository for all data which is planned to be newly ingested to the NFDI4Cat environment without using an existing system at a partner site. For this repository, a metadata-driven approach can be used. As the general description in EngMeta²³ is in accordance with DataCite²⁴, which is a prerequisite for obtaining a DOI, repository software has to be chosen that is able to register a DOI. During the project, repository software should be carefully analysed and selected. No matter what software is selected, the repository has to be designed in a way that it can have multiple, heterogeneous storage backends which might be spatially separated and have different technologies. These backends have to be united in a common shared middleware. In the

²⁰ a) Schembera, Björn, and Thomas Bönisch. "Challenges of research data management for high performance computing." *International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries*. Springer, Cham, **2017**; b) Iglezakis, D., und B. Schembera. „Anforderungen Der Ingenieurwissenschaften an Das Forschungsdatenmanagement Der Universität Stuttgart - Ergebnisse Der Bedarfsanalyse Des Projektes DIPL-ING“. *O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal / Herausgeber VDB*, Bd. 5, Nr. 3, September **2018**, 46–60

²¹ *Sci. Data* **2016**, 3, 160018.

²² Schembera, Björn, and Juan M. Durán. "Dark Data as the New Challenge for Big Data Science and the Introduction of the Scientific Data Officer." *Philosophy & Technology* (2019): 1-23.

²³ <https://www.izus.uni-stuttgart.de/fokus/engmeta/>

²⁴ <https://datacite.org/>

middleware, a central metadata store has to gather all metadata information of all data objects from all backends. Of course, specific requirements have to be addressed. For example, data which is under intellectual property regulations must not be registered in the DOI service and must not get published. The repository has to incorporate measures to address these issues of confidentiality.

Figure 3-1: Linked extensible infrastructure for NFDI4Cat

The upper layer is a central component for querying and search and retrieval of the data from the repository network. This layer interfaces to the available repositories, searches and queries these and links the user to the specific repository for retrieval. For access control, an authentication and role based authorization system needs to be designed and established. This means, the NFDI4Cat repository system has to be developed as a layered architecture: A distributed storage layer as the technological base for a middleware layer that is the core of the service. On top of this, a user layer with graphical user interface (GUI) and command line interface (CLI) handles the interaction with the users and integrates the provided distributed repositories. The layered architecture of the technology base of the central repository intends to ensure a user experience of maximum convenience and focussed on minimal response times. The consortium is of the opinion that user acceptance is a central prerequisite and existing web-based applications set a high standard with regard to performance and user experience which need to be matched up to a certain level of expectation.

Equally important, the availability of local is vital to enable a seamless and steady flow of data and metadata into the repository. The local tools should facilitate easy data collection and quality assurance along the whole work flow of heterogeneous catalysis research in order to do better experiments and research, including experiment planning, synthesis, testing, data processing, visualization, evaluation and modelling. The envisioned tools and methods should make it easy to non-experts to obtain good data, e.g. via data driven quality assurance (automatic outlier detection, consistency checks, error estimates), facile planning of experiments via semi-automatic Design of Experiments (DOE) methods that run along with the data acquisition, means of automatic documentation of important parameters of synthesis, testing and data processing and metadata generation. Easy to use tools and low entry barriers are highly desirable. Moreover, educating catalysis researchers in quality assurance via easy access to examples, tutorial, standard procedures and reference materials will be vital.

User engagement is vital for the success of NFDI4Cat. In general, NFDI4Cat will focus to solve existing problems of the community, not to create new obstacles. The user community and all fields of catalysis research are well represented in the organization structure of NFDI4Cat. Already prior to NFDI, the community developed, discussed and published a roadmap and requirements for a digitalization process in catalysis research. In the proposal planning phase, user conferences were held and potential users submitted feedback, ideas and requests based on electronic questionnaires. Interacting with users and fully integrating them into the development, testing and scaling of NFDI4Cat will ensure acceptance and success of the endeavour. Main aspects of potential user acceptance resulting from this consultation are e.g. low entry barriers, ready-to-use, open and extendable software tools, training measures, and in particular full control over the data publication process, data sharing and IP related concerns, all of which will be addressed in NFDI4Cat.

User needs will thus also be monitored in the future on a regular basis e.g. via beta testers, regular questionnaires distributed within the community, special sessions and regular training measures along annual national catalysis conferences, organized and managed by DECHEMA as a representative of the whole community. The user feedback will be vital to adjust NFDI4Cat at a technical, organisational as well as structural level.

To achieve user-friendly tools, user acceptance test will be carried out at several stages. Except for the early development state, involving testers from outside NFDI4Cat is considered essential. Only by carefully listening to user feedback the envisage popularity of the platform and tools can be realised.

3.3 Data Quality Management

Quality assurance (QA) is an integral part of catalysis research. However, many methods are costly in terms of resources. Thus, the level at which QA measures are implemented currently in public research labs widely varies. Moreover, these methods are not fully standardized, and rely also on the individual research and reporting standards. Common QA measures in performance testing include tests for catalyst stability, the test for potential restricting during reaction, the assessment of mass and heat transport limitation (many of the commandments that are known in catalysis research),²⁵ the calculation of mass balances and error estimation via repeated measurements at different levels (repeated analytical runs, repeated testing, repeated synthesis, ...).²⁶ Other potential measures include device calibration, the automatic generation of log files, and the storage of raw data for later re-processing.

However, for many of the experimental planning, measuring and documentation steps no common standards exist. Lab books are still typically hand-written and not connected to data bases. Reactor, setup and analytics configurations are often not stored and reported along with the results, which also applied to the data processing routines. Hence, the currently derived data are often incomplete and not obtained via consistent procedures. Even in optimal cases the obtained data will be incomplete by nature, since not all details of synthesis steps, measurements or data processing can be currently documented with reasonable effort. Often, an individual's experience determines data quality, and a complete set of QA measures has not been implemented so far in openly available software for catalysis research.

However, the need for benchmarking and best practice procedures has been recognized in some recent literature focused on electro catalysis, where in particular the lack of addressing catalyst stability and changes during testing has led to strongly varying performance numbers for supposedly similar.²⁷ Despite the realization of the general importance of benchmarking procedures,²⁸ reference catalysts, best practice procedures, benchmarking protocols, common reporting standards as well as tools and software that support QA in heterogeneous catalysis are not commonly available yet to the research community.

The issue of quality management will therefore be addressed on different levels. NFDI4Cat aims in particular for the highest standards already at the initial state of data creation. Thus,

²⁵ ACS Symposium Series **1989**, 411, 99–119.

²⁶ <https://eurokin.org/?cat=30>

²⁷ a) *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, 137, 4347–4357; b) *ChemSusChem* **2017**, 10, 4140–4143; c) *ACS Catal.* **2017**, 7, 3768–3778.

²⁸ *ACS Catal.* **2016**, 6, 2590–2602.

best practice procedures and benchmarking routines for catalysis experiments will be developed together with the community. For reactions reference samples will be established. This development will be initiated for catalytic reactions and specific use cases addressed within NFDI4Cat, but also aim at a generalization for the different catalysis disciplines. The results will be documented as guidance and teaching materials.

In general, all data measured according to minimum experimental standards will be considered for the NFDI consortium. However, essential quality checks and quality ratings will be implemented also in the developed software tools and guide the users in the quest of creating better data and documentation, e.g. metadata. The issue of improved metadata is addressed in parts by the automatic generation of metadata along the way of measuring, processing and curating. Moreover, on the different levels of NFDI4Cat algorithms for quality control, quality rating and recommendations for improvement of the data and metadata will be implemented. Exemplarily, this will be reflected in complementary software tools for visualization, for computing statistical measures of data distribution and diversity, in algorithms and indicators for outlier detection, and consequently in tools that guide the design of experiments (DOE), which can operate also iteratively to produce data suited to answer specific catalysis related research questions. Also here, user friendliness, low entry barriers for new users and seamless integration into a typical catalysis research work flow will have the utmost priority.

Means of community engagement will include regular questionnaires distributed within the community, community conferences, special sessions and regular training measures along annual national catalysis conferences, user conferences, user feedback for developed tools and a regular evaluation of direction and impact of NFDI4Cat via community evaluation organized and managed by DECHEMA.

3.4 Metadata standards

Metadata is the crucial point to make research data FAIR. Every discipline needs appropriate description criteria for their data; however some attributes are the same across all disciplines.

EngMeta, which was developed for the use case of computational engineering at HLRS and the Stuttgart University Library.²⁹ pays tribute to this fact and tries to balance generic and domain-specific parts. For a good metadata description respectively, an ontology that matches the described research object, four generic categories of description attributes were identified: Descriptive metadata offers general information about the data, such as a title or keywords describing the data. Technical metadata provides information about the data

²⁹ <https://www.izus.uni-stuttgart.de/fokus/engmeta/>

objects, for example their size or their checksum. Process metadata describes the process of creating data, such as involved methods, experimental or computational hardware. Domain-specific metadata serves as the domain-specific description for the respective field of research.

During our research we found that these four are the core categories for every metadata description. The first two categories (descriptive and technical metadata) are generic for all scientific disciplines, whereas process metadata has to incorporate already discipline-specific information.

The goal of every further development of ontologies or metadata standards has to incorporate the idea of the four metadata categories. Moreover, it must shape the latter two categories for the specific needs of the discipline.

In the case of NFDI4Cat, existing metadata schemes have to be analysed and checked for which of the four categories are already existing and what has to be adapted. Especially the accordance of EngMeta and the Chemical Markup Language (CML)³⁰ has to be evaluated and elements have to be incorporated. Since existing databases already work with CML, compatibility with this standard is crucial.

The metadata required in catalysis research is quite extensive. The outcome of catalytic experiments is highly dependent on an immense number of parameters, all of which impact e.g. the resulting properties, performance and stability of a resulting catalyst in its working environment. Among other things, all of these parameters should become documented metadata in the presented approach. Exemplarily for heterogeneous, this requires (1) A description of the components, processing steps and processing conditions (T , p , gases, ...) during the synthesis of the catalyst. (2) The catalyst pretreatment steps (calcination, reduction) and sequence of operation conditions (p , T , gas composition, flow rates, ...) determine the working state and behaviour of a catalyst. All metadata from (1) and (2) form the history of this catalyst, where also the order of treatments can make a huge difference. (3) The reactor environment used for testing (size, shape, flow characteristics ...) needs to be documented. (4) The analytical equipment used to assess a catalysts performance (technical components, calibration, sensitivity, detection limits) describes what can be measured at all, and within which error bars. (5) Techniques of material characterization provide results that highly depend on the specification and operation conditions of the applied analytical device depending on the analysis technique and the respective type of data obtained. (6) The modelling of catalytic reactors includes typically a large number of parameters as well as assumptions that are required to build up useful models. It is clear that by nature such metadata sets will be always incomplete. Moreover, even the "minimum set of

³⁰ *J. Cheminform.* **2011**, *3*, 43.

metadata" cannot be defined a priori but highly depends on the specific application, reaction and aim of the respective experiment or investigation.

In the CaRMeN toolbox, the metadata should include all original (raw) data of the experimental measurements, the processing chain of these data, intermediate results, and also dates and personal conducting the measurements as well as publications based on these measurements. The metadata are needed to generate input files for the numerical simulation of the reactors, in which kinetic data have been measured. *Drivers* use these metadata to combine the experiment with the specific reactor/process simulation software (e.g. CFD simulation) and to set-up the input files for the numerical simulation. For instance information of catalyst material and loading, porosity of the support structure, volumetric flow rates, temperature profiles, inlet mixtures etc. are automatically linked to the models. The user can always directly access these metadata from the user interface to retrieve specific information needed. The format of the original and metadata is rather flexible, new formats, reactors, processes etc. just require a specific new driver.

For each simulation run using CaRMeN a data package is generated. It is planned to extend the CaRMeN toolbox with a user accessible repository where these data packages can be stored and published.

The packages need to contain the raw data of the experimental measurements and its associated metadata (reactor used, date, personnel conducting measurements, ...) as well as unique identifiers and the order of all data pre-processors (so called *Loaders*). Together with the information about which *Mixin* (e.g. reaction mechanism) and which *Driver* was used, one can recreate the exact simulation results by applying the *Loaders* on the raw data in the correct order and then running the specified *Driver*.

Additionally, the package contains the unique identifiers and the order of the *Loaders* that were used to post-process the simulation results.

By storing uses of CaRMeN in this fashion, published results, for example, are easily reproducible by anyone using CaRMeN.

We also avoid storing duplicate information that way and therefore keep the memory footprint at a minimum.

It will also be possible to publish individual *Loaders*, reactor definitions and other "building blocks". In combination with an accessible, intuitive user interface and a comprehensive search function, which lets users find such "building blocks" or even complete results that fit their needs, this achieves a high level of reusability.

Figure 3-2: Structure of planned CaRMEn data packages (simplified).

The development of ontologies and data standards has a long tradition in process engineering, particularly driven by the process systems engineering activities.³¹ Data standards and exchange are very important in automation and control of chemical plants. These activities include the transfer of data from modelling to actual representation of a plant state and its influence on the control strategy (model-predictive control). In process engineering projects to develop chemical processes and construct plants, data exchange is important from early process design, laboratory experiments, and equipment design to plant construction and commissioning.³² These aspects are partially treated in the DEXPI initiative for the German chemical industry,³³ in DIN/ISO15926, or SFIHOS activities in the oil and gas industry.³⁴

The most elaborated ontology in process engineering is probably OntoCAPE developed at RWTH Aachen with own homepage.³⁵ Figure 3-3 gives an overview of the different layers of OntoCAPE.

³¹ Marquardt, W., Morbach, J., Wiesner, A., Yang, A., *OntoCAPE: A Re-Usable Ontology for Chemical Process Engineering*, Springer, Berlin, **2010**.

³² *Reac. Chem. Eng.* **2019**, *4*, 1522–1529.

³³ <https://dexpi.org>

³⁴ <https://uspi.nl/index.php/projects/frameworks-methodologies/136-cfihos>

³⁵ www.avt.rwth-aachen.de/cms/AVT/Forschung/Software/~ipts/OntoCape

Figure 3-3: Structure and Layers of OntoCAPE. ³⁶[Mor09]

Chemical reactions are represented by the reaction mechanism, but no properties of the catalyst itself are used (Figure 3-4). There are additional modules to cover thermodynamic data of compounds or to describe multi-phase systems, based on thermodynamic and transport properties

³⁶ Morbach, J., A Reusable Ontology for Computer-Aided Process Engineering, Dissertation RWTH Aachen, 2009.

Figure 3-4: Ontology module reaction mechanism.³⁷

The existing systematic of OntoCAPE tries to cover the description of compounds as molecules with their properties as a pure substance as shown for oxygen (Figure 3-5).

Figure 3-5: Ontological representation of Oxygen and of a chemical component with physical properties.³⁸

This short description of OntoCAPE will serve as an example, which data are necessary and how they might be organised. Catalysts and reactors are mainly represented by their costs, not by performance data or even structures in case of catalysts. The multitude of typical reactors, particularly for the different phases and contact mechanism as well as the heat integration is not covered.

An overview of library information system is given by Warr and Suhr.³⁹ A recently opened catalysis data hub of limited focus and insecure future funding with its own ontology can be found under Catalysis-Hub.org.⁴⁰ [This platform is an US-based initiative with partners in Stanford University and the US Dpt. of Energy among others.

³⁷ Morbach, J., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., Material, Technical Report LPT-2008-27, **2008**.

³⁸ Morbach, J., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., Material, Technical Report LPT-2008-27, **2008**.

³⁹ W.A. Warr, C. Suhr, Chemical information management. VCH, Weinheim, **1992**.

⁴⁰ *Sci. Data* **2019**, 6, 75.

Current needs in ontology and metadata standards besides the ones describing the catalyst itself are the

- description of the catalyst under conditions of a technical process
- types of reactors and operating conditions (batch, conti, temperatur management,...)
- representation of important unit operations such as extraction, absorption, adsorption, and desorption, membrane technology and crystallization
- assistance of process modelling and control⁴¹ [Eng18]
- material science

Without being complete a number of factors are depicted in Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-6: Examples for important factors for the performance of a catalyst to be considered for ontology and metadata organisation

With the close linkage of the research fields of molecular science, catalysis, reactor and process technology, novel combination can be addressed. Experimental and simulation data can be discussed in a wider view of influence of boundary conditions and the mutual influence of different parameters. Interconnections and relations between the different parameters can be addressed, which was not possible in the past. Historical data can be retrieved and made visible for future investigations. This needs a concise ontology for the interlinked fields, rapid data search machines, decentralized data repositories for historical and current data as well as quality management for data quality and reliability. If possible,

⁴¹ G. Engel, T. Greiner, S. Seifert, Ontology-Assisted Engineering of Cyber-Physical Production Systems in the Field of Process Technology, IEEE Trans. Ind. Informatics, 14(6) 2792–2802, 2018.

reproducibility of experimental and simulation results should be checked automatically and will be a future important review part for publishing novel results.

As proposed by Edwards, metadata is not just "data about data", but it has its „role in an Ephemeral process of scientific communication, rather than as an enduring outcome or product.⁴² This means designing a metadata model never comes to an end but is an important part of scientific communication.

However, one needs to have a starting point which can then be - according to the above definition - iteratively improved and adapted. As a very first step in the development of EngMeta, the scientific workflow was analysed. It can be divided in the 3 main phases of data production, data analysis and publication in the case of computational engineering. Then, it was checked which data is processed in each of the three steps and how this data and the processes themselves could be possibly described. This led to an object model description of the research process and provided a full picture of the scientific workflow in a formalized way. This formalized scientific workflow description (the object model) was then transformed to a metadata model, where the object properties had to be further developed. It was found out that four main categories of metadata fields can be determined, which are descriptive metadata, subject specific metadata, process metadata and technical metadata. HLRS also found out that both descriptive and technical metadata are very much the same for many areas of research. For example, every dataset is characterized by a name, a description, a keywords a.s.o. and has certain attributes such as the file size or the format. Also, process metadata is mostly the same, at least in a bigger discipline. This part of the metadata describes the process leading to the research data. This can be either computational resources or experimental equipment, but also the actors involved. Moreover, a subject specific part has to cover all the information which is specific to a field of science.

⁴² *Soc. Stud. Sci.* **2011**, *41*, 667–690.

Figure 3-7: Metadata fields in EngMeta⁴³

In EngMeta, HLRS shaped this category for computational engineering in thermo- and aerodynamics and the result of the metadata description can be seen in Figure 3-7. Developing a metadata model can only be successful along these general steps explained above. (1) The analysis of the scientific workflow. (2) This workflow has to be modelled in a meaningful object model. (3) This object model has to be transformed into a rich metadata model (which includes more details and contains the object properties as well). (4) This model has to be converted to a machine readable format, such as XML.

Only by experience it can be determined, if the expectations regarding the description can be met. This is the real meaning of metadata development as a process: When the above steps are done, this does not mean that a metadata development is over but iterative improvements come in play.

EngMeta was designed for computational engineering along the general steps, and with the use of existing metadata schemes. Single existing schemes already cover parts of the model. For example, PREMIS is used for the technical a metadata and DataCite for the descriptive part. The later also allows the obtaining a DOI for the described dataset. Moreover, ExptML for experimental equipment description and CodeMeta for software description were incorporated into EngMeta.

Metadata Extraction

When a metadata model with a rather broad description is developed, the question arises how all this metadata information can be collected. During the research for EngMeta, an automated metadata extraction has been developed. Lots of metadata is already available

⁴³ <https://www.izus.uni-stuttgart.de/fokus/engmeta/>

through the input, output and log files of the simulation codes in a structured or semi-structured form in computational engineering. One first has to distinguish the four categories: Technical metadata, process metadata and domain-specific metadata is in general good to extract automatically, whereas descriptive metadata is hard to extract. This is due to the fact that the metadata information from first three categories already exists in some files. The automated metadata extraction was generically developed for computational engineering, and one of its use cases was thermodynamics simulation with GROMACS. In GROMACS, information on the computational environment is scattered through various output- and log-files of the code. The automated extraction of metadata was programmed to collect this metadata from different sources. After the collection this data is parsed and transferred into the EngMeta scheme. The extraction is generic in a sense that the parsing of the files is directed by a configuration file, meaning that the extraction is configurable for different simulation codes and outputs and even user generated files, without changes in the code. For NFDI4Cat, the metadata extraction has to be adapted. Right now, it is designed for supercomputer and clusters and for Linux environments. For the usage in the NFDI4Cat infrastructure, more platforms and also experimental instruments have to be included. Moreover, sample configuration files have to be developed for these instruments or simulation codes, if applicable. The automated metadata extraction is written in Java, so it is in principle compatible with a manifold of platforms. It was also successfully tested for Windows environments. Last, Extracting has to be adapted to one or more specific metadata standards, if EngMeta is not used. Right now, EngMeta is the only metadata model which is supported by the metadata extraction. This would include mapping a formal metadata standard to Java classes, which can be performed mostly automatically.

3.5 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance

NFDI4Cat aims to implement the FAIR principles via technical, organizational and legal measures.

Findability is assured by globally unique and persistent identifiers. Organizational and technical measures will be implemented to enrich the data manually and semi-automatically with metadata along the work flow of data creation and processing. The metadata will be indexed and a search will be implemented across the whole repository. Respective procedures and software tools will be developed and open sourced.

The meta will become accessible via a repository. Starting from the central repository, the respective data can be retrieved from a centralized or local storage place. The implemented protocols will be open, free and universal, and coordinated with other related NFDIs. The protocol will allow for and require an authentication. The centrally stored part of the metadata will stay accessible also when the respective local data is no longer available.

Figure 3-8: Data flow within NFDI4Cat

The (meta)data will become interoperable by developing standardized formats in collaboration with related NFDIs. The metadata aim for unified formats throughout the different disciplines of catalysis research, but also coordinated with material science and engineering. Also the vocabulary will follow fair principles. Metadata will be able to reference to other metadata.

Data will be re-usable. Implemented procedures and quality measures will assure accurate and relevant attributes. In collaboration with community clear and accessible data usage licences will be developed. The licences are of particular importance as a corner stone of potential reward models for the users that generate high-quality data. Data and meta-data standards will be developed along with and tailored for the community in order to foster highest acceptance and usability.

Quality assurance will be implemented on many different levels. Procedures, best-practise guides and software tools will be developed that help to plan, conduct and evaluate experiments. For data entering the local repository, quality control and quality ratings will be in place. Algorithms will be developed to assess data quality, but also to propose better experiments and designs-of-experiment. Educating the community in good experimental, evaluation and research data practise will be integral in the project. A stepwise development, along with a transformation of the community, will assure that the measures will stay viable also in the future.

3.6 Service provides by the consortium

For catalysis research, a distributed repository environment will be required. This will include existing repositories, newly created repositories as well as a central repository hosted by HLRS Stuttgart. This way, we can build a flexible environment that fulfills the needs of the different laboratories. Each repository will allow for data import and export, and also will comprise other domain-specific functionality. Each repository will also enable publishing the data, which includes the assignment of respective DOIs.

On top of this repository layer, a metadata portal will be setup. This portal provides an easy access point for all the data that is available in the different repositories. This includes search functionality that can be used by both, humans and machines.

This presentation layer further provides some domain-agnostic functionality.

Figure 3-9: Workflow within NFDI4Cat and with other NFDI.

Part of the offered services will be the development of software, i.e. a locally operated tool chain that follows the work flow of typical catalysis research (see Figure 3-9) and facilitates a very low entry barrier to a data driven approach. The offered tools will enhance the data and metadata aspects of each of the steps. The software will be developed and maintained as open source and will be made accessible to the community via training measures.

The software enables (1) data importing, storage and curation in a local data base to manage all data of a research group, provide import options for existing report files, a semi-automatic / assisted metadata enrichment, automatic consistency checks indicating lack of data quality, missing data, potential experimental errors and provide estimated error bars. (2) Tools for data quality assessment provide visualization, outlier detection, statistical evaluation, as well as consistency checks. An integrated DOE is aimed for as well as tools for simple import of literature and repository data. (3) Reporting and publishing tools provide

means to report also data quality, enable data curation for modelling, and facilitate data selection and processing for publication.

Required service for quality assurance in catalysis

Tools, services and software to realize this vision are needed in several key areas. Tools for better measurements include a set of recommended measuring procedures, of benchmarking protocols, reference catalysts and ideally a centralized benchmarking and catalyst testing facility that provides access to best-practice catalyst testing for all researchers.

Tools for QA in data processing includes standard software or libraries for processing routines, a common nomenclature, and approaches to document all processing routines along with the processed data.

QA in data importing, storage and curation would require local data base to manage all data of a research group, to provide parsers that import existing report files into the data base, a semi-automatic / assisted metadata enrichment, automatic consistency checks indicating lack of data quality, missing data, and potential experimental errors and provide estimated error bars.

Tools for better data quality assessment should provide the ability to visualize existing data, detect outliers, simple statistical evaluation of data quality, significance testing and reproducibility as well as consistency checks against older data. An integrated DOE would help to focus new experiments to either to explore new regions in parameter space, improve statistical significance of potential findings, or aim for improved catalyst performance. Moreover, tools for simple import of literature and other data would enable a comparison and consistency check against published data.

Finally also reporting and publishing tools should provide means to report also data quality, enable data curation for modelling, and facilitate data selection and processing for publication.

Improved procedure, tutorials, recommendations

On a different level procedures and recommendations will be developed that provide guidelines for better research and experiments, i.e. recommended measuring procedures, benchmarking protocols, reference catalysts and a centralized benchmarking and catalyst testing facility. Quality assurance will be a central aspect, i.e. via standard software or libraries for processing routines, a common nomenclature, and approaches to document all processing routines along with the processed data.

4 Work Programme

4.1 Overview of task areas

The work programme was structured into eight task areas (TA) as listed in Table 4.1.1. The task areas TA1 and TA2 address the challenge to collect data including metadata in the various catalysis disciplines. All steps in catalyst research, that is synthesis, characterisation and testing, are addressed from different partners. As describe in section 3.1, all sub disciplines of catalysis are still at a rudimentary state and need to evolve from there. This early state is a great chance to reduce the faceting in the community by developing data and metadata standards together. For example, the synthesis data (recipe and process variables of all processing steps) of a solid catalyst is equally important in electro catalysis and in heterogeneous catalysis. Another example is catalyst performance testing which has a lot in common (in term of data) for several sub-disciplines. While catalyst research is diverse, the output for a reaction engineer or process engineer has to be very similar. Thus, therefore a data which flow outbound (from catalysis research to engineering) unification of data and metadata will have tremendous advantages.

Figure 4-1: Project structure scheme to represent the actual work being done, the funded participants in the catalysis disciplines, engineering and data science (lower part) and the information technologies (top) that are supported by accompanying activities.

The measures in TA1 and TA2 have been developed against this background. They try to bring together all catalysis disciplines as well as partners from different position on the *value chain from molecule to process*. Initially ontologies are developed that are used to derive a

metadata standards specification. Based on this specification “local” (one place, one discipline) and local-extended (one place, multiples catalysis disciplines or catalysis & engineering or catalysis & data science) are developed, tested, improved and finally linked to the meta-data portal. This *Linked Extensible Infrastructure and Access Management* is built in Task Area 4 by information technology experts.

In Task area TA3 “Data Analysis, Quality Management and Re-Use” address data curation and explore several “data-to-value” ideas.

The important community and user related aspects are addressed in the TaskAreas TA5 “Dissemination and Outreach/Training” and TA6 “Networking with NFDIs, SFBs and International” and TA7 “Intellectual Property and Confidentiality, Licences and Reward models”.

Table 4.1.1: Taskareas and links to subchapter with details on the Measures. Each TaskArea has group of Spokespersons.

TA#	Task Area	Measures	Responsible Co-Spokesperson(s)
1	Ontology Development and Metadata Standards	See 4.2	Beller/Linke, Kockmann, Haumann
2	Data standards, Data Collection, Interfaces	See 4.3	Krähnert, Özaslan Deutschmann/Studt/Grunwaldt, Beller/Linke, Bornscheuer
3	Data Analysis, Quality Management and Re-Use	See 4.4	Krähnert/Müller
4	Linked Extensible Infrastructure and Access Management	See 4.5	Resch/Bönisch, Schimmler
5	Dissemination and Outreach/Training	See 4.6	Gläser, Kragl, Palkovits
6	Networking with NFDIs, SFBs and International	See 4.7	Wagemann, Gläser,
7	Intellectual Property and Confidentiality , Licences and Reward models	See 4.8	Gläser, Beller/Linke
8	Management	See 4.9	Wagemann

4.2 Ontology development and metadata standards (TA1)

The co-applications from the catalysis and engineering disciplines will first develop ontologies and metadata standards. HLRS will assist in the ontology development and the development of the metadata schemes with its experience from developing EngMeta within the DIPL-ING project. The approach used there is shown in chapter 3.4 and is also promising for the catalysis field as here also several scientific domains are combined.

Measure 1: Develop/extend ontologies for catalyst synthesis data

Measure 2: Develop/extend ontologies for catalyst performance data

Measure 3: Develop/extend ontologies for reactor engineering

Measure 4: Develop/extend ontologies for process engineering

The Ontologies in M1-M3 will be developed jointly by the catalysis applicants. For catalyst synthesis data, process engineering will be also involved to address unit operations of the preparation. Synergies can be also expected in the ontology development for performance testing and reaction engineering.

Measure 5 Develop/extend ontologies for catalysis-specific characterisation data

It is expected that characterisation relevant for catalysis is not fully covered in NFDI4Chem activities. Therefore missing techniques will be addressed here.

Measure 6 Develop/extend ontologies operando data

The developed of the ontology/metadata for operando data will be built upon the work in M2 and M5.

Measure 7 Metadata standards for catalyst synthesis data

Measure 8 Metadata standards for catalyst performance data

Measure 9 Metadata standards for reactor engineering

Measure 10 Metadata standards for catalysis-specific characterisation data

Measure 11 Metadata standards for operando data

Measure 12 Metadata standards for process engineering

The metadata standard will be developed based on the ontologies from M1-M6. Metadata standards will be drafted, discussed within NFDI4Cat and later discussed with the community.

Measure/Milestone M1: Consolidate metadata standards for basic pilot design

Measure/Milestone M2: Consolidate metadata standards for extended pilot design

The metadata form a key building element for the local pilots that will be designed and build at most places. Extended pilots that include data from different disciplines or different stages in the value chain *from molecule to process* will be developed, implemented and tested at TUB (with FOKUS), KIT and LIKAT. LIKAT has planned a two-stage development that starts with homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis and extends to photo-catalysis and operando data in the 2nd stage.

4.3 Data Standards, Data Collection and Interfaces (TA2)

Collaboration with other Task Areas

This task area will collaborate with several other task areas of this effort. The deployment of the metadata scheme will be done together with TA1.

A close collaboration with TA4 is required to setup and deploy the tools for data acquisition. For the development of interfaces the both TAs need to work together, too. Together with TA3 the interoperability of the analysis tools with the infrastructures is in focus. The outreach and training effort in TA5 will be supported with specific information about the infrastructure and its interplay. In addition, it will be supported with material about the services. TA 6 has a direct link to this task area as several developments in the infrastructure and concerning the services shall be harmonised and synchronized.

The findings of TA 7 concerning confidentiality will have an influence on the access policy based authorization management for the infrastructure.

Data standards

Catalysis research produces experimental data in many different formats, with different content, and often not well-defined nomenclature. Some of the data is trapped in proprietary file formats. Even the amount and type of data that is required to describe a catalytic experiment is not fully defined yet. Thus, definitions or recommendations of the extent of data that describe experiments in a reasonably complete fashion need to be developed. Moreover, also formats for each type of data have to be specified.

The data that needs to be described covers the whole work flow of catalysis research. It starts with catalyst synthesis and performance measurements, the characterization of catalyst materials before and after catalysis, and possibly also during catalysis (operando), and includes also the reactor engineering and the process design. While all of these steps are connected to each other, each of these steps has very specific requirements that need to be standardized and addressed. The work of developing data standards is therefore subdivided into different measures (#1 - #6) with a different focus and different contributors from the respective fields. This subdivision will be used also later on in this task area to enable a better description of the related effort and resources.

Data standards will be defined in the first two project years.

Measure 1: Data standards for catalyst synthesis data

The catalyst performance data such as conversion and selectivity as function of operating conditions will be linked to the synthesis data for reliable evaluation of the catalyst. This link is in particular challenging for heterogeneous catalysts due to the complexity and large number of influencing parameters including information on support, syntheses conditions, pre-cursor material. Therefore, novel data standards need to be developed.

Measure 2: Data standards for catalyst performance data

The digital integration of the catalyst synthesis and performance data into models for reactor and process engineering is another challenge. Data formats will be established that support automatic archiving of experimental and theoretical information on the catalytic system in the context of the laboratory and technical reactor.

Measure 3: Data standards for reactor engineering

The digital integration of the catalyst synthesis and performance data into models for reactor and process engineering is another challenge. Data formats will be established that support automatic archiving of experimental and theoretical information on the catalytic system in the context of the laboratory and technical reactor.

Measure 4: Data standards for catalysis-specific characterisation data

The characterization data will focus on the identification of the number of active sites, their structure and allow a comparison of catalytic performance data. Hence, storage of relevant data to gain insight into these properties should be preferentially stored with each sample. The whole workflow to receive the number of active sites and the structure should be described. These workflows should be developed exemplarily for some techniques, e.g. NMR (molecular catalysis), TEM/XRD/chemisorption for supported catalysts (dispersion), XPS, XANES/EXAFS, XES for surface structure and composition, Characterization data from some techniques applied in catalysis may also be addressed in NFDI4Chem or FAIRmat.

Measure 5: Data standards for operando data

In many catalysts, structural changes occur during activation, start of the reaction and during reaction. Hence, data standards have to be developed that connect the structural evolution with that of the catalytic properties so that they can be put into microkinetic models and also allow molecular modelling of the structural changes. In certain cases it is not sufficient to collect data in global manner but to identify structure and performance in spatially resolved manner to allow for multiscale modelling. Hence, in pilot projects one should develop a) data

standards for structural data to compare different techniques, b) connect them with space and time and c) connect them with other data like catalytic properties. Due to space and time one of the critical issues is big data volumes and data analysis routines. In case of X-ray and neutron data joint efforts should be realized with DAPHNE.

Measure 6: Data standards for process engineering

The data standards of measures 1-6 will provide the basis for the data standards to be developed for process engineering. Here, data standards will be defined that allow direct use of the data describing the catalyst and the reactor in process engineering studies. Therefore, the data need to be linked to computer simulation tools to upscale from laboratory to the technical application and integration in to system analysis software.

Measure 7: Interface specification for local repositories (in-/outbound data flow)

The interface specification for local repositories builds upon the (meta-)data standards defined in TA 1 and TA2.

Furthermore, flexible interfaces will be developed to permit links to local repositories, which is essential to use the developed tools by broad community and combined the very valuable knowledge of their existing local repositories, which are very diverse in format.

Experimental data in catalysis can be generated by a vast number of different devices. In order to enable the transfer of this data into RDM systems, interfaces have to be specified. Moreover, such data interfaces also need to provide a connection back to the experimentalists systems, e.g. in order to plan and run new experiments. In addition, interfaces need to be specified between local data processing tools and the overall repository.

Data interfaces can exist on different levels of data complexity, ranging from raw data provided by a single technical device (e.g. a single run of a gas chromatograph) up to highly aggregated and already processed aggregated data (e.g. conversion and selectivity as a function of temperature, pressure and contact time). Thus, interface specifications are required on the different levels in order to enable data transfer into the RDM system. Such defined interfaces will enable the development of software tools for data import into RDM system. Moreover, they can serve as a guideline for device vendors to generate in the future more easily processable data.

The measure therefore addresses the specification of different types of interfaces. The incoming data flow will address the connection to existing procedures, devices and other sources that provide data for the local RDM systems. Also interfaces for outgoing will be specified, e.g. in order to transfer information back to the experimental setups.

Similarly, interfaces need to be specified for processed experimental data that is further transferred from local tools into repositories, i.e. published into the repository and beyond. The interfaces need to be clear and transparent in order to allow full control of what data is being published, with whom it will be shared, and what is the included level of quality control. Similarly, interfaces will be defined for inbound data that is downloaded from the repository into local software tools for further local processing.

Interfaces will be specified in the first two project years.

Data collection tools (Measure 8 – 12)

Data collection tools comprise a set of tools in terms of software and defined procedures that facilitate the import and integration of experimental data into an RDM system as well as enrichment with automatically and manually provided metadata. Quality assurance is an integral part of each type of data acquisition and must be facilitated by both, the methods as well as the software tools.

The work of developing tools and procedures is therefore subdivided into different measures (#8 - #12) with a different focus and different contributors from the respective fields. This subdivision will be used also later on in this task area to enable a better description of the related effort and resources.

Tooling will be developed in years two to four.

Measure 8: Tooling for data collection of catalyst synthesis data

Catalyst synthesis is still mostly manual. Thus, data collection will ideally be realized via ELNs for manual process. For robotic synthesis (e.g. at LIKAT) data are already in available in digital form. However, the formats are manufacturer specific. Therefore, tools are needed to convert to the new standards that NFDI4Cat will develop.

Measure 9: Tooling for data collection of catalyst performance data

The derivation of catalyst performance data is conducted in a variety of different catalytic laboratory-scale experiments using many different reactors such as flow reactors, fixed beds, and differentially operated reactors. The use and analysis of the data of those different set-ups in a comparable way demands digital tools that facilitate the comparison of the catalyst performance data under those varying conditions, their development is the measure taken here.

Measure 10: Tooling for data collection of reactor engineering

The optimization of reaction engineering of reactors and plants calls for an efficient implementation of a huge number of catalyst performance data combined with synthesis and

characterization data into data collection tools that are useable for scale-up and reactor and process design and optimization. These collection tools will be developed in this measure.

Measure 11: Tooling for data collection of catalysis-specific characterization data

Catalysis-specific characterization data are very essential information related to the structure-activity relation of catalyst performance. The tooling of those data collections will be the core of this measure. Since the catalysis-specific characterization data are very heterogeneous in different data collections, filters have to be developed to easy access the information needed.

Measure 12: Tooling for data collection of operando data

Based on the data standards (measure 5) the data collection will be furthered by pilot projects. Good examples are collections of data by operando IR, Raman, X-ray absorption, NMR or scattering data. X-ray and neutron based techniques furthermore allow imaging of the processes. Spatially resolved gas phase analysis can be conducted by SpaciPro-mass spectrometry or IR and in certain cases with laser light based techniques.

Development of local pilots

Specific local pilot repositories will be set up for different partners. (# 13) These pilots will serve the purpose of developing and testing respective tools, procedures and software, and to implement them for specific use cases for representative challenges in the different disciplines of catalysis. These pilots will be later on extended in order to bridge between different disciplines of catalysis, between catalysis and reactor and process engineering, and between catalysis and data science. (# 14)

In parallel to tool development, pilots will be developed in years two to four.

Measure 13: Develop basic local specific pilots

A good example for operando characterization are reactions within the SPP2080 on dynamics of catalysts and reactor, the simplest ones being CO₂ hydrogenation to methane and methanol where structural changes are expected to occur.

KIT will focus on a basic specific local pilot combining electrocatalysis and heterogeneous catalysis: High temperature (co-) electrolysis using solid-oxide cells will be used to produce hydrogen (and CO), which then is converted to methane, methanol, and DME. The standards and tools developed in the measures above will be used to implement all data of the individual physical and chemical processes into one data stream that automatized the workflow and integration. The software CaRMEN developed in Karlsruhe will form the basis for this integration.

One pilot for heterogeneous catalysis will be set up for BASCAT. The pilot will address the conversion of synthesis gas (CO + hydrogen) into larger hydro carbons and oxygenates. FOKUS along with BASCAT will develop methods and software tools that implement for heterogeneous catalysis that support the whole data work flow from defined experimental data, data import, data storage as well as further data processing in terms of curation and visualization (see Figure 3-2). Methods include guidelines for best-practice experiential procedures in heterogeneous catalysis that assure optimum data quality and appropriate quantity. The software will be a modular and extendable open source tool, into which other functions can be integrated by different work groups. (see section 4.4).

Measure 14: Develop basic local cross-cutting pilots

The cross-cutting pilot developed at KIT will combine data structures from molecular modeling, catalyst performance data and 3D-characterization catalyst characterization data for the first time. These data sets will then be the basis of reactor and process engineering and be applied to high temperature (co-) electrolysis to use renewable power for the production of useful chemicals and fuels such as methane, methanol, and DME.

LIKAT has planned a two-stage development that starts with homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis and extends to photo-catalysis and operando data in the 2nd stage.

Test functionality of basic pilots

The functionality of the developed basic local pilots as well as the basic cross-cutting pilots needs to be tested. (# 15 & # 16) Furthermore, user feedback needs to be collected to assess and improve user acceptance. (# 17) The tests will be run on different catalytic problems, with different users, and includes users that have not been part of the development process.

This action will be performed by the project partners from the catalysis field and the project participants. The personnel performing this activity are either project staff or end users in the laboratories who cannot be funded out of this project. Therefore, no additional funding is requested for this measure.

Tests will mainly be performed in year four.

Measure 15: Test functionality of basic local pilots (use cases)

At KIT the functionality of basic local pilot based on performance data for catalyst and electrolysis cell will be used to optimize the operating conditions for the coupling (thermal integration) of a high temperature (co-)electrolysis of steam (and CO₂) with a methanation reactor.

Measure 16: Test functionality of basic cross-cutting pilots (use cases)

The functionality of cross-cutting pilot developed at KIT will be tested by using molecular derived data to describe the reaction kinetics, feed that into reactor simulation, which then is used for system design concerning SOEC and methanation coupling, i.e., a workflow from the molecular models (DFT) to the process design and test will be established for this cross-cutting pilot.

Measure 17: User acceptance tests basic pilots

User acceptance test will carried out by involving user that are exposed to the pilot for the first time to test user-friendliness. The feedback will be used to improve the pilot in this regard.

Measure/Milestone M1: Consolidate experiences from basic pilot phase

The experiences gained in the basic pilot phase will be reflected and documented as basis for the next phase in the development.

Measure 18: Develop extended local specific pilots**Measure 19: Develop extended local cross-cutting pilots****Measure 20: Test functionality of extended local pilots (use cases)****Measure 21: Test functionality of extended cross-cutting pilots (use cases)****Measure 22: User acceptance tests extended pilots****Measure/Milestone M2: Consolidate experiences from extended pilot phase**

The development of the extended pilots follows the same principles as the basic pilots.

Measure 23: Develop guidelines for best practises

One important aim of NFDI4cat is to do better catalysis science. In order to do so, users need to be trained and educated. A prerequisite for this is the existence of best-practise procedures that include besides the data aspects also the catalysis science itself. Guidelines for best practise will therefore be developed along the whole project for performing catalyst synthesis, catalytic tests, material characterization as well as data processing and modelling. On all levels, these guidelines will include recommendations on how to document each step, and how to efficiently generate and process the respective data and metadata.

After finalising the pilot phase, guidelines will be developed in project year five.

BasCat, with some support from FOKUS will develop guidelines for the area of heterogeneous catalysis.

For Biocatalysis, terminologies and guidelines will be established for enzyme activity data and biocatalytic reaction performance data at the Universities of Greifswald and Rostock.

Sustainability of local tool box and compliance with FAIR principles

Along the project, different tools will be developed for local repositories. These tools need to be unified into a general data collection and processing toolbox for the local data processing. (# 24) The quality and usefulness will in large parts determine the aimed-for rapid community adoption and thus require excellent document and need to be easy to deploy and use. The toolbox needs to be maintained and further developed in a sustainable way. (# 25)

Along creating guidelines, toolboxes will be created in project year five.

FOKUS will integrate the tools and modules developed for heterogeneous catalysis into Piveau, an open source data management ecosystem developed by Fraunhofer FOKUS. Functionalities to import, process, and store (meta-)data will be re-used and tailored to the specific needs of catalysis research. In a similar fashion, existing functionalities to monitor the (meta-)data (e.g., to check (and potentially improve) the quality) and visualize will be extended both by some use case- and domain-specific characteristics. In a later stage, other parts of Piveau to e.g. process data before publishing will be implemented driven by the needs of catalysis research.

Measure 24: Assemble universal data collection toolbox for local repositories

Measure 25: Sustainability of the toolbox for local repositories

Metadata extraction is also part of the data acquisition. Herein, data is analysed for already existing metadata, may it be implicitly or explicitly. The metadata extractor *ExtractIng* has to be adapted to the use cases within this project. This means it first has to be analysed, which information are already present in the data files, the output and log files of the computational or experimental tools or different other files. Then, the extractor has to be adapted to these files. By design, *ExtractIng* works with a generic approach: For new cases, only configuration files have to be written and no changes in the code have to be performed. It has to be checked if *ExtractIng* works inside lab environments and specific computer platforms and eventually adapted. However, as it is written in Java, *ExtractIng* provides high compatibility with most computer platforms.

The work on *ExtractIng* will be performed by HLRS. In addition, HLRS will support the work on Interfaces as specified above. HLRS will require on full time position for this effort, starting in project year two. In the first project year 3 PM are foreseen to make *ExtractIng* work with the prototype repository.

4.4 Data Analysis, Quality Management and Re-Use (TA3)

Data acquired from experiments need to be further processed in order to provide a maximum of value for improved catalysis research. Important steps in the data analysis are visualization, modelling, predictions based on the models as well as a plan for better experiments (DOE) based on the models and data. In this context, recent innovations in the field of ML are of indispensable value. Moreover, monitoring and assessing data quality is equally important. Other desired capabilities are ways to perform kinetic modelling, easily explore the influence of mass- and heat transfer, and to connect to other data bases that e.g. provide molecular data based on DFT. Use cases in different areas of catalysis will serve as a basis to develop the required tools and to test also interoperability with other related consortia.

Aim of this task area is the development of novel algorithms and data analysis tools that facilitate the different steps of typical data processing in catalysis, ranging from design-of-experiments via visualization, modelling and predictions to different means of quality assurance. Major challenges faced in this area are (1) the management and integration of heterogeneous data sources, (2) data quality monitoring, and (3) novel robust machine learning algorithms and data analysis tools that are reproducible and interpretable.

Measure 1: Integrate existing tools into basic pilots (CaRMEN of KIT)

Data entering the RDM system needs to be monitored with respect to data quality and completeness. Moreover, the inherently incomplete nature and heterogeneity of typical research data in catalysis requires new approaches to data fusion. Measures #2 and #3 will therefore focus on the development of new algorithms for data quality monitoring, and for the fusion of heterogeneous data. Including existing domain knowledge in the field of catalysis will be vital to define relevant quality indicators. The newly developed algorithms will be implemented in tools, e.g. software, that provide a simple non-expert access to the algorithms (#6). The implementation is facilitated by the modular nature of the developed software framework.

The goal of measure #7 is to foster interdisciplinary entanglement between theory and application in catalytic research and ML. Algorithms and software will be developed to further process and evaluate locally the data which has been already imported into a local RDM repository (see 4.3). Particular focuses of the proposed work are modelling via new developed ML techniques, predictions derived from these models, and DOE to test predictions against real experiments (#8). One main focus of the modelling will be novel algorithms that are able to fuse heterogeneous datasets in a robust way. Data quality

monitoring will be approached by algorithms for e.g. statistical analysis, data quality rating and outlier detection (Fig. 3-6). This will be tackled by a tight integration between ML along the whole local data work flow, and will attempt to merge strong prior knowledge constraints with existing data-driven models. This way statistical inference can be focused on the challenging aspects of the problem, while a priori knowledge is represented exactly and artefact-free.

Measure 2: Novel algorithms to monitor and rate data quality

Measure 3: Novel algorithms to fuse heterogeneous data

Measure 4: Tools to monitor and validate metadata

Measure 5: Tools to enrich/generate metadata automatically

Measure 6: Tools to monitoring and access data quality

Measure 7: Tools to facilitate data re-use by data scientists

Measure 8: Tool for DoE based on models and data

Measure 9: Tools for data analysis (visualisation, modelling, prediction)

Measure 10: Tools to evaluate kinetic models

Measure 11: Tools to interface external repositories

Measure 12: Tools to quickly explore influence of heat and mass transfer

Measure 13: Assemble universal toolbox for (meta)data quality management and meta-data enrichment

Measure 14: Sustainability of universal toolbox (meta)data quality and meta-data enrichment

Measure 15: Use case machine learning application in heterogeneous catalysis

The rapidly progressing field of machine learn provides unique opportunities to model data, to identify correlations, and to reveal complex relations within the data. Based on the data pilots from the different catalysis disciplines use cases for machine learning will be developed that demonstrate and explore the potential of ML in catalysis research.

At the TU Berlin, BasCat will develop such use in collaboration with BBDC exemplarily for applications in heterogeneous catalysis.

Measure 16: Use case process simulation/design integration (data-to-value)

In cooperation with other partners and NFDI consortia, we will design metadata and ontology descriptions (TA1) for the resulting input-output data. The computational pipeline will be described in an electronic lab book using a workflow language like WDL, Nextflow, or CWL, following FAIR standards and setting up a best practice example for the confirmable workflow for this use case that could be followed in computational experiments in catalysis. As we will closely cooperate with other NFDI consortia on this, like MaRDI and FAIRmat,

through the involvement of the co-applicant in these consortia, the electronic lab books for computational pipelines will also be available across disciplines.

Measure 17: Use case cross-consortia data analysis (interoperability)

The standards that will be developed for describing the computational pipeline and data and exemplified with the use case for numerical simulation (#18) will then be tested and employed for more advanced computational experiments related to Power2Chemicals processes. As this is quite a dynamic field of research right now, we cannot describe the particular process(es) that will be involved then, but it is clear that advanced catalytic techniques will be involved and the Power2X technologies will remain an important part of the energy transition so that more and more advanced processes will need computational design and optimization strategies.

Measure 18: Use case numerical simulation

The use case for numerical simulation is based on the optimization and control of a methanation reactor. Here, we have a full workflow from modelling to simulation to optimization and control of the process. Therefore, we will use this to describe how a confirmable workflow in numerical experiments involving several software components and data sources can be implemented.

Measure/Milestone M1: Consolidate experiences from use cases

4.5 Linked Extensible Infrastructure and Access Management (TA4)

This task area is responsible for the design, deployment and operation of the distributed repository infrastructure for NFDI4Cat. In addition, it will plan, deploy and operate the required services in the distributed infrastructure.

The repository infrastructure for NFDI4Cat is envisioned as layered distributed approach: A distributed storage layer as the technological base for a middleware layer that is the core of the service. On top of this, a user layer with GUI and CLI handles the interaction with the users and integrates the provided distributed repositories.

The repository is the heart of the research data management efforts and has to handle the following tasks: First, it has to integrate existing repository systems. Second, it has to provide a solution for distributed data sources where data is bound to specific storage devices e.g. within an institution. And third, it has to provide a new repository (or several repositories) for all data which is planned to be newly ingested to the NFDI4Cat environment without using an existing system at a partner site. For this repository, a metadata-driven approach can be used, meaning the metadata has a severe impact on the design of the repository. The repository must also be able to handle heterogeneous storage backends. These backends have to be united in a common shared middleware. In the middleware, a central metadata store has to gather all metadata information of all data objects from all backends.

Of course, specific requirements have to be addressed. For example, data which is under intellectual property regulations must not be registered in the DOI service and must not get published. The repository has to incorporate measures to address these issues of confidentiality.

The first step of the effort is a detailed requirements analysis for the catalysis community. Discussions have already shown that quite some requirements have to be taken into account which are specific to the community. This has led to the proposed layered approach. Based on the requirements, a detailed plan for the infrastructure will be developed. A second outcome of the requirements analysis phase will be the specification of services. In parallel to the analysis and planning phase, a pilot repository will be setup for BASCAT. This pilot will help to develop the planned tools and show the acceptance of such a system in the laboratory. In addition, it will help to identify all issues that arise when integrating a repository in the daily workflow of a catalysis laboratory.

Figure 4-2: Gantt Chart showing the execution time of the measures in Task Area 4

Measure 1: Requirements Analysis

Within this measure the requirements of the catalysis community will be collected, discussed and analysed. The different laboratories where the data is generated have very different methods of data acquisition and data handling. They even have different status in the work methodology and the IT-support for this. Therefore, a detailed analysis of the state-of-the-art and the requirements are key. Especially as not only the current state of working, but also already planned future developments like the setup of a laboratory information and management system (LIMS) have to be taken into account. In addition, some institutions have already a structured method to store their data, some others are already using some kind of repository and some thirds are at the very beginning of data management.

The analysis phase will in addition collect the expectations of the future users from the catalysis laboratories on the environment. This is a second key factor as the system needs to be accepted by its users – for data retrieval but even more important for the data ingest. Only if the environment can show that it is helpful in the daily work of the scientists and technicians, it will be accepted and filled with the required data. Especially the hurdle of metadata acquisition needs to be low as this is felt as an additional unnecessary effort in the beginning. Here, we plan for tools and interfaces that make data acquisition and metadata acquisition as well as the data ingest as easy as possible.

As a third field, there are the requirements of the institutions where data is generated. There are legal and administrative constraints. One example is the question when data should become available for whom? Independent of the answer to this, the data should already be ingested to the repository environment when they are generated to make the data flow easy to handle and transparent. And it omits redundant copies, too.

In the catalysis field, industry has already experience with research data management for their own needs. Therefore, in a fourth part of this effort, the collected requirements will be

discussed and optimized together with connected industrial players. Those are mainly project participants and members of the Advisory Council.

To mention an example of an important requirement, the repository software must be able to export the metadata with the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Being able to expose metadata information with this protocol, the metadata can be harvested by other repositories or integrated in the presentation layer.

A second example is the interoperability with national and international services like ORCID or DataCite which are required to make data citable and to link the contributions to registered authors.

Result of this measure is a detailed specification of the required repository infrastructure and the intended services. This detailed specification will contain a requirements prioritization for risk management. It is clear that these documents will be developed iteratively between the stakeholders of the project.

The requirements analysis will mainly be performed by HLRS, with some support from FOKUS. The other project partners will provide insight into their working environments and will support the measure with their knowledge and expertise.

HLRS plans for 1.5 FTE for the first two years; FOKUS plans 0.5 FTE for the first two years. A substantial part of the effort will be two to three visits to each project partner from the catalysis field to learn and understand on the spot, how the scientists are working, how they are using their current environment and what they are planning for the future. In a second step, findings and opportunities will be discussed to further improve the analysis.

Measure 2: Software Evaluation

In parallel to the requirements analysis, a software evaluation will take place. The repository market is quite dynamic and repository software as well as supporting tools develop fast. The different software has different abilities and characteristics as well as different roadmaps which need to be fully understood and elaborated. A focus is on open source software as this limits the licensing costs and opens the opportunity for own developments and extensions.

The result of this measure is a software catalogue containing all the interesting meta-repository, repository and tools software with all features and development paths listed. This catalogue together with the specification documents will be the basis for the service and environment development.

The software evaluation will be mainly performed by HLRS, with some support from FOKUS.

HLRS plans for 0.5 FTE for two years and FOKUS 0.25 FTE for two years to perform this effort. Besides using description of the software for the evaluation, test installations of promising candidates will be performed.

Measure 3: Pilot System

In parallel to the software evaluation and the requirements analysis, a pilot system based on existing solutions that best fit the use case will be setup for BasCat. It is planned to use some modules of Piveau, a data management ecosystem developed by FOKUS. The purpose of this prototype deployment is manifold:

- The users get an impression on the technology and there is an early feedback which will help the requirements analysis.
- The users get a better feeling about existing services and the opportunities of the technology which will help to shape new services and which will potentially impose new requirements nobody had in mind beforehand.
- The prototype environment will act as a platform to test tools and act as a basis for further tool development for AP3.
- The prototype environment will help the system deployers and operators to better understand the technology. In addition, it will help to understand how users handle the system and it will give a feeling about required performance and response times. This will also add to the requirements document.
- On the hardware side, a setup is intended which will make use of disk and tape storage. This will help to understand the system performance with different storage technology as well as finding parameters for data migration between storage technologies depending on the characteristics of accesses.

To make full profit of the setup, regular feedback rounds will be organized to discuss the state of the system, the user experiences, the services and potential changes and improvements to the environment, the services and the tools.

The result of this measure is experience and this will influence the specification. In addition, this is additional input for the service and environment planning and design.

This measure will be performed by Fraunhofer FOKUS, HLRS and BasCat. HLRS will setup and operate the hardware and will work on the hardware-software interface. FOKUS will provide, setup and support the software. BasCat will use the system, integrate it into the daily work and provide feedback.

HLRS as well as FOKUS would like to use 0.5 FTE in the first three project years of this effort. This is required for hardware and software setup, operations, configuration changes and all kind of adaptations and adjustments on the pilot system.

Measure 4: Repository Layer

The purpose of this measure is the setup of the distributed repository environment which will be the core of the service. The systematic collection of research data has to be handled in this layer. Based on the specification, the environment it will be designed, planned and deployed. The software will be chosen based on the evaluation in measure two. Currently, we assume that a few repositories will have to be deployed. As the repository layer serves as an abstraction layer for all the different systems of storage which we will have to integrate with their data into the repository environment. Storage systems is meant here as superset for storage devices like hard disks or tapes with a kind of file system, data bases, etc. where data is located mainly without or with limited metadata. In this case, we will setup a repository, which will integrate all those data and provide the opportunity to enrich them with the required metadata.

In addition, we will have institutions included that do not want to store their data and the metadata at an external site, but nevertheless want to provide access to it. Those sites will have a local repository being setup. Furthermore, we need to have a repository to be setup where the community not having write access to another system can upload their data and metadata. This repository will be hosted at HLRS in Stuttgart.

This measure will mainly be performed by HLRS which plans one FTE in project year two, 2 FTE in project year three where the main part of the layer shall be setup. For project year 4 and five again one FTE is requested for adaptations and adjustments on the distributed infrastructure.

Measure 5: Presentation Layer: Metadata Portal and User Interface

The upper layer is the central component for querying and search and retrieval of data from the repository network. This layer is the integrating element and interfaces to the available repositories, searches and queries these and links the user to the specific repository for retrieval. This layer has to be accessible via a web service as well as a command line interface.

Here, NFDI4Cat will look for the best solution according to the specification document. There exist several software solutions for this layer, including Piveau or GeRDI. Both projects plan to work together in the context of the planned cross-cutting consortium Bridge4NFDI.⁴⁴

This measure will be driven by Fraunhofer FOKUS and HLRS.

FOKUS plans for 2 FTE for years three to five for this measure. HLRS for 0.5 FTE. We request this for the setup and required adaptation work.

Measure 6: Additional Services

This measure will take care of the availability of the requested services. Depending on the available tools and the outcome of the requirements analysis, existing tools will be deployed and new tools will be developed.

Hot candidates for additional services are tools to judge the data quality. For this community, some services of this kind can be fully automatic as there are some metrics for specific kinds of data sets. In addition, there are discussions ongoing to setup a data quality rating system where data (re-)users can judge the data quality according to their experience with the data.

The objective is to make all the services available within the distributed infrastructure. This measure will closely interact with TA3 on data analysis tools and it will be driven by HLRS.

HLRS is requesting 1 FTE for three years for the software installation and adjustments together with necessary software developments.

Measure 7: User Access & User Management

Discussions in the consortium have shown that Intellectual Property and Confidentiality play an important role. Nevertheless, the respective data shall be made available in the repository layer as access by a smaller or larger group is desirable. This group can even change through the life time of the data. In addition, the data can already be ingested into the repository environment when it is generated using the available tools to enrich them with the metadata at this step. Therefore, access control is a major requirement. For this, an authentication and role based authorization system needs to be designed and established for the distributed environment within this measure.

This action will be performed by HLRS requesting one FTE for three project years to perform the work.

⁴⁴ <https://www.bridge4nfdi.de>

Measure 8: Operations

The distributed infrastructure which is setup needs to be kept available and accessible. In this measure, the operation of the infrastructure will be handled. This includes trouble management, phone support and daily operational procedures.

This measure will be performed by HLRS. We request one FTE for project years three to five, when the repository is setup and becoming operational.

The primary operational costs for the equipment at HLRS side like power and cooling as well as infrastructure costs will be covered by HLRS. In addition, HLRS will provide two server systems in kind. Furthermore, HLRS will provide access to hard disk storage space of about 100 TB as well as up to 1 PB of background storage on tape.

Measure 9: Sustainability of the Infrastructure

The topic of this measure is the long term sustainability of the NFDI4Cat infrastructure with its services. It will elaborate opportunities for future financing and further extension of the infrastructure and the service portfolio.

Measure 10: Specification Document Review and User Acceptance Tests

This measure comprises all testing and review activities by the users. This includes the review of the specification document for the repository infrastructure and the additional services at the end of project year two and the test of the deployed infrastructure and services in project year four and five.

This action will be performed by the project partners from the catalysis field and the project participants. In addition, interested partners from the advisory council and other parties are welcome to test and provide feedback. Of course, this feedback is limited to the publicly available data sets and services.

The personnel performing this activity are either project staff working in other task areas or end users in the laboratories who cannot be funded out of this project. Therefore, no additional funding is requested for this measure.

Collaboration with other Task Areas

This task area will collaborate with several other task areas of this effort. The deployment of the metadata scheme will be done together with TA1. In addition, requirements from the

ontology development will be collected by the work of measure 1 within the requirements analysis.

A close collaboration with TA2 is required to setup and deploy the tools for data acquisition. For the development of interfaces the both TAs need to work together, too. Together with TA3 the interoperability of the analysis tools with the infrastructures is in focus. The outreach and training effort in TA5 will be supported with specific information about the infrastructure and its interplay. In addition, it will be supported with material about the services. TA 6 has a direct link to this task area as several developments in the infrastructure and concerning the services shall be harmonised and synchronized. The findings of TA 7 concerning confidentiality will have an influence on the access policy based authorization management for the infrastructure. For measure 7 in TA 8 (Management) staff of this task area will operate the tools for the collaboration within the project.

Risks of Implementation

There is a certain risk, that the available software for repositories and services together with developments possible by the developers in the frame of this project are not fully covering the requirements of the specification. A detailed planning at the end of project year two will show whether there are enough resources available to cover all requirements. If this is not the case, the implementation of requirements will be postponed according to the prioritization in the specification document.

4.6 Dissemination and Outreach/Training (TA5)

This task area aims at disseminating the results obtained in the previous work packages through various channels such as conferences, workshops and publications and at implementing knowledge and experience obtained within NFDI4Cat in a postgraduate Research Data Management School of Catalysis as well as in teaching modules of catalysis-related curricula at universities. It also includes public relations management and monitoring the overall acceptance of data infrastructures and their utilization into the academic and industrial community.

Measure 1: Research Data Management School of Catalysis

The Research Data Management School of Catalysis will be planned and contents will be elaborated during the first year. Several modules for the RDM School will be developed including data quality and formats, acquisition, storage, and publication. These modules will be developed with support of the Research Academy Leipzig. Course materials as well as flyers for announcements will be prepared and distributed. A first course will be offered in the second year within the German Catalysis Institutes (Katalyse-Lehrverbände).⁴⁵ Based on the experience and participants' feedback, training sessions at national conferences are planned. In the third and fourth year, the RDM School of Catalysis will offer two courses, one in Frankfurt with a European perspective and one in Leipzig with a national perspective. These courses will be open to the PhD candidates, postdocs and young researcher from industry.

Measure 2: Organise annual NFDI4Cat conferences (user-developer exchange)

A yearly NFDI4Cat conference will aim at connecting users of data from catalysis-related sciences and applications and developers of data infrastructures as well as tools for utilizing them. They will provide platforms for exchange and discussion, but also to discuss needs and potential approaches for research data management. The NFDI4Cat conferences are planned for two days and will be held at DECHEMA, and organized jointly with Leipzig University.

Measure 3: Public relations management

The outcomes of the NFDI4cat will be communicated to research and teaching institutions nationwide. A dedicated person will serve as a contact point for questions from users and developers for within NFDI4Cat as well as other NFDI initiatives, collaborative research consortia, national and international communities and universities.

Measure 4: Regular community surveys on knowledge about and adaptation of RDM

From the second year onwards, the adaptation of RDM will be monitored by surveys at the national GeCatS conference, at Europacat as well as via a web-based tool. These surveys

⁴⁵ <http://gecats.org/lehrverbuede>

will ensure that the research data infrastructure developed within NFDI4Cat is aligned in pace and scope with expectation and demands of the communities on the sides of both science and industry.

Measure 5: RDM sessions at international conferences

To foster discussion and spread results and approaches from NFDI4Cat, RDM session will be offered at international conferences such as the Europacat, International Catalysis Congress (ICC), and at conferences of the European Catalysis Societies. These will especially aim at dealing and utilizing with scientific data in all branches of catalysis science, and focus on scientific goals such as deepening understanding of catalysts and catalytic activity. International experts from both data science as well as experimental and computational catalysis will be invited to provide overviews and perspective presentations on catalysis-oriented RDM.

Measure 6: Integrating RDM in Laboratory Courses in Catalysis

RDM will be integrated in Laboratory Courses in Catalysis at several participating academic and non-university institutions. Web-based routines for data acquisition and evaluation will be applied. These courses will train and educate students at early stages of their studies and to prepare them to apply RDM in their future research activities.

Measure 7: Deliver data from use cases as data publications

The lessons learned and results obtained in the use cases for the different branches of catalysis (see TA2) will be summarized and made publicly available as data publications. These will be disseminated, e.g., via data repositories available at several Universities of the NFDI4Cat consortium members.

Measure 8: Deliver tools as resource publication

Tools (software) can be also published and enter the publication list of the researcher. This is hardly known and used in the Catalysis discipline. We want to publish tools from NFDI4Cat also as resource publications. Currently this could be done via Zenodo⁴⁶ but new services are expected to evolve.

Measure 9: Disseminate scientific results as publications & at conferences

Results for the test and use cases (TA2) and laboratory courses (Measure 6) will be published in at least two scientific publications and presented at national and international conferences.

Measure 10: Disseminate guidelines for best practises

A booklet (electronic and hard copy) with guidelines for work flows, data formats, acquisition and reporting will be made publicly available. These will highlight selected examples from the use cases and provide reliable and user-friendly concepts for RDM as well as demonstrate

⁴⁶ <http://zenodo.org>

4.7 Networking with NFDIs, SFBs und international (TA6)

Networking within the NFDIs is seen as vital for the success of NFDI as a whole and its purpose and NFDI4Cat as single consortium. NFDI4Cat has therefore been engaged in an intense dialogue and exchange with consortia that tackle neighbouring or common topics. with search consortia detailed discussions about topics and how to address them well already held. In the best case these discussions have already led to detailed agreements or inclusions in the detailed work plans. Wherever necessary facilitators were identified who work as bridging individuals on common topics for the consortia and will safeguard the common interests of the consortia in order to ensure success of each specific endeavour. The consortia with which NFDI4Cat has detailed agreements about collaborative interests and detailed steps in the respective collaborations are in particular NFDI4Chem, FAIRmat, DAPHNE and NFDI4Ing. Apart from the consortia mentioned here specifically NFDI4Cat will be open for collaboration with all other NFDI consortia with who common topics can be identified.

NFDI4Cat and NFDI4Chem share common interests in the following topics that will be addressed: in cooperation in the development of ontologies, meta-data formats and the cross-linking of data repositories. While NFDI4Chem focusses more on fundamental aspects in chemistry NFDI4Cat also covers the areas of technical chemistry and chemical engineering sciences.

NFDI4Cat addresses all fundamental and applied aspects of with its associated fields of technical chemistry and chemical engineering and enables and supports cross-disciplinary research to realise the vision from molecule to process. Special emphasis is placed on the cross-disciplinary nature of catalysis linking homogeneous, heterogeneous and bio-catalysis, building upon the chemical physics of surfaces of materials and chemical reactions at surfaces, a focus of FAIRmat. Multiscale modelling aspects of catalysis will be explored in collaboration with FAIRmat.

NFDI4Cat and DAPHNE share common interests in characterization data on catalysts and therefore will develop joined schemes for connecting them to the functionality of materials. DAPHNE focusses on data at large scale facilities which are of tremendous importance for operando and tomographic characterization of catalysts. IP-sensitive data are also relevant in DAPHNE and joint discussion will transfer experience from NFDI4Cat to DAPHNE. Joint workshops with the goal of establishing common examples, policies, best practice and guides for metadata catalogues, data repositories are planned.

NFDI4Cat and NFDI4Ing will cooperate in the field of ontology development and metadata formats in order to harmonize the efforts in neighbouring fields.

Apart from the efforts concerning interactions with other NFDI consortia, NFDI4Cat has identified a dedicated list of SFB's and SPP's that will be discussion and cooperation partners. From the point of view of the consortium these SFB's and SPP's play an important role in the interaction and in many development topics. The SFBs and the SPPs can be first users of the services rendered by the NFDI4Cat consortium and are therefore vital partners in beta-testing the pilots developed in their core functionalities. In the discussion we see SFBs and the SPPs it became clear that there is a natural interest in that role within the respective research endeavours. The breadth of topics covered by the SFBs and the SPPs will ensure that the functionality of the information architecture can also be tested in the full breadth by a user community covering the full range of aspects relevant to catalysis, technical chemistry and chemical engineering.

At University of Rostock the Collaborative Research Center 1270 Elaine is located. It aims at developing and understanding electrical active implants and is bridging electrical engineering and medicine. It already has a central project to establish a common research data infrastructure. As a first outcome an expert advice is available for the members of the CRC to set up a data management plan. This is supported by a web-based tool. Electronic lab journals have been introduced for the scientists working within the CRC. The Rectorate of University of Rostock is supporting this initiative by additional funding to make these tools available to all faculties and scientists and install this permanently. An expert group is currently setting up a strategy for handling research data. Besides scientists from the faculties also the experts from the library as well as from the IT and Media Centre are involved from the very beginning.

The following SPP's and SFB's could be identified as further partners interested in exchange and in developments and services brought forward by NFDI4Cat.

SFB/Transregio 63 "Integrierte chemische Prozesse in flüssigen Mehrphasensystemen" addresses aspects of technical chemistry, chemical engineering and catalysis.

SPP2080 „Katalysatoren und Reaktoren unter dynamischen Betriebsbedingungen für die Energiespeicherung und -wandlung“ (Speaker. J.-D. Grunwaldt) addresses aspects of catalysis and chemical engineering in the context of “Energiewende”.

SFB/TRR 150 „Turbulente, chemisch reagierende Mehrphasenströmungen in Wandnähe“ (Vice-speaker: O. Deutschmann) addresses aspects of catalysis, technical chemistry and chemical engineering.

Apart from the above-mentioned efforts NFDI4Cat will be in intense exchange and discussion with the Helmholtz-Kolleg Energy-Related Catalysis (Sprecher O. Deutschmann) due to common interests and mission targets on a broad basis. The Helmholtz-Kolleg addresses aspects of catalysis, technical chemistry and chemical engineering.

Any effort of NFDI4Cat will also be reflected by international collaborations through discussion and presentation of results achieved by the consortium. The purpose is to ensure that the work of NFDI4Cat is reflected critically also by international experts from the field and finds resonance on an international basis. The potential of rendering services by the consortium on an international basis should not be excluded at this point in time. It is to be seen whether the services that can be provided by the consortium are technically interesting to party from outside and can be offered on a legally sound basis.

NFDI4Cat has established exchange and cooperation with the European Federation of Catalysis Societies and the North American Catalysis Society. A contact has been established with the Boreskov Institute in Russia. The relationships established to the leading catalysis societies in the world are seen as important cornerstones for the success of the consortium through a critical reflection of the achievements made within the project. The international catalysis societies they will be invited who the consortium's conferences on a regular basis.

NFDI4Cat is in dialogue with the *Research Data Alliance* concerning ontologies and metadata formats. From the consortium's perspective the Research Data Alliance is currently a unique set-up allowing for an open dialogue around topics to be addressed by the consortium ensuring an international discussion forum. This is seen as a vital element for the sustainability of any of the consortium's efforts.

The following measures are proposed and will be addressed:

M4.7-1 Development of a line of dialogue with all partners with shared interest in the field of ontology development.

Ontology development is a vital piece important for the core functionality of the information infrastructure. Any development must find resonance in the respective national and international community as well as in neighbouring fields. Therefore establishment of a line of dialogue we see organizations and consortia describe to exist is seen as important.

M4.7-2 Development of a line of dialogue with all partners with shared interest in the field of standardized metadata formats.

Standardized metadata formats play also an important role for the core functionality of the information infrastructure. Meta-data have special relevance regarding several aspects concerning the quality and lifetime of data. As described in the previous measure also here Oh resonance with respective national entities and the community as well as the international community and neighbouring fields has to be sought.

M4.7-3 Integration of common developments in the specific work packages of NFDI4Cat.

Any agreement that is reached uncommon ontologies and me TA data formats has to find an entry into the respective work packages addressed in this proposal. As the developments will be open source by default, progress and status after discussions can clearly be tracked by the community neighbouring NFDIs the NFDI head office. Measure 4.73 therefore has to engineer net the status of the discussion is reflected by the respective work packages addressing the topics of common ontologies and metadata formats.

M4.7-5 Coordination of interaction and services provided to SFB's and SPP's.

As described above the interaction to the SFBs and SPPs is seen as an important line of dialogue, an opportunity for beta testing of the information infrastructure and an opportunity for obtaining relevant data sets that can be handled and used within the information infrastructure. The same is true for the interaction with the Helmholtz-Kolleg Energy-Related Catalysis. Also, here an opportunity for beta-testing off the information infrastructure and an opportunity for obtaining relevant data sets that can be handled and used within the information infrastructure are expected.

M4.7-6 Coordination of interaction entertained with international organizations.

As described above the interaction and the dialogue to international organizations is seen as important regarding two points: first as important source of input on an expert level regarding content and functionality of the solutions developed. Secondly, it is expected that services will be requested by members of the international organisations once the consortium develops functional and acceptable solutions.

4.8 Intellectual Property and Confidentiality, Licences and Reward models (TA7)

The sharing of data for the benefit of the community and science in general is one of the central cornerstones within the NFDI. The work package “Intellectual Property and Confidentiality” addresses sensitive points around data sharing procedures and resulting consequences. Within this work-package NFDI4Cat will try to define pathways and procedures for the treatment of these topics on a community consensus basis, even beyond the consortium itself. This work package “IP and Confidentiality” belongs to the two workstreams. Workstream (B) *Data Science and Information Infrastructure Design* and Workstream (C) *Community and User related Aspects*. A starting point for the work-package is the basic guidelines for the treatment of data in a consistent workflow are given in the Horizon 2020 guidelines for “Open access and Data management”⁴⁷

Although open access is the default setting for Horizon 2020 and therefore within the NFDI it has to be accepted that not all data can be open and an understanding and sensitivity within the community and respective effective mechanisms and measures have to be developed and institutionalized that insure confidentiality and intellectual property rights at all stages. The development of such mechanisms must be made in accord with the community of NFDI4Cat and to be aligned with other consortia within the NFDI and of course with the NFDI head office. Not only has a sensibility for the topic to be created and a consensus to be reached within the community on how a practical way of implementation can be reached, but also from a practical point of view measures must be taken resulting in effective mechanisms that have to be created. These mechanisms will have to be embedded in the information architecture and aid in safeguarding the general policy of Horizon 2020 and the NFDI.

Beyond confidentiality and IP, also the motivation and incentives of individual users to contribute and use the NFDI4cat infrastructure has to be considered. Typical rewards in academic research are the publication of experimental results, interpretations and explanations in peer reviewed journals. Uploading data to the NFDI can be seen as the publication of the experimental results alone, and therefore needs new types of rewards. It is therefore vital, that incentives for the individuals will be created. Discussing and defining such incentives will therefore be an important task within the community and among the applicants, but also in collaboration with other NFDIs.

Reward should be given according to e.g. data amount and quality. Moreover, in order to specify rewards specific licenses could be used. Such licenses can be easily attached to each data point. Licenses could include restriction for non-commercial use only or also obligations and fees resulting from the use of the data such as proper crediting. Thus, new

⁴⁷ [Horizon 2020 Guidelines for Open Access and Data management](#))

license models need to be developed and their implementation as meta-data needs to be tested. Also here, the contribution of the community and other NFDIs will be indispensable. Consultation with the industrial advisory board and legal consultants plays an important role in the whole process. Each basic principle that is reflected in community consensus and has found entry in the principle safeguarded by the FBI head office has also to be translated in viable mechanisms that can be addressed by proper implementation on a software basis. Any implementation on a software basis into the information infrastructure must be backed up by appropriate training of users being part of the catalysis and engineering community utilizing the information infrastructure developed by the consortium. In order to ensure such appropriate training measures and implementation into the Graduate School of the consortium will be pursued.

The following measures are proposed and will be addressed:

M4.1: Development of a model that addresses the sensitive points of data treatment in the light of “Intellectual Property and Confidentiality” on the basis of community consensus.

Within measure 4.1 an invitation to the community of NFDI4Cat to a discussion about the topics of intellectual property and confidentiality will go out. The goal of this discussion is to create sensitivity for the two above mentioned topics and to arrive at a community accepted model on how to deal with the two topics, that has also the potential for technical implementation. The discussion will take place on 3 levels: a) via interviews with members of NFDI4Cat; b) via surveys of members of NFDI4Cat and members of the catalysis and engineering community and c) on a discussion forum level in the annual NFDI4Cat conferences. Consultation with the industrial advisory panel is an important element of the process. Fulfillment and conclusion of the measure is the arrival of a model that on a consensus basis can reflect the needs of the community and is sound on a legal basis.

M4.2 Outreach to other NFDI consortia for model discussion and validation

Measure 4.1 will deliver a model which will be the basis of an intensive discussion with other NFDI consortia. The goal of this discussion with the other consortia is to arrive at a potentially modified and validated model that is ready for dissemination and technical implementation. Consensus with other consortia and the NFDI head office is the goal of this measure. It is not intended to arrive at a singular solution for the NFDI4Cat consortium. Which is potentially in conflict with solutions developed in other consortia or principles developed by the NFDI head office?

M4.3 Pilot for implementation of the developed model for the treatment of data concerning “Intellectual Property and Confidentiality” into the software framework and hosting structure for data.

The goal addressed by the development of this pilot is to deal with the sensitive points of data treatment raised by the community of NFDI4Cat and other in NFDI consortia and must reflect the discussion addressed in measure 4.2. Not only must this pilot be based on the results of the discussion, but it must also deliver a technical footprint that can handle the issues to be addressed on a day-to-day basis. User acceptance is one of the most important issues that must be addressed in this measure as well. Therefore, early testing of the pilot is vital by responsible user groups so that their feedback can be integrated into an improved solution.

M4.4 Implementation of the final model and training (programming and implementation in information infrastructure, implementation in “graduate school”)

Based on the experience with the previous pilot developed in measure 4.3 the final model has to be implemented into the information infrastructure. It is important that at this point adequate user training takes place which enables users to work with the implemented features. Furthermore, it is intended to implement a module in the “NFDI4Cat Graduate School” addressing the basic principles of confidentiality and intellectual property. Also teaching users the respective software features so that the user community can use the system in a safe and proper way. System maintenance and further development of the information infrastructure will have to keep an eye on the implemented features safeguarding aspects of intellectual property and confidentiality. Any future development will have to take care that the principles in the measures 4.1 and 4.2 are respected and find appropriate entry into any of later developed software versions. It is assumed that such features or respectively the implementation of such features into other systems can be rendered as a service.

4.9 Management (TA8)

DECHEMA is a non-profit, interdisciplinary scientific society with more than 5,500 personal and institutional members. DECHEMA is dedicated to the support of R&D progress and implementation in various fields of chemical engineering, including catalysis and nanotechnology. DECHEMA is the coordinator of various national and EU projects, organizes around 50 conferences with over 10000 participants per year, and offers more than 20 training courses on different topics. Co-ordination and support of DECHEMA's activities is carried out by about 120 employees. DECHEMA will ensure through its own status the non-profit character of NFDI4Cat and will guarantee for a reliable and high-quality management of the consortium.

In NFDI4Cat DECHEMA will therefore be in charge of the management and distribution of the funds to the co-applicant institutions. Related to that are measures for the dissemination of results, developed tools and infrastructures which will be made available to the project partners (co-applicants and participants) as well as the whole catalytic community, other NFDIs and the general public.

Measure 1: Project management

This measure includes several aspects of scientific and administrative project management aspects.

i. Monitoring of the overall project progress and quality management

Together with LIKAT as the leading scientific partner, DECHEMA will monitor the progress towards the objectives of the project. Regular phone and/or video conferences with the TA leaders and the coordination team will ensure tight monitoring and fast corrective actions if necessary.

ii. Press/social media activities:

As NFDI4Cat aims to raise the awareness for their objectives as much as possible, it will be important to make use of social media, in particular, LinkedIn. Users from the consortium will be identified who have substantial numbers of followers and will be used as multipliers. Furthermore, the NFDI4Cat website will contain a Blog sharing the latest news on NFDI. Additional podcasts with statements of key players will complement these activities, if possible in connection to known dissemination events. Regular press releases, including interviews for local, national and international newspapers, and a dedicated newsletter will tackle the attention via traditional channels.

iii. Organisation of project meetings and status conferences

DECHEMA will organise and post-process all necessary consortium meetings as well as meetings of the General Assembly, Steering Group (TA leaders) and the Advisory Board, both face to face and telephone-conferences/web-based. Status conferences will be

organized on a yearly basis. The activities will be strongly linked to TA5 on “Dissemination and Outreach”.

iv. Communication with the DFG

DECHEMA will be responsible for all necessary communication issues with the DFG on behalf of the consortium, incl. possible amendments. All partners will contribute by providing input corresponding to their TA on demand.

Measure 2: Research administration of financial, legal and administrative requirements

DECHEMA as the applicant institution will manage and coordinate all financial and administrative activities in the project, including monitoring and maintaining the overall adherence to the financial budgets. DECHEMA will prepare and negotiate a Consortium Agreement in accordance with the requirements and needs of the DFG with regard to the envisaged structure of the NFDI as a whole. Moreover, DECHEMA will distribute the DFG contribution according to the work plan, the Consortium Agreement and the decisions made by the consortium. The administrative and financial monitoring of the project will also be done by the applicant institution.

Measure 3: Website

Within the first six months, DECHEMA will develop a project website as central information and communication tool for all project partners and interested stakeholders. This website will have a separate space with secured access for the NFDI4Cat partners in order to guarantee flexible and fast communication and data transfer amongst the partners. The public part of the website will contain all relevant information on NFDI4Cat including dissemination material. The maintenance and continuous updating of the website will be an essential part of this task. Due to the long funding period of NFDI, a larger update of the website is foreseen in year 5, taking technological developments into account.

Measure 4: Conferences, meetings and workshops

During the 5 years of the funding period a series of public events will be organized. As DECHEMA offers its facilities with conference rooms up to 250 people as an in-kind contribution to NFDI4Cat, the budget refers mainly to catering costs:

- i) Kick-off event: at Month 2 a kick-off event will take place
- ii) Joint events with other NFDIs: NFDI4Cat will evaluate possible co-operation with other consortia and jointly organise dissemination events addressing all possible stakeholders to present the main objectives and findings of the NFDI4Cat consortium.
- iii) Status conferences: Status conferences will be organized on a yearly basis.

Workshops with stakeholders and other preparatory actions might be organised jointly as part of a large event aggregating the community.

Measure 5: Dissemination material and travel

DECHEMA will prepare a project leaflet containing all relevant information on NFDI4Cat topics and procedures as well as roll-ups, posters and related materials during the whole funding period. This requires also regular updates during the lifetime of NFDI4Cat.

Communication with the scientific community and relevant stakeholders is a key-element of NFDI4Cat to ensure acceptance and adoption of the tools and infrastructure which will be developed within the consortium. In addition to digital communication tools, the NFDI4Cat team will establish a dialogue with the already existing networks of the project partners. By active participation (i.e. poster presentations, lectures, roll-ups) at conferences and project events, the consortium will inform the individual stakeholder groups.

Measure 6: Organisation of reviews by external experts

Ongoing monitoring of the compliance with FAIR principles and all other user and community requirements will be performed and evaluated by external experts. Furthermore, NFDI4Cat will be consulted by the industrial advisory panel as mentioned in TA 7

Measure 7: Provide community collaboration tooling

HLRS will provide access to its FusionForge service for the project. With this tool, a git repository, mailing lists, a wiki environment and more is provided. In addition a regression testing tool will be made available.

This service will be operated by project staff of HLRS who is mainly working in TA 4.

4.10 Overview of activities by co-applicant

Sections 4.1 to 4.9 present a view on NFDI4Cat based on the overall work plan. However, most task areas involve several partners the view on the activities and tasks of each partner is blurred. Therefore we provide here a short summary of the activities of each co-applicant and participant.

FAU: The HyMat (Hybrid Materials) group of Dr. Haumann will contribute to the development of ontologies (TA1) for hybrid materials such as immobilized homogeneous catalysts, e.g. supported ionic liquid phase (SILP) catalysts. In addition, FAU will contribute to the use cases (TA2). Literature data for use cases will be reviewed, extracted and incorporated into the repositories. New data will be generated in the laboratories using both, classical heterogeneous catalysts and our novel hybrid materials in dedicated reactors for batch and continuous mode.

Greifswald University aims to develop data analysis tools, standards and interfaces to facilitate this for biocatalytic reactions. This builds up from recently published principles where experimental results for specific enzymatic reactions (e.g., for Baeyer-Villiger-monoxygenase-catalyzed reactions [1], transaminase-catalyzed reactions [2] and the BioCatNet concept [3]), where harmonized in a digitalized manner. As a showcase reaction to be studied within the NFDI4Cat initiative we will use the transaminase-catalyzed reactions, where many examples using various enzymes, substrates and at different scales (lab to industrial scale) are accessible.

HLRS: The contributions of HLRS are data science and IT related. The main focus is on TA4 where they have the task area responsibility and where HLRS will part of the design, the setup, the deployment and the operation of the whole infrastructure. This includes the requirements analysis, a software evaluation as well as a pilot system. Furthermore, they will care for additional services and an authentication and authorization service. Towards the project end, they will also work on the sustainability of the services and the infrastructure.

In addition, HLRS will contribute to the development of the metadata ontologies in TA1 with its experience from the DIPL-ING project. In TA2, they will work on the adoption of the metadata harvester “Extracting” to the specific machinery in the catalysis laboratories as well as on the development of required interfaces to the environment. In TA7 HLRS will be involved using its contacts to track the efforts in RDM for catalysis especially in Russia. The coordination of the developments with neighbouring NFDIs is on its agenda as well. In TA8 HLRS will care for providing the collaboration IT-infrastructure for the project.

KIT: The work will focus on development of data standards, data acquisition tools, and interfaces on the digitalization process chain from heterogeneous (electro-) catalysis towards reactor and process engineering applying those catalysts. This process chain includes molecular data based on DFT and QM on the microscopic end of the chain, characterization data on catalyst and catalytic reactors in situ and operando (spectroscopy, microscopy), kinetic models on the mesoscopic scale as well as macro kinetics, modelling of mass and heat transport in catalytic reactors and eventually process simulation. The challenge here is not only the definition of data standards, the big data to handle, the establishments of links and interfaces between to-be-developed repositories along this line but also feedback and (mathematical) optimization loops. Therefore, the potential of novel strategies of artificial intelligence such as state-space control strategies and physics-based neuronal networks will be examined to support this development. The tool CaRMEN will serve as starting tool for the software to be developed.

LIKAT will contribute to NFDI4Cat in the development of ontologies and data standards in homogeneous, heterogeneous catalysis as well as in chemical engineering. These standards will be developed and coordinated with the participants from the same catalysis disciplines. In heterogeneous catalysis data are stored already since more than 15 years in a "LIKAT-standard". We want to build upon this work and make the tools more flexible (include homogeneous and phot catalysis). Moreover, describing catalyst synthesis in a structured form is a great challenge that we will address (together MPI CEC, TUB, FAU).

MPI CEC will contribute with experimental and computational work on homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis for small molecule activation (e.g. H₂, CO, CO₂, N₂). This includes data on preparation and characterization of catalysts as well as performance data. In homogeneous catalysis, a special emphasis will be laid on novel ways to explore ligand effects in organometallic catalysis by data mining analysis.

MPI DCTS will contribute use cases for numerical experiments in the context of catalytic processes necessary for supporting the energy transition in Germany. In particular, we will follow-up on research projects on Power2Gas and Power2X pursued at MPI DCTS together with the department "Process Systems Engineering", led by Prof. Dr.-Ing. Kai Sundmacher, and several partners at German universities. In these processes, CO₂ is employed for methanation and other processes to produce basic chemicals.

The first use case is based on the optimization and control of a methanation reactor. Here, we have a full workflow from modeling to simulation to optimization and control of the process. Therefore, we will use this to describe how a confirmable workflow in numerical

experiments involving several software components and data sources can be implemented. In cooperation with other partners and NFDI consortia, we will develop metadata and ontology descriptions (TA1) for the resulting input-output data. The computational pipeline will be described in an electronic lab book using a workflow language like WDL, Nextflow, or CWL, following FAIR standards and setting up a best practice example for the confirmable workflow for this use case that could be followed in computational experiments in catalysis. As we will closely cooperate with other NFDI consortia on this, like MaRDI and FAIRmat, through the involvement of the co-applicant in these consortia, the electronic lab books for computational pipelines will also be available across disciplines.

The standards that will be developed for describing the computational pipeline and data and exemplified with the first use case will then be tested and employed for more advanced computational experiments related to Power2Chemicals processes. As this is quite a dynamic field of research right now, we cannot describe the particular process(es) that will be involved then, but it is clear that advanced catalytic techniques will be involved and the Power2X technologies will remain an important part of the energy transition so that more and more advanced processes will need computational design and optimization strategies.

TU Berlin: Catalysis research with tightly integrated data science and RDM can foster great advances for the involved fields. Research groups at TU Berlin provide required expertise in the field of heterogeneous catalysis, the development of data infra structures and portals as well as method development on the field of machine learning. Focused on application in heterogeneous catalysis the BBDC (Berlin Big Data Center) und BZML (Berlin Zentrum für Maschinelles Lernen), represented by Prof. Dr. Klaus-Robert Müller, will develop methods for the integration of heterogeneous data sources, a monitoring of data quality as well as new robust ML methods and data analysis tools. Dr. Sonja Schimmler (Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems FOKUS, Open Distributed Systems / TU Berlin) will develop methods and software tools that integrate and model the whole data flow in heterogeneous catalysis. BasCat at TU Berlin (Dr.-Ing. habil. Ralph Krähnert) will co-develop and implement these methods exemplarily in specific examples of heterogeneous catalysis with focus on the hydrogenation of CO (syngas chemistry). The derived tools will be tested and further developed with other het cat labs within NFDI4Cat and other applications. The resulting open source software will be stepwise scaled and rolled out in iterative cycles to the whole NFDI4Cat.

TU Braunschweig aims to develop data standards and data acquisition tools for benchmarking electrochemical catalytic reactions. As possible showcase reactions within the NFDI4Cat initiative we will contribute data for CO₂ reduction to syngas or formate and for

oxygen reduction reaction which is occurred at the fuel cell cathode. Material properties (structure, chemical distribution), electrode preparation (very thin films versus several μm -thick catalyst-coated layers) will be correlated with the different electrochemical set-ups (electrochemical half-cell cells and single hardware cells) and electrochemical parameters (current density, overpotential) to provide information about the kinetics and mass transport properties for electrochemical reactions. Operando/ in-situ and ex-situ microscopic and spectroscopic characterization techniques will help to understand the elementary processes, which are required for further modelling and simulations.

The research program of **TUDO-AD**, Prof. Dr.-Ing. N. Kockmann: Starting from an elaborated chemical and process engineering ontology interlinked with existing bibliographic information models, the research data handling process is elaborated with a set of metadata. Existing metadata structures are used such as datacite.org.

TUDO-TC, Prof. Dr. D. Vogt: The group is one of TUDO's members of SFB/TR 63. The research program deals with homogeneously catalyzed reactions; from the molecular basis of reaction mechanisms, ligand design, kinetics and catalyst testing on lab scale to process development on miniplant scale. Among others, reactions investigated are carbonylations, hydroformylation and amination reactions. Reference data from these processes can be taken for research data management and infrastructure, particularly to present scale-up issues. The group has implemented an electronic lab-journal (sciformation) that significantly contributes to data handling and data management.

TUDO-Bioprosesstechnik, Dr.-Ing. Katrin Rosenthal: The research group together with Prof. Stephan Lütz is focusing on biocatalysis from the development of new enzymes over enzyme cascades to bioprocess development. The research program deals with various kinds of biocatalytic reactions; from cell-free protein synthesis; biotransformations and biocatalyst testing and screening on lab scale to process development on pilot scale. Among others, reactions investigated are oxidases, laccases, and electro-biotechnological reactions. Reference data from these processes can be taken for research data management and infrastructure, particularly to present scale-up issues. The group will implement an electronic lab-journal (sciformation) in near future that significantly contributes to data handling and data management.

RWTH: The group of Prof. Wessling (RWTH) and Prof. Palkowitz aims to develop a joint infrastructure comprising experimental data acquisition for catalyst screening combined with a subsequent fast evaluation of obtained data towards process design. The workgroup operates the ELECTRA competence centre for electrochemical process development. This

infrastructure project comprises multiple experimental facilities for fast and reliable experimental analysis of electrochemical processes. These facilities allow defined measurement conditions and high-throughput experiments at the pilot scale. Among the investigated processes, there are several approaches for electrochemical reduction and conversion of CO₂. Significant amounts of data are generated by measuring these catalytic systems. However, raw data can often not directly be used for the identification of catalysts well suited for process design. Obtainable yield, energy consumption, and downstream processing have a significant impact on whole process efficiency. Based on our expertise in the field of research data management, we identified the tremendous potential for integrated evaluation of measurement data in process simulation and design ([10.1016/j.memsci.2018.10.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2018.10.013)).

RWTH-CVT will contribute to the ontology development (TA1) for electrochemical catalysis and electrochemical process design. To achieve this goal, they will use the vast amount of data generated by our electrochemical competence centre to develop data standards exemplarily for our processes. These standards will be generalised in cooperation within the consortium i.e., with partners focusing on smaller-scale process development or simulation thereof. Research Data Management (RDM) has been a focus in their group for several years now. The efforts have yielded not only publications but also the research data management spin-off FURTHRresearch. The resulting software package FURTHRmind is currently applied for data acquisition and evaluation on various research areas in their group, including the electrochemical competence centre. With the bouquet of tools for local data management (ELN, RDM, etc.), they will work on the definition and development of a general interface standard of RDM software towards a distributed hierarchical data repository.

Rostock University aims to develop data analysis tools, standards and interfaces for enzymatic- as well as chemocatalytic reactions. Aspects of downstream processing as well as data for eco-efficiency analysis will be included. Special emphasis will be put on non-conventional reaction media such as ionic liquids as well as mass transport for multi-phase systems such as solid-liquid (immobilised catalysts, whole cells) or liquid-gas (oxidation, reduction, and syngas-reaction). Another important aspect is the role of traces of water which is at least in organometallic catalysis often overlooked. As a showcase reaction alcohol-dehydrogenase reduction as well as Laccase oxidised oxidation reaction will be investigated where similar reactions with organocatalysts or copper-complexes exist. Together with the Faculty of Computer Science and Electrical Engineering teaching modules for students will be developed.

The **Chair of Technical Chemistry II at TU München** addresses fundamental aspects of catalysts and catalyzed reactions that enable catalysis to lower the carbon footprint via radically new approaches to synthesize energy carriers and chemical intermediates. The research is focused to enable catalyzed conversions at significantly lower reaction temperatures and with higher selectivity than possible today. Two aspects of enzyme sites, i.e., the tight fit of the space around the active site and the chemical functionality of this space, are used as guideline to synthesize novel catalysts. The in-depth characterization of the nature and structure of such catalytically active sites, of their chemical functionality and of the space around it, as well as of the molecules populating this space is the key to the successful realization of this strategy. The dynamic evolution of these catalysts is studied throughout their lifespan and spectroscopically monitored during catalyst synthesis, sorption and reactions, exploring possible operation conditions and their limitations. This work combines advanced physicochemical methods to characterize reactions on surfaces including IR, Raman, and solid state NMR spectroscopy with X-ray absorption spectroscopy to characterize the structure and electronic state of these materials during sorption and catalysis

Advisory Council: The experiences of the chemical industry in data management (in laboratories as well as in process control) will be made available to NFDI4Cat through an Advisory Council which not only provides information on pros and cons of specific data base structures and tools but also provides the view of external potential users. The following companies have expressed their willingness of becoming member of the Advisory Council: BASF, hte GmbH, Linde AG, Evonik Industries AG, Covestro AG and Clariant AG and ThyssenKrupp AG. The letters of support can be found in Annex 4. As head of the council Dr. Andreas Schunk, Vice President at hte GmbH & BASF SE, has been agreed on.

7 Appendix

7.1 Bibliography and list of references

[DarkData] Schembera, Björn, and Juan M. Durán. "Dark Data as the New Challenge for Big Data Science and the Introduction of the Scientific Data Officer." *Philosophy & Technology* (2019): 1-23.

[HPCRDM] Schembera, Björn, and Thomas Bönisch. "Challenges of research data management for high performance computing." *International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries*. Springer, Cham, 2017.

[AnfRDM] Iglezakis, D., und B. Schembera. „Anforderungen der Ingenieurwissenschaften an das Forschungsdatenmanagement Der Universität Stuttgart - Ergebnisse der Bedarfsanalyse des Projektes DIPL-ING“. *O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal / Herausgeber VDB*, Bd. 5, Nr. 3, September 2018, S. 46-60, doi:10.5282/o-bib/2018H3S46-60.

[EngMeta] Schembera, Björn, and Dorothea Iglezakis. "The Genesis of EngMeta-A Metadata Model for Research Data in Computational Engineering." *Research Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research*. Springer, Cham, 2018.

[EngMeta_IJMSO] (in revision) Schembera, Björn, and Dorothea Iglezakis. "EngMeta - A Metadata Model for Computational Engineering." *International Journal for Metadata, Semantics and Ontologies*.

[DataCite] J. Brase, "DataCite - A Global Registration Agency for Research Data," *2009 Fourth International Conference on Cooperation and Promotion of Information Resources in Science and Technology*, Beijing, 2009, pp. 257-261. doi: 10.1109/COINFO.2009.66

[BWDA] (in revision) Bach, F., Schembera, B., van Wezel, J.: Design and Implementation of the first Generic Archive Storage Service for Research Data in Germany. *International Journal of Digital Curation*. (2019).

[Cha18] Chang, E.J., Ashraf, J., Hussain, F.K., Hussain, O.K., *Measuring and Analysing the Use of Ontologies: A Semantic Framework for Measuring Ontology Usage*, Springer, Cham, 2018

[Eib19] Eibeck, A., Lim, M. Q., & Kraft, M. (2019). J-Park Simulator: An ontology-based platform for cross-domain scenarios in process industry. Preprint Cambridge Centre for Computational Chemical Engineering.

- [Eng18] G. Engel, T. Greiner, S. Seifert, Ontology-Assisted Engineering of Cyber–Physical Production Systems in the Field of Process Technology, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informatics*, 14(6) 2792-2802, 2018
- [Koc19] N. Kockmann, Digital methods and tools for chemical equipment and plants, *Reac. Chem. & Eng.*, 4, 1522-1529, 2019
- [Mar10] Marquardt, W., Morbach, J., Wiesner, A., Yang, A., *OntoCAPE: A Re-Usable Ontology for Chemical Process Engineering*, Springer, Berlin, 2010
- [Mor07] Morbach, J., Wiesner, A., Marquardt, W., *A Meta Model for the Design of Domain Ontologies*, Technical Report LPT-2008-24, 2007
- [Mor08a] Morbach, J., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., *Mathematical Models*, Technical Report LPT-2008-28, 2008
- [Mor08b] Morbach, J., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., *Material*, Technical Report LPT-2008-27, 2008
- [Mor08c] Morbach, J., Yang, A., Wiesner, A., Marquardt, W., *Supporting Concepts*, Technical Report LPT-2008-26, 2008
- [Mor08d] Morbach, J., Bayer, B., Wiesner, A., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., *OntoCAPE 2.0 - The Upper Level*, Technical Report LPT-2008-25, 2008
- [Mor09] Morbach, J., *A Reusable Ontology for Computer-Aided Process Engineering*, Dissertation RWTH Aachen, 2009
- [Ont19] [OntoCAPE homepage: www.avt.rwth-aachen.de/cms/AVT/Forschung/Software/~ipts/OntoCape](http://www.avt.rwth-aachen.de/cms/AVT/Forschung/Software/~ipts/OntoCape)
- [Sic14] Sicilia, M.-A., *Handbook of metadata, semantics and ontologies*, World Scientific, 2014
- [War92] W.A. Warr, C. Suhr, *Chemical informationmanagement*. VCH, Weinheim, 1992
- [Wie08] Wiesner, A., Morbach, J., Yang, A., Bayer, B., Marquardt, W., *Chemical Process Systems*, Technical Report LPT-2008-29, 2008
- [Win19] Winther KT, Hoffmann MJ, Boes JR, Mamun O, Bajdich M, Bligaard T. Catalysis-Hub. org, an open electronic structure database for surface reactions. *Scientific data*. 2019 May 28;6(1):75.
- .
- [DarkData]** Schembera, Björn, and Juan M. Durán."Dark Data as the New Challenge for Big Data Science and the Introduction of the Scientific Data Officer."*Philosophy & Technology* (2019): 1-23.
- [HPCRDM]** Schembera, Björn, and Thomas Bönisch."Challenges of research data management for high performance computing."*International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries*.Springer, Cham, 2017.

[AnfRDM] Iglezakis, D., und B. Schembera. „Anforderungen der Ingenieurwissenschaften an das Forschungsdatenmanagement Der Universität Stuttgart - Ergebnisse der Bedarfsanalyse des Projektes DIPL-ING“. *O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal / Herausgeber VDB*, Bd. 5, Nr. 3, September 2018, S. 46-60, doi:10.5282/o-bib/2018H3S46-60.

[EngMeta] Schembera, Björn, and Dorothea Iglezakis. "The Genesis of EngMeta-A Metadata Model for Research Data in Computational Engineering." *Research Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research*. Springer, Cham, 2018.

[EngMeta_IJMSO] (in revision) Schembera, Björn, and Dorothea Iglezakis. "EngMeta - A Metadata Model for Computational Engineering." *International Journal for Metadata, Semantics and Ontologies*.

[DataCite] J. Brase, "DataCite - A Global Registration Agency for Research Data," *2009 Fourth International Conference on Cooperation and Promotion of Information Resources in Science and Technology*, Beijing, 2009, pp. 257-261. doi: 10.1109/COINFO.2009.66

[BWDA] (in revision) Bach, F., Schembera, B., van Wezel, J.: Design and Implementation of the first Generic Archive Storage Service for Research Data in Germany. *International Journal of Digital Curation*. (2019).

[Cha18] Chang, E.J., Ashraf, J., Hussain, F.K., Hussain, O.K., *Measuring and Analysing the Use of Ontologies: A Semantic Framework for Measuring Ontology Usage*, Springer, Cham, 2018

[Eib19] Eibeck, A., Lim, M. Q., & Kraft, M. (2019). J-Park Simulator: An ontology-based platform for cross-domain scenarios in process industry. Preprint Cambridge Centre for Computational Chemical Engineering.

[Eng18] G. Engel, T. Greiner, S. Seifert, *Ontology-Assisted Engineering of Cyber-Physical Production Systems in the Field of Process Technology*, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informatics*, 14(6) 2792-2802, 2018

[Koc19] N. Kockmann, *Digital methods and tools for chemical equipment and plants*, *Reac. Chem. & Eng.*, 4, 1522-1529, 2019

[Mar10] Marquardt, W., Morbach, J., Wiesner, A., Yang, A., *OntoCAPE: A Re-Usable Ontology for Chemical Process Engineering*, Springer, Berlin, 2010

[Mor07] Morbach, J., Wiesener, A., Marquardt, W., *A Meta Model for the Design of Domain Ontologies*, Technical Report LPT-2008-24, 2007

[Mor08a] Morbach, J., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., *Mathematical Models*, Technical Report LPT-2008-28, 2008

- [Mor08b] Morbach, J., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., Material, Technical Report LPT-2008-27, 2008
- [Mor08c] Morbach, J., Yang, A., Wiesner, A., Marquardt, W., Supporting Concepts, Technical Report LPT-2008-26, 2008
- [Mor08d] Morbach, J., Bayer, B., Wiesner, A., Yang, A., Marquardt, W., OntoCAPE 2.0 - The Upper Level, Technical Report LPT-2008-25, 2008
- [Mor09] Morbach, J., A Reusable Ontology for Computer-Aided Process Engineering, Dissertation RWTH Aachen, 2009
- [Ont19] OntoCAPE homepage: www.avt.rwth-aachen.de/cms/AVT/Forschung/Software/~ipts/OntoCape
- [Sic14] Sicilia, M.-A., Handbook of metadata, semantics and ontologies, World Scientific, 2014
- [War92] W.A. Warr, C. Suhr, Chemical information management. VCH, Weinheim, 1992
- [Wie08] Wiesner, A., Morbach, J., Yang, A., Bayer, B., Marquardt, W., Chemical Process Systems, Technical Report LPT-2008-29, 2008
- [Win19] Winther KT, Hoffmann MJ, Boes JR, Mamun O, Bajdich M, Bligaard T. Catalysis-Hub. org, an open electronic structure database for surface reactions. Scientific data. 2019 May 28;6(1):75.

HLRS

- (in revision) Bach, F., Schembera, B., van Wezel, J.: Design and Implementation of the first Generic Archive Storage Service for Research Data in Germany. International Journal of Digital Curation. (2019).
- (to appear (accepted)) Selent, B., Kraus, H., Hansen, N., Schembera, B., Seeland, A., Iglezakis, D.: Management of Research Data in Computational Fluid Dynamics and Thermodynamics. Proceedings of eScience Tage Heidelberg (2019)
- Schembera, B., Durán, J.M.: Dark Data as the New Challenge for Big Data Science and the Introduction of the Scientific Data Officer. Philosophy & Technology. (2019).
- Schembera, B., Iglezakis, D.: The Genesis of EngMeta - A Metadata Model for Research Data in Computational Engineering. In: Garoufallou, E., Sartori, F., Siatiri, R., und Zervas, M. (Hrsg.) Metadata and Semantic Research. S. 127-132. Metadata and Semantic Research, Cham (2019).
- Iglezakis, D., Schembera, B.: Anforderungen der Ingenieurwissenschaften an das Forschungsdatenmanagement der Universität Stuttgart - Ergebnisse der Bedarfsanalyse des Projektes DIPL-ING. o-bib. Das offene Bibliotheksjournal. 3, (2018).
- Schembera, B., Bönisch, T.: Challenges of Research Data Management for High Performance Computing. International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital

Libraries. S. 140--151. International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (2017).

van Wezel, J., Hammad, A., Krauß, P., Kurze, T., Meyer, J., Potthoff, J., Schembera, B.: Towards an Interoperable Data Archive. Gehalten auf der EUMETSAT(2015).

Edwards, P. N., Mayernik, M. S., Batcheller, A. L., Bowker, G. C., & Borgman, C. L. (2011). Science friction: Data, metadata, and collaboration. *Social Studies of Science*, 41(5), 667–690. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312711413314>

Murray-Rust, P., Townsend, J. A., Adams, S. E., Phadungsukanan, W., & Thomas, J. (2011). The semantics of Chemical Markup Language (CML): dictionaries and conventions. *Journal of cheminformatics*, 3(1), 43.

HLRS

- **Metadata Extractor *ExtractIng***: This tool was developed for automated metadata extraction and is currently in the process of Open Source publication on GitHub.

- **Dataverse Respository *DaRUS***: Within the DIPL-ING Project, a prototypical research data respository was deployed and is now ready to use⁴⁸.

- **Metadata Model *EngMeta***: The metadata model *EngMeta* was developed within the project DIPL-ING and was released as an XML Schema⁴⁹.

- **PRACE**: European supercomputer infrastructure. HLRS has a responsibility for high speed data transfers.

-**InHPC-DE**: Fostering a tighter technical integration of the GCS centres, HLRS is leading the Work Package on Data Management.

- PREMIS⁵⁰

- ExptML⁵¹

- CodeMeta⁵²

- DataCite⁵³

- Dataverse⁵⁴

- CML⁵⁵

⁴⁸ <https://www.izus.uni-stuttgart.de/fokus/darus/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.izus.uni-stuttgart.de/fokus/engmeta/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/>

⁵¹ <http://exptml.sourceforge.net/>

⁵² <https://codemeta.github.io/>

⁵³ <https://datacite.org/>

⁵⁴ <https://dataverse.org/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.xml-cml.org/>

- GridFTP⁵⁶

⁵⁶ <http://www.prace-ri.eu/data-transfer-with-gridftp/>

7.2 Curricula vitae and lists of publications

Prof. Dr. Matthias Beller

Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse e. V.

Albert-Einstein-Straße 29a

18059 Rostock

Phone +49(381)1281-113

E-Mail Matthias.Beller@catalysis.de

University training and degree

1982 - 1987 Study of chemistry at Georg-August-Universität, Göttingen

1987 - 1989 PhD thesis at the Institute for Organic Chemistry at Georg-August-Universität, Göttingen (Prof. Dr. L. F. Tietze), Graduation with honors (Dr. rer. nat.)

1990 postdoctoral stay with Prof. PhD K. B. Sharpless at Massachusetts Institute of Technology (USA)

Profession

1991 - 1993 Research chemist in the Central Research at Hoechst AG

1993 Group leader of "Organometallic chemistry - catalysis" at the Central Research of Hoechst AG

1994 - 1995 Project leader of "Homogeneous catalysis" at Hoechst AG

1996 - 1998 Associate Professor for Inorganic chemistry at the Technical University of Munich

June 1998 Director of the "Leibniz-Institut für Organische Katalyse an der Universität Rostock e.V. (IfOK)" aligned with a full professorship "Catalysis" at the University of Rostock

March 2001 Call for a C4-Professorship for Industrial Chemistry at the RWTH Aachen

Dec. 2005 Director of the newly founded „Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse e.V.“

Sept. 2006 Call for a W3-Professorship for Organic Chemistry at the Georg-August-Universität Göttingen

Awards and other activities (selection)

1997 Otto Roelen-Medaille der DECHEMA

2004 - 2006 Head of the Board of the German Catalysis Society „ConNeCat“

2006 Leibniz-Prize of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft

Innovation Award (Hansestadt Rostock, Germany)

Verdienstorden am Bande der Bundesrepublik Deutschland

- 2006 - 2014 Head of the Board of the GDCh working group "Sustainable Chemistry"
 since 2007 Member of the Board of the Department „Science and Technology of Life, Light and Matter“ at the University of Rostock
- 2008 - 2014 Member of the Board of the "German Catalysis Society", "GECATS"
 since 2009 Member of the Board of the "European Technology Platform SusChem"
 since 2009 Member of the "Deutsche Akademie der Naturwissenschaften Leopoldina"
- 2010 Paul Rylander Award of the Organic Reactions Catalysis Society (USA)
 2010 European Sustainable Chemistry Award of the EuChemS
 2012 Gay-Lussac-Humboldt Award of the French Academy of Sciences
 since 2012 Vice-President of the Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Society, WGL
- 2014 Emil-Fischer-Medaille
 2015 ERC Advanced Grant
 2016 Honorary Doctor of the University of Rennes 1
 since 2016 Member of Scientific Advisory Board of ARC CBBC
- 2017 Karl Ziegler Prize from the GDCh, German Chemical Society
 Dr. Karl Wamsler Innovation Award für Katalyse-Forschung (TU München und Chemieunternehmen Clariant)
- 2018 EAB Member SFB 1333 University of Stuttgart
 Highly Cited Researchers 2018
- 2019 Member of the Scientific Advisory Board of the DWI (Leibniz-Institute for interactive materials)

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. **2019** Sang R, Kucmierczyk P, Dühren R, Razzaq R, Dong K, [Liu J](#), Franke R, Jackstell R, **Beller M**. Synthesis of Carboxylic Acids by Palladium-catalyzed Hydroxycarbonylation. *Angewandte Chemie (International Ed. in English)*. DOI: [10.1002/anie.201908451](#)
2. **2019** Li W, Liu W, Leonard D, Rabeah J, Junge K, Brückner A, **Beller M**. Practical Catalytic Cleavage of C(sp³)-C(sp³) Bonds in Amines. *Angewandte Chemie (International Ed. in English)*. DOI: [10.1002/anie.201903019](#)
3. **2018** Liu J, Dong K, Franke R, Neumann H, Jackstell R, **Beller M**. Selective Palladium-Catalyzed Carbonylation of Alkynes: An Atom-Economic Synthesis of 1,2-Dicarboxylic Acid Diesters. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. DOI: [10.1021/jacs.8b05852](#)
4. **2018** Formenti D, Ferretti F, Scharnagl FK, Beller M. Reduction of Nitro Compounds Using 3d-Non-Noble Metal Catalysts. *Chemical Reviews*. DOI: [10.1021/acs.chemrev.8b00547](#)

5. **2017** Jagadeesh RV, Murugesan K, Alshammari AS, Neumann H, Pohl MM, Radnik J, **Beller M**. MOF-derived cobalt nanoparticles catalyze a general synthesis of amines. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*. DOI: [10.1126/science.aan6245](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan6245)
6. **2017** Dong K, Fang X, Güllak S, Franke R, Spannenberg A, Neumann H, Jackstell R, **Beller M**. Highly active and efficient catalysts for alkoxy-carbonylation of alkenes. *Nature Communications*. 8: 14117. DOI: [10.1038/ncomms14117](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14117)
7. **2016** [Li H](#), Dong K, Jiao H, Neumann H, Jackstell R, **Beller M**. The scope and mechanism of palladium-catalysed Markovnikov alkoxy-carbonylation of alkenes. *Nature Chemistry*. 8: 1159-1166. DOI: [10.1038/nchem.2586](https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.2586)
8. **2016** Elangovan S, Neumann J, Sortais JB, Junge K, Darcel C, **Beller M**. Efficient and selective N-alkylation of amines with alcohols catalysed by manganese pincer complexes. *Nature Communications*. 7: 12641. DOI: [10.1038/ncomms12641](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms12641)
9. **2015** Jagadeesh RV, Stemmler T, Surkus AE, Bauer M, Pohl MM, Radnik J, Junge K, Junge H, Brückner A, **Beller M**. Cobalt-based nanocatalysts for green oxidation and hydrogenation processes. *Nature Protocols*. 10: 916-26. DOI: [10.1038/nprot.2015.049](https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2015.049)
10. **2015** Li H, Dong K, Neumann H, **Beller M**. Palladium-Catalyzed Hydroamidocarbonylation of Olefins to Imides. *Angewandte Chemie (International Ed. in English)*. DOI: [10.1002/anie.201503954](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201503954)

Prof. Dr. Peter Benner

Max Planck Institute for Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems
Department “Computational Methods in Systems and Control Theory”
Sandtorstrasse 1, 39106 Magdeburg, Germany
Phone +49 (391) 6110 451 (-450 for secretary)
Email benner@mpi-magdeburg.mpg.de

Education

2001	Habilitation/Venia Legendi in Mathematics, U Bremen
1997	PhD in Mathematics, TU Chemnitz-Zwickau
1993	Diplom in Mathematics with minor in Economics, RWTH Aachen

Research Experience

2013 – 2014	Managing Director of the Max Planck Institute for Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems, Magdeburg
Since 2011	Honorarprofessor (Adjunct Professor), Otto von Guericke U Magdeburg
Since 2010	Director and Scientific Member of the Max Planck Institute for Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems, Magdeburg
Since 2010	Head of “Mathematics in Industry and Technology”, TU Chemnitz
2003 – 2010	Full Professor “Mathematics in Industry and Technology”, TU Chemnitz
2002 – 2003	Lecturer at the Institute for Mathematics, TU Berlin
2001 – 2002	Visiting Associate Professor, TU Hamburg-Harburg
1997 – 2001	Assistant Professor at the Center for Industrial Mathematics, U Bremen

Funding

Until now, responsible for more than 15 grant projects with resources for staff (PhD students or postdocs) and equipment, financed by the European Commission, COST, the German Ministries for Education and Research/Economics and Energy (BMBF/BMWi), the German Research Foundation (DFG), the Max Planck Strategic Innovation Fund, and industry.

Professional Activities and Memberships

Since 2019	Member of the SIAM Book Committee
2019–2022	Member of the SIAM Council

Since 2017	Chair of Max Planck network “BiGmax: MaxNet on Big-Data-Driven Materials Science”
2017–2019	Member of the “SIAM Fellow Selection Committee”
2014–2017	Member of the selection committee “SIAM W. T. and Idalia Reid Prize”
Since 2013	Member of the Scientific Advisory and Programme Committee of the European Conference on Computational Optimization (EUCCO),
Since 2013	Member of the Scientific Committee of the European Conference on Numerical Mathematics and Advanced Applications
Since 2013	GAMM delegate, International Council for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (ICIAM)
2012–2020	Member of the council of the European Mathematical Society (EMS)
2012	Member of the Scientific Committee of the 2012 SIAM Conference on Applied Linear Algebra, Valencia
2011–2016	Member of the GAMM Managing Board
Since 2011	Member of the Executive and Scientific Committees of the Model Reduction of Parametrized Systems (MoRePaS) workshops
2011	Co-chair of the 17th Conference of the International Linear Algebra Society (ILAS), 2011, Braunschweig
Since 2010	Member of the Steering Committee of the Model Reduction of Complex Dynamical Systems (MODRED) workshops
2009–2013	Chair of GAMM Activity Group “Applied and Numerical Linear Algebra”
Since 2007	Member of the Steering Committee of the Matrix Equations and Tensor Techniques (METT) workshops
Since 2004	Associate and Guest Editorships of 11 scientific journals and 2 book series in Mathematics and Computer Science with peer review

Honors and Recognitions

2018	J. Tinsley Oden Faculty Fellowship, U Texas at Austin
2017	SIAM Fellow (Class of 2017)
2015	Distinguished Professor, Shanghai U
2010	Guest Professorship U Littoral Côte d’Opale, Calais
1993	Springorum-Denk Münze of RWTH Aachen for excellent diploma thesis

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

- [1] P. Benner, V. Khoromskaia, and B. N. Khoromskij. Range-Separated Tensor Format for Many-Particle Modeling. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 40(2):A1034–A1062, 2017. [doi:10.1137/16M1098930](https://doi.org/10.1137/16M1098930)
- [2] P. Benner, J. Bremer, L. Feng, P. Goyal, and K. Sundmacher. POD-DEIM for Efficient Reduction of a Dynamic 2D Catalytic Reactor Model. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 106:777-784, 2017. [doi:10.1016/j.compchemeng.2017.02.032](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2017.02.032)
- [3] P. Benner, S. Gugercin, and K. Willcox. A Survey of Projection-Based Model Reduction Methods for Parametric Dynamical Systems. *SIAM Review*, 57(4): 483-531, 2015. [doi:10.1137/130932715](https://doi.org/10.1137/130932715).
- [4] E. Bänsch, P. Benner, J. Saak, and H. K. Weichelt. Riccati-Based Boundary Feedback Stabilization of Incompressible Navier-Stokes Flow. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 37(2): A832-A858, 2015. [doi:10.1137/140980016](https://doi.org/10.1137/140980016).
- [5] P. Benner and T. Breiten. Two-Sided Projection Methods for Nonlinear Model Order Reduction. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 37(2): B239-B260, 2015. [doi:10.1137/14097255X](https://doi.org/10.1137/14097255X).
- [6] M. Mangold, D. Khlopov, S. Palis, L. Feng, P. Benner, D. Binev, and A. Seidel-Morgenstern. *Nonlinear Model Reduction of a Continuous Fluidized Bed Crystallizer*. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, 289:253-266, 2015. [doi:10.1137/14097255X](https://doi.org/10.1137/14097255X).
- [7] P. Benner, and T. Damm. Lyapunov Equations, Energy Functionals, and Model Order Reduction of Bilinear and Stochastic Systems. *SIAM Journal on Control and Optimization*, 49(2): 686-711, 2011. [doi:10.1137/09075041X](https://doi.org/10.1137/09075041X).
- [8] P. Benner, R.-J. Li, and T. Penzl. Numerical Solution of Large Lyapunov Equations, Riccati Equations, and Linear-Quadratic Control Problems. *Numerical Linear Algebra with Applications*, 15(9): 755-777, 2008. [doi:10.1002/nla.622](https://doi.org/10.1002/nla.622).
- [9] P. Benner, and E. S. Quintana-Ortí. Solving Stable Generalized Lyapunov Equations with the Matrix Sign Function. *Numerical Algorithms*, 20(1): 75-100, 1999. [doi:10.1023/A:1019191431273](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1019191431273).
- [10] P. Benner, V. Mehrmann, and H. Xu. A Numerically Stable, Structure Preserving Method for Computing the Eigenvalues of Real Hamiltonian or Symplectic Pencils. *Numerische Mathematik*, 78(3): 329-358, 1998. [doi:10.1007/s002110050315](https://doi.org/10.1007/s002110050315).

Prof. Dr. Uwe Bornscheuer

Professor for Biotechnology & Enzyme Catalysis,

Institute of Biochemistry,

Greifswald University,

Phone +49 (0)3834 420 4367

Email uwe.bornscheuer@uni-greifswald.de

Education and Professional Background

1985 – 1990 Study of Chemistry at the University of Hannover

1991 – 1993 PhD thesis under the supervision of Professor Dr. Karl Schügerl and Prof Dr. Thomas Scheper (Institute of Technical Chemistry, Hannover University)

1993 – 1994 Postdoc in the lab of Prof. Dr. Tsuneo Yamane, Nagoya University, Nagoya, Japan

1994 – 1998 Habilitation at the Institute of Technical Biochemistry, Stuttgart University, Stuttgart

Since 1999 Professor and Head of Dept. of Biotechnology & Enzyme Catalysis, Institute of Biochemistry, Greifswald University.

10/2002 – 09/2008: (Managing) Director of the Institute of Biochemistry, Greifswald

10/2003 – 03/2004: Sabbatical at Diversa Corp. (now Verenum Corp.), San Diego, USA

10/2004: Declined two offers for Professorship at the Technical University of Freiberg and Hamburg-Harburg (Germany)

08/2009: Cofounder and Chairman of Advisory Board of Enzymicals AG

02 – 03/2010: JSPS research fellow, Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan

04 – 07/2017: Sabbatical at INRA/University Toulouse, Toulouse, France

Since 04/2018: Vice Dean of the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Greifswald University

Honors/Awards

- Greifswald Research Award (2018)
- Stephen S. Chang Award (AOCS, USA) 2015
- Kaufmann Medaille (DGF, Deutschland) 2014
- Chevreul Medal (SFEL, France) 2012
- Biocat2008 Award (Hamburg) 2008
- Two fellowships from the Japanese Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS), 1993, 2010

- Stipends of the 'Fonds der Chemischen Industrie', Germany, 1993, 1996-1998

Scientific Output

- >480 publications (WoS h-index: 64, GoogleScholar h-index: 80)
- >40 patent applications
- >40 book chapters

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. Reisky, L., Préchoux, A., Zühlke, A.K., Bäumgen, M., Robb, C.S., Gerlach, N., Roret, T., Stanetty, C., Larocque, R., Michel, G., Song, T., Markert, S., Unfried, F., Mihovilovic, M.D., Trautwein-Schulz, A., Becher, D., Schweder, T.*, **Bornscheuer, U.T.***, Hehemann, J.H.* (2019), A marine bacterial enzymatic cascade degrades the algal polysaccharide ulvan, *Nat. Chem. Biol.*, **15**, 803-812
2. Palm, G.J., Reisky, L., Böttcher, D., Müller, H., Michels, E., Walczak, M. C., Berndt, L., Weiss, M.S., **Bornscheuer, U.T.***, Weber, G.* (2019), Structure of the plastic-degrading *I. sakaiensis* MHETase bound to a substrate, *Nat. Commun.*, **10**, 1717.
3. Reisky, L., Büchenschütz, H.C., Engel, J., Song, T., Schweder, T., Hehemann, J.H.*, **Bornscheuer, U.T.*** (2018), Oxidative demethylation of algal carbohydrates by cytochrome P450 monooxygenases, *Nature Chem. Biol.*, **14**, 342-344
4. Rudroff, F., Mihovilovic, M.D., Gröger, H., Snajdrova, R., Iding, H., **Bornscheuer, U.T.*** (2018), Opportunities and challenges for combining chemo- and biocatalysis, *Nature Catal.* **1**, 12-22.
5. Pavlidis, I.V., Weiß, M.S., Genz, M., Spurr, P., Hanlon, S.P., Wirz, B. Iding, H., **Bornscheuer, U.T.*** (2016), Identification of (S)-selective transaminases for the asymmetric synthesis of bulky chiral amines, *Nature Chem.*, **8**, 1076-1082
6. Schmidt, S., Scherkus, C., Muschiol, J., Menyes, U., Winkler, T., Hummel, W., Gröger, H., Liese, A., H.-G. Herz, **Bornscheuer, U.T.*** (2015), An enzyme cascade synthesis of ϵ -caprolactone and its oligomers, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **54**, 2784-2787.
7. Gall, M., Thomsen, M., Peters, C., Pavlidis, I.V., Jonczyk, P., Grünert, P.P., Beutel, S., Scheper, T., Gross, E., Backes, M., Ley, J.P., Hilmer, J.M., Krammer, G., Geissler, T., Palm, G., Hinrichs, W., **Bornscheuer, U.T.*** (2014), Enzymatic conversion of flavonoids using bacterial chalcone isomerase and enoate reductase, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **53**, 1439-1442.
8. **Bornscheuer, U.T.***, Huisman, G., Kazlauskas, R.J., Lutz, S., Moore, J., Robins, K. (2012) Engineering the third wave in biocatalysis, *Nature*, **485**, 185-194.

9. Höhne, M., Schätzle, S., Jochens, H., Robins, K., **Bornscheuer, U.T.*** (2010) Rational assignment of key motifs for function guides *in silico* enzyme identification, *Nature Chem. Biol.*, **6**, 807-813.
10. Kazlauskas, R.J., **Bornscheuer, U.T.*** (2009), Finding better protein engineering strategies, *Nat. Chem. Biol.*, **5**, 526-529.

*corresponding authors

Prof. Dr. Olaf Deutschmann

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Institute for Chemical Technology and Polymer Chemistry (ITCP)

Engesserstr. 20, D-76131 Karlsruhe.

Phone +49 (0) 721 608 – 43064

Email: deutschmann@kit.edu

University training and degree

1986-1991 Physics, Technical University of Magdeburg and the Humboldt University Berlin, Germany, MSc in Physics (Diplom-Physiker)

Advanced academic qualification

1998-2001 Habilitation, Venia legendi Physical Chemistry, Heidelberg University, Germany, mentor: Prof. J. Warnatz

1992-1996 PhD work, Dr. rer. nat. in Chemistry, Department of Chemistry at Heidelberg University, Germany, supervisor: Prof. J. Warnatz

Postgraduate professional career

since 2006 Professor (W3/Full), Chair in Chemical Technology, Director at the Institute for Chemical Technology and Polymer Chemistry, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) (former University of Karlsruhe)

2003-06 Assoc. Professor (C3) for Chemical Technology, University of Karlsruhe, Institute for Chemical Technology and Polymer Chemistry

1999-2002 Assistant Professor (C1, C2, Hochschuldozent), Heidelberg University, Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing (IWR)

1998 Consultant, Los Alamos National Laboratory, Division of Chemical Science and Technology, Los Alamos, NM, USA

1997-1998 Postdoc with Lanny D. Schmidt, University of Minnesota, Department of Chemical Engineering and Materials Science, Minneapolis, MN, USA

Honors and awards

2018 Fellow of The Combustion Institute, Pittsburgh, USA, for pioneering research in heterogeneous catalysis in support of combustion and energy-conversion technologies.

2006 Offer for Chair in Combustion Technology at University of Stuttgart (declined)

2004 DECHEMA Award of the Max Buchner Research Foundation

- 2001 Distinguished Lecturer Series, Catalysis Center of the University of California at Berkeley
- 1991 Hermann - Oberth - Medal in Silver, International Astronautical Federation

Selected positions and professional commitments

- 2017 Visiting Professor (6 months) at Colorado School of Mines, Golden, CO, USA
- since 2016 Adjunct member of the Faculty for Chemical Engineering at KIT
- since 2015 Editorial Board of "International Journal of Chemical Kinetics"
- since 2014 Coordinator at KIT of the DFG Collaborative Research Centres (SFB/TRR 150) "Turbulent, chemically reacting, multi-phase flows near walls"
- since 2014 Editorial Board of "Journal of Emission Control Science and Technology"
- since 2013 Editorial Board of "The Proceedings of The Combustion Institute"
- since 2013 Board of Directors of "Institute of Catalysis Research and Technology" and Coordinator of the Division "Modeling and Simulation", KIT – National Laboratory
- since 2011 Founding Directors of "Abgaszentrum Karlsruhe"
- since 2010 Speaker of the Helmholtz Research School "Energy-Related Catalysis"
- since 2008 Director of the Steinbeis Transfer Center Reactive Flows, an enterprise of the Steinbeis GmbH & Co. KG für Technologietransfer, Stuttgart, Germany

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. Banerjee, Y. Wang, J. Diercks, O. Deutschmann. Hierarchical Modeling of Solid Oxide Cells and Stacks producing Syngas via H₂O/CO₂ Co-electrolysis for Industrial Applications. *Appl. Energy* 230 (2018) 996.
2. M H. Gossler, L. Maier, S. Angeli, S. Tischer, O. Deutschmann. CaRMEN – A tool for analyzing and deriving kinetics in the real world. *PhysChemChemPhys* 20 (2018) 10857.
3. K A. Giehr, L. Maier, S. Schunk, O. Deutschmann. Thermodynamic considerations on the stability of Co/ γ -Al₂O₃ and Ni/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalysts under dry and steam reforming conditions. *ChemCatChem* 10 (2018) 751.
4. V. Kappings, C. Grün, D. Ivannikov, I. Hebeiss, S. Kattge, I. Wendland, B.E. Rapp, M. Hettel, O. Deutschmann, U. Schepers. vasQchip: A novel microfluidic, artificial blood vessel scaffold for vascularized 3D tissues. *Advanced Materials Technologies* (2018) 1700246.

5. Spatially Resolved Operando Measurements in Heterogeneous Catalytic Reactors. Eds.: A. Dixon, O. Deutschmann. *Advances in Chemical Engineering*, vol. 50, 2017, Elsevier, ISBN 978-0-12-812589-2.
6. Banerjee, O. Deutschmann. Elementary Kinetics of the Oxygen Reduction Reaction on LSM-YSZ Composite Cathodes. *Journal of Catalysis* 346 (2017) 30.
7. S. Kannepalli, A. Gremminger, S. Tischer, O. Deutschmann. Optimization of axial catalyst loading in transient-operated zone-structured monoliths: Reduction of cumulative emissions in automotive oxidation catalysts. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 174 (2017) 189.
8. Karakaya, L. Maier, O. Deutschmann. Surface reaction kinetics of the oxidation and reforming of CH₄ over Rh/Al₂O₃ catalysts. *Int. J. Chem. Kinetics* 48 (2016) 144.
9. L. Kunz, F.M. Kuhn, O. Deutschmann. Kinetic Monte Carlo Simulations of Surface Reactions on supported nanoparticles: A novel approach and computer code. *Journal of Chemical Physics* 143 (2015) 044108.
10. Zellner, R. Suntz, O. Deutschmann. Two-dimensional spatial resolution of concentration profiles in catalytic reactors by planar laser-induced fluorescence: NO reduction over diesel oxidation catalysts. *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* 54 (2015) 2653.

Prof. Dr. Roger Gläser

Institute of Chemical Technology, Leipzig University,

Linnéstr. 3, 04103 Leipzig

Phone +49 (0)341 97-36301

Email roger.glaeser@uni-leipzig.de

Academic Education

10/1997 – 05/1993 Study of Chemistry, Universität Stuttgart, Diploma graduation; Prof. Dr.-Ing J. Weitkamp

Scientific Education

01/2007 Habilitation in Chemical Technology, Universität Stuttgart, Prof. Dr.-Ing. J. Weitkamp

06/1997 Doctorate in Chemical Technology, Universität Stuttgart, Prof. Dr.-Ing. J. Weitkamp

Professional Career

since 2016 Vice Dean of the Faculty of Chemistry and Mineralogy, Leipzig University, Germany

since 2011 Vice Director of the Virtual Institute for Energy Research (VIER), Leipzig University, Germany

since 2007 Full professor of Chemical Technology and Executive Director of the Institute of Chemical Technology, Leipzig University, Germany

Miscellaneous

Selected other professional activities:

02/2012-04/2014 Director of the Graduate Center Mathematics/Informatics and Natural Sciences of the Research Academy Leipzig

since 2010 Member of the Scientific Advisory Board of Institut für Energie- und Umwelttechnik e.V. (IUTA), Duisburg

since 08/2010 Elected member of the Council the Faculty of Chemistry and Mineralogy of Universität Leipzig

since 01/2011 Vice Director of the Virtual Institute for Energy Research (VIER) of Universität Leipzig

since 01/2014 Appointed Member of the Senate Commission for the Graduate Schools of the German Science Foundation (DFG)

since 2014 Speaker of the Research Profile Area "Sustainable Systems and

	Biodiversity" (one of nine centres of excellence at Leipzig University, together with Prof. T. Bruckner and Prof. C. Wirth)
06/2015-10/2018	Chair of the Scientific Advisory Board of Leibniz-Institute for Surface Modification (IOM), Leipzig
since 08/2016	Vice Dean of the Faculty of Chemistry and Mineralogy of Universität Leipzig
since 03/2017	Chairman of the Board of the German Zeolite Association
since 05/2018	Chairman of the Board of Trustees of Institut für Energie- und Umwelttechnik e.V. (IUTA), Duisburg
since 03/2019	Chairman of the Commission of the German Catalysis Society (GeCatS)

Honors:

2006	Young Faculty Award 2006 of the Society of Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology (DECHEMA)
2002	Jochen-Block-Award of the Catalysis Section of the Society of Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology (DECHEMA)

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. M. Purfürst, S. Naumov, K.-J. Langeheinecke und R. Gläser, Influence of Soot on Ammonia Adsorption and Catalytic DeNO_x-Properties of Diesel Particulate Filters Coated with SCR-Catalysts, *Chemical Engineering Science* 2017, 168, 423-436.
2. N. Wilde, J. Přeč, M. Pelz, M. Kubů, J. Čejka, R. Gläser, Accessibility Enhancement of TS-1-Based Catalysts for Improving the Epoxidation of Plant Oil-Derived Substrates, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 2016, 6, 7280-728.
3. J. Titus, T. Roussière, G. Wasserschaff, S. Schunk, A. Milanov, E. Schwab, G. Wagner, O. Oeckler, R. Gläser, Dry Reforming of Methane with Carbon Dioxide over NiO-MgO-ZrO₂, *Catal. Today* 2016, 270, 68-75.
4. N. Wilde, M. Pelz, S. Gebhardt, R. Gläser, Highly Efficient Nano-Sized TS-1 with Micro/Mesoporosity from Desilication and Recrystallization for the Epoxidation of Biodiesel with H₂O₂, *Green Chemistry* 2015, 17, 3378-3389.
5. M. Lange, M. Kobalz, J. Bergmann, D. Lässig, J. Lincke, J. Möllmer, A. Möller, J. Hofmann, H. Krautscheid, R. Staudt, R. Gläser, Structural Flexibility of a Copper-Based Metal Organic Framework: Adsorption of C₄-Hydrocarbons and in situ XRD, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 2014, 2, 8075-8085.
6. M. Bastos-Neto, C. Patzschke, M. Lange, J. Möllmer, A. Möller, S. Fichtner, C. Schrage, D. Lässig, J. Lincke, R. Staudt, H. Krautscheid, R. Gläser, Assessment of Hydrogen

- Storage by Physisorption in Porous Materials, *Energy & Environmental Sci.* 2012, 5, 8294-8303.
7. N. Novak Tušar, S. Jank, R. Gläser, Manganese-Containing Porous Silicates: Synthesis, Structural Properties and Catalytic Applications, *ChemCatChem* 2011, 3, 254-269.
 8. R. Gläser, "Heterogeneous Catalysis", in: "Handbook of Green Chemistry", P. Anastas, Hrsg., Band 4: "Supercritical Solvents", W. Leitner und P.G. Jessop, Hrsg., Kapitel 6, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim (2010), S. 243-279.
 9. R. Valiullin, J. Kärger, R. Gläser, Correlating Phase Behaviour and Diffusion in Mesopores: Perspectives Revealed by Pulsed Field Gradient NMR, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 2009, 11, 2781-2992.
 10. M. Dvoyashkin, R. Valiullin, J. Kärger, W.-D. Einicke, R. Gläser, Direct Assessment of Transport Properties of Supercritical Fluids Confined to Nanopores, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2007, 129, 10344-10345.

Dr. Marco Haumann

Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Chemie- und Bioingenieurwesen (CBI)

Lehrstuhl für Chemische Reaktionstechnik (CRT)

Egerlandstraße

91058 Erlangen

Phone +49 9131 85-67420

Email marco.haumann@fau.de

3

Education / work experience

1989-09.1991	Mechanical Engineering, TU Dortmund, Germany.
1991-12.1997	Chemistry, TU Berlin, Germany.
1995-06.1996	DAAD scholarship, University of Greenwich, London, UK.
1998-08.2001	Dissertation "Hydroformylation of higher alkenes in microemulsions", Prof. Reinhard Schomäcker, TU Berlin, Germany.
2002-10.2003	Post-doctoral research fellow "New ligand modified cobalt complexes as hydroformylation catalysts", Sasol Technology (Pty) Ltd, Sasolburg, South Africa.
2003-12.2010	Senior scientist, Prof. Peter Wasserscheid, Chemical Reaction Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, Germany.
2011-12.2012	Branch Campus Vice President, FAU Busan, South Korea.
2013-present	Senior scientist, Prof. Peter Wasserscheid, Chemical Reaction Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, Germany.
2014-03.2015	Deputy W3 professorship, Chemical Engineering, Ulm University, Germany.

Research interests

Homogeneous catalysis, Immobilization techniques, Kinetics, Reaction engineering, Reactor design, Heterogeneous catalysis, supported ionic liquid phase (SILP) technology.

Scientific visibility

> 60 publications in peer reviewed journals (>2200 citations, h-factor 27, Scopus, 09/2019).

8 book chapters, 10 patents together with industrial partners.

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

(peer-reviewed journals only)

1. *First very stable and highly regioselective supported ionic liquid-phase (SILP) catalysis: Continuous-flow fixed-bed hydroformylation of propene.* A. Riisager, R. Fehrmann, S. Flicker, R. van Hal, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, *Angew. Chem.*, 2005, 117, 826, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2005, 44, 815 (VIP).
2. *Chromium catalyzed tetramerization of ethylene in a continuous tube reactor - Proof of concept and kinetic aspects.* S. Kuhlmann, C. Paetz, C. Hägele, K. Blann, R. Walsh, J. T. Dixon, J. Scholz, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, *J. Catal.* 2009, 262, 83.
3. *Ultra-Low-Temperature Water–Gas Shift Catalysis using Supported Ionic Liquid Phase (SILP) Materials.* S. Werner, N. Szesni, M. Kaiser, R.W. Fischer, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, *Chem. Cat. Chem.* 2010, 2, 1399.
4. *Ethene-induced, Temporary Inhibition of Grubbs Metathesis Catalysts.* J. Scholz, A. Demin, S. Loekman, N. Szesni, W. Hieringer, A. Görling, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, *Adv. Synth. Cat.* 2011, 353, 2701.
5. *Continuous gas-phase hydroaminomethylation using supported ionic liquid phase catalysts.* M.J. Schneider, M. Lijewski, R. Wölfel, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2013, 52, 6996.
6. *Ethylene to 2-Butene in a Continuous Gas Phase Reaction using SILP-Type Cationic Nickel Catalysts.* J. Scholz, V. Hager, X. Wang, F.T.U. Kohler, M. Sternberg, M. Haumann, N. Szesni, K. Meyer, P. Wasserscheid, *ChemCatChem* 2014, 6, 162.
7. *Supported homogeneous catalyst makes its own liquid phase.* A. Kaftan, A. Schönweiz, I. Nikiforidis, W. Hieringer, K.M. Dybala, R. Franke, A. Görling, J. Libuda, P. Wasserscheid, M. Laurin, M. Haumann, *J. Catal.* 2015, 321, 32.
8. *Detailed Investigation of the Mechanism of Rh-Diphosphite Supported Ionic Liquid Phase (SILP)-Catalyzed 1-Butene Hydroformylation in the Gas Phase via Combined Kinetic and Density Functional Theory (DFT) Modeling Studies.* S. Walter, H. Spohr, R. Franke, W. Hieringer, P. Wasserscheid, M. Haumann, *ACS Catal.* 2017, 7, 1035-1044.
9. *Dynamic equilibria in supported ionic liquid phase (SILP) catalysis: in situ IR spectroscopy identifies $[RuCO)_xCl_y]_n$ species in water gas shift catalysis.* T. Bauer, R. Stepic, P. Wolf, F. Kollhoff, W. Karawacka, C.R. Wick, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, D.M. Smith, A.-S. Smith, J. Libuda, *Cat. Sci. Technol.* 2018, 8, 344.
10. *Mechanism of the Water–Gas Shift Reaction Catalyzed by Efficient Ruthenium-Based Catalysts: A Computational and Experimental Study.* R. Stepic, C.R. Wick, V. Strobel,

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Norbert Kockmann

TU Dortmund University
Faculty of Biochemical and Chemical Engineering
Laboratory of Equipment Design (W2)
Emil-Figge-Str. 68
D-44227 Dortmund
Phone +49-231-755-8077
Email Norbert.Kockmann@bci.tu-dortmund.de

Scientific and professional career:

- 1991 Diplom-Ingenieur, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, TU Munich, Prof. Dr. Klaus Ehrlenspiel
- 1991-1996 Scientific researcher at Chair of Technical Thermodynamics, Heat and Mass Transport, Faculty of Production Technology, University of Bremen, Prof. Dr. Klaus Genthner
- 1996 PhD thesis on Fouling in Suspension Flow in Vertical Falling Film
- 1997-2001 Project Manager at Messer Griesheim GmbH, Krefeld, finally manager for erection of air separation units and a Syngas plant, Dr. A. Knapp, Dr. J. Flato
- 10/2001-09/07 Research Assistant and group leader for Micro Process Engineering at the Chair of Design of Microsystems at Institute of Microsystems Technology (IMTEK) at Albert-Ludwig-University of Freiburg, Prof. Dr. Peter Woias
- 2007 Habilitation in the field of Microsystems Technology, Habilitation thesis on Transport Phenomena in Micro Process Engineering
- 10/2007-03/11 Head of chemical laboratory and Senior Scientist at Lonza AG, Visp, CH, Dr. W. Brieden, Dr. J. Pont, Dr. A. Heyl
- 04/2011 Professor of Equipment Design at TU Dortmund, Faculty of Biochemical and Chemical Engineering

Awards:

- 2009 ASME ICNMM09 Outstanding Researcher Award
- 2010 Sandmeyer Prize for Industrial Chemistry of Swiss Chemical Society
- 2013 Prize of best presentation at ProcessNet-FG-meeting Extraction; Poster prize of the ProcessNet-FG meeting Extraction
- 2015 ASME ICNMM2015 Outstanding Researcher Award; ASME ICNMM2015 Poster Award

- 2016 ASME ICNMM2016 Poster Award
- 2017 Best Presentation ProcessNet-FG-meeting Crystallization; ASME ICNMM2017 Poster Award
- 2018 Poster Award at ProcessNet-FG-meeting Reaction Technology; CIT-Lecture on ProcessNet Annual Meeting

Miscellaneous:

- since 2004 Member of organizing committee of ASME-ICNMM
- 2009-2011 Member of SGVC Managing Board, responsible for Reaction Engineering
- 2011-2016 Chief Scientist at INVITE GmbH, a common research platform of TU Dortmund and Bayer Technology Services GmbH, Leverkusen, Germany
- 2013-2016 cooperating professor at LIKAT, Rostock, Germany
- since 06/2014 Dean of Studies of the Faculty of Biochemical and Chemical Engineering
- since 01/2016 Vice chairman of ProcessNet-FG Process, Equipment and Plant Technology
- since 10/2016 Member of Editorial Board of Chemie-Ingenieur-Technik, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim
- since 10/2018 Member of Editorial Board of Theoretical Foundations of Chemical Engineering, Springer

Member in various committees of VDI Society Chemical and Process Engineering (VDI-GVC) and the Society for Chemical Technology and Biotechnology (DECHEMA); Member of VDI, Dechema, Society of University Professors, SGVC, ASME.

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. S. Schwolow, B. Heikenwälder, L. Abahmane, N. Kockmann, T. Röder, Kinetic and scale-up investigations of a Michael addition in microreactors, Org. Proc. R&D, 18, 1535-1544, 2014
2. S. Goicoechea, H. Ehrich, P.L. Arias, N. Kockmann, Thermodynamic analysis of acetic acid steam reforming for hydrogen production, J. Power Sources, 279, 312-322, 2015

3. S.K. Kurt, F. Warnebold, K.D.P. Nigam, N. Kockmann, Gas-Liquid Reaction and Mass Transfer in Microstructured Coiled Flow Inverter, *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, 169, 164-178, 2017
4. N. Kockmann, L. Bittorf, W. Krieger, F. Reichmann, M. Schmalenberg, S. Soboll, Smart Equipment – A Perspective Paper, *Chem. Ing. Technik*, 90 (11), 1806-1822, 2018
5. N. Kockmann, Abriss der Entwicklungsgeschichte der Reaktionstechnik, in W. Reschetilowski (Ed.) *Handbuch der Reaktionstechnik*, Springer, Berlin, 2018.
6. L. Bittorf, F. Reichmann, M. Schmalenberg, S. Soboll, N. Kockmann, Equipment and Separation Units for Flow Chemistry Applications and Process Development, *Chem. Eng. & Technol.*, online first, May 2019
7. N. Kockmann, Digital methods and tools for chemical equipment and plants, *Reac. Chem. & Eng.*, 4, 1522-1529, 2019
8. F. Reichmann, K. Vennemann, T.A. Frede, N. Kockmann, Mixing time scale determination in microchannels using reaction calorimetry, *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, 91(5), 622-631, 2019
9. S. Schwolow, B. Mutsch, N. Kockmann, T. Röder, Model-based scale-up and reactor design for solvent-free synthesis of an ionic liquid in a millistructured flow reactor, *Reac. Chem. & Eng.*, 4(3), 523-536, 2019
10. L. Hohmann, M. Schmalenberg, M. Prasanna, M. Matuschek, N. Kockmann, Suspension Flow Behavior and Particle Residence Time Distribution in Helical Tube Devices, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 360, 1371-1389, 2019

Prof. Dr. Udo Kragl

Universität Rostock

Institut für Chemie

Abteilung Technische und Analytische Chemie

Albert-Einstein-Straße 3a

18059 Rostock

Phone +49 (0)381/498-6450

Email udo.kragl@uni-rostock.de

Education and Professional Background

- 1981 – 1987 Study of Chemistry at the University of Bonn
- 1988 – 1992 Ph. D. thesis at the Institute of Biotechnology, Research Center Jülich (with Prof. Dr. Wandrey); grade: “excellent”)
- 1992 Post-Doc at Ciba Geigy Limited, International Research Laboratories, Takarazuka, Japan
- 1993 – 1998 Habilitation for “Technische Chemie“ at University of Bonn
The experimental work was performed at the Institute of Biotechnology, Research Center Jülich
- Since 1998 Full Professor for Industrial Chemistry (Technische Chemie) at University of Rostock
- 2003 Offer from TU Munich for the same position declined
- 2003 Establishment of a Research Group at the Leibniz-Institute for Catalysis at University of Rostock, Topic: “Functionalisation of Compounds from Renewable Resources”
- 02 – 04.2007 Stay at National University of Singapore, Dept. of Chemistry as visiting professor

Awards

- 1997 Grant from the Karl-Winnacker-Foundation, Frankfurt
- 2012 Grant from the BMBF for the work on “Ionic liquids in Biotechnology”
- 2015 Title „Professor of the Year Jahres 2015“ in the category Medicine and Natural Sciences from the magazine UNICUMBeruf

2001 - 2004	Responsible for Students Affairs & Vice-Director of the Institute of Chemistry
2003 - 2008	Member of the Board of the DECHEMA section "Catalysis"
2004 - 2008	Member of the Board of the Competence Network Catalysis ConNeCat Germany
2004 - 2006	Dean of the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences of the University of Rostock
2007 - 2015	Founding Dean of the Faculty for Interdisciplinary Research at University of Rostock
08/2009	Cofounder of Enzymicals AG
2009 - 2019	Member of the Commission of the German Catalysis Society
Since 2011	Member of the Board BioConValley e.V.; since April 2015 Chairmen
Since 2015	Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer, Rostock University
Since 2019	Board member of the German Catalysis Society GeCats (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Katalyse)

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. Meyer, L.-E.; Gummesson, A.; **Kragl, U.** and von Langermann, J. Development of Ionic Liquid-Water-Based Thermomorphic Solvent (TMS)-Systems for Biocatalytic Reactions. *Biotechnology Journal* **14**, 1900215(2019), e1900215.DOI: 10.1002/biot.201900215
2. Großeheilmann, J. and **Kragl, U.**
Simple and Effective Catalyst Separation by Novel CO₂-induced Switchable Organocatalysts.
ChemSusChem **10**, 2685-2691 (2017)
3. Neise, C.; Rautenberg, C.; Bentrup, U.; Beck, M.; Ahrenberg, M.; Schick, C.; Keßler, O.; **Kragl, U.** Stability studies of ionic liquid [EMIm][NTf₂] under short-term thermal exposure
RSC Advances **6**, 48462-48468 (2016)
4. Kummer, S.; Ruth, W.; **Kragl, U.**; Kummer, S.; Ruth, W.; Kragl, U.
Electrochemical Initiated C-N Coupling of 3-Methylcatechol and n-Hexylamine in a Flow Cell Monitored with ESI-MS
Electroanalysis **28**, 1992 (2016)

5. Großeheilmann, J.; Fahrenwaldt, T.; **Kragl U.**
Organic Solvent Nanofiltration-Supported Purification of Organocatalysts
ChemCatChem **8**, 322-325 (2016)
6. Großeheilmann, J.; Bandomir, J.; **Kragl, U.** Preparation of Poly(ionic liquid)s-supported Recyclable Organocatalysts for the Asymmetric Nitroaldol (HENRY) Reaction
Chemistry - A European Journal **21**, 18957-18960 (2015); DOI: 10.1002/chem.201504290
7. Illner, S.; Hofmann, C.; Löb, P.; **Kragl, U.**
A Falling-Film Microreactor for Enzymatic Oxidation of Glucose
ChemCatChem **6**, 1748-1754 (2014)
8. Illner, S.; Plagemann, R.; Saling, P.; **Kragl, U.**
Eco-efficiency analysis as a reaction-engineering tool - Case study of a laccase-initiated oxidative C-N coupling
Journal of Molecular Catalysis B: Enzymatic **102**, 106-114 (2014)
9. Kohse, S.; Neubauer, A.; Pazidis, A.; Lochbrunner, S.; **Kragl, U.**: Photoswitching of Enzyme Activity by Laser Induced pH-Jump.
Journal of the American Chemical Society **135**, 9407-9411. (2013)
10. Wenda, S., Illner, S., Mell, A., **Kragl, U.** Industrial biotechnology – the future of green chemistry?
Green Chemistry **13**, 3007-3047 (2011); DOI: 10.1039/c1gc15579b

Dr.-Ing. habil. Ralph Krähnert

Group Leader, Technische Universität Berlin,

BasCat - UniCat BASF JointLab

Hardenbergstr. 36, 10623 Berlin,

Phone +49 30 314 73727

Email ralph.kraehnert@tu-berlin.de

University training and degree

03/2000 Diploma in Process Engineering, Technische Universität Clausthal, Mentors of diploma thesis: O.C. Sandall (UCSB) and A. Vogelpohl (TU Clausthal)

Advanced academic qualifications

11/2018 Habilitation in Technische Chemie, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany, Mentor: P. Strasser

11/2005 PhD in Chemical Engineering, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany, Mentor: M. Baerns

Postgraduate professional career

06/2018 - Group leader “Data science and modelling in heterogeneous catalysis” at BASCAT, The UNICAT-BASF Joint Lab, Technische Universität Berlin

06/2017 - 2018 Group leader “Catalysis and Modeling” at BASCAT, The UNICAT-BASF Joint Lab, Technische Universität Berlin

01/2011 - Leader of a junior research group (DFG-UNICAT), Technische Universität Berlin

05/2009 - 05/2012 Leader of a junior research group (BMBF- Nanofutur), Technische Universität Berlin, Mentor: P. Strasser

06/2007-04/2009 Leader of a junior research group (BMBF- Nanofutur), Leibniz-Institute for Catalysis Berlin, Mentor: B. Lücke

11/2005-05/2007 PostDoc, at Leibniz-Institute for Catalysis Berlin, Mentor: U. Dingerdissen

1999 - 2000 Research Scientist, University of California, Santa Barbara, USA, Mentor: O.C. Sandall

Other

- 2018 - Member of the executive board of DFG Priority program SPP 2080
- 2014 - 2018 Member of the executive board of the DFG Cluster of Excellence EXC 314 UNICAT
- 2013 - 2018 Member of executive board of DFG-SFB 1109
- 2012 - 2015 Einstein-Junior-Fellow of the Einstein Stiftung Berlin
- since 2009 Scientific Advisor for Start-up company "Creative Quantum" providing professional and research services in computational chemistry (<http://www.creative-quantum.eu>)
- 2006 Nanofutur-Young-Researcher-Award 2006 of the German Ministry of Science and Education BMBF

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. "A meta-analysis approach to catalysis: Property-performance relationships identified from literature data for the oxidative coupling of methane", R. Schmack, A. Friedrich, E. Kondratenko, J. Polte, A. Werwatz, R. Kraehnert, Nature Communications 2019, 10:441 , <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08325-8>
2. "Future's Challenge in Heterogeneous Catalysis: Understanding Catalysts under Dynamic Reaction Conditions", K. F. Kalz, R. Kraehnert, M. Dvoyashkin, R. Dittmeyer, R. Gläser, U. Krewer, K. Reuter, J. D. Grunwaldt, Chem Cat Chem, DOI: 10.1002/cctc.201600996
3. "Nanocasting of Superparamagnetic Iron Oxide Films with Ordered Mesoporosity", K. Kraffert, A. Kabelitz, K. Siemensmeyer, R. Schmack, D. Bernsmeier, F. Emmerling, R. Kraehnert, Advanced Materials Interfaces, <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/admi.201700960/abstract>
4. "Unifying Concepts in Room-Temperature CO Oxidation with Gold Catalysts", F. Kettemann, S. Witte, A. Birnbaum, B. Paul, G. Clavel, N. Pinna , K. Rademann , R. Kraehnert , J. Polte, ACS Catalysis (7), 2017, 8247–8254
5. "Highly active binder-free catalytic coatings for heterogeneous and electro catalysis: Pd on mesoporous carbon and its application in butadiene hydrogenation and hydrogen evolution" , D. Bernsmeier, L. Chenchom, B. Paul, S. Rümmler, B. Smarsly, R. Kraehnert, ACS Catal. 6,2016, 8255-8263
6. "Synthesis and OER activity of NiO coatings with micelle-templated mesopore structure ", M. Bernicke, B. Eckhardt, A. Lippitz, E. Ortel, D. Bernsmeier, R. Schmack, R. Kraehnert, ChemistrySelect 3, 2016, 482 -489
7. "Time resolved in situ studies on the formation mechanism of iron oxide nanoparticles using combined fast-XANES and SAXS", A. Kabelitz, A. Guilherme, M. Joester, U.

Reinholz, M. Radtke, R. Bienert, K. Schulz, R. Kraehnert, F. Emmerling, *Cryst. Eng. Comm.* 17, 2015, 8463-8470

8. "New triblock copolymer templates PEO-PB-PEO for the synthesis of Titania films with controlled mesopore size, wall thickness and bimodal porosity", E. Ortel, A. Fischer, L. Chuenchom, J. Polte, F. Emmerling, B.M. Smarsly, R. Kraehnert, *Small* 2012, 8 (2), 298–309.
9. "Mechanism of gold nano particle formation in the classical citrate synthesis method derived from coupled in-situ XANES and SAXS evaluation", J. Polte, T.T. Ahner, F. Delißen, S. Sokolov, F. Emmerling, A.F. Thünemann, R. Kraehnert, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, 132, 1296–1301.

Prof. Dr. Johannes August Lercher

Professor, Department Chemistry

Technische Universität München

Lichtenbergstrasse 4

85748 Garching, Germany

Phone 0049-89-28913540

johannes.lercher@mytum.de

Director, Institute for Integrated Catalysis

Pacific Northwest National Laboratory

902 Battelle Boulevard

Richland, WA 99352, USA

Phone 001-509-3752725

johannes.lercher@pnnl.gov

Academic education

1985 Habilitation (venia docendi) for Physical Chemistry at the Technische Universität Wien

1980 Dr. techn., Chemistry, Technische Universität Wien

(Advisor. Prof. Heinrich Noller)

"Acid Sites on Al₂O₃/MgO and Al₂O₃/SiO₂ Mixed Metal Oxides" (Summa cum Laude)

1978 Dipl. Ing., Chemistry, Technische Universität Wien (Summa cum Laude)

Professional experience

2011 - date Battelle Fellow, Director Institute for Integrated Catalysis, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, Richland, WA, USA

1998 - date Professor, Chemistry Department, Technische Universität München, Germany

2003 - 2007 Member of the Senate, Technische Universität München

2000 - 2003 Chairman of the Chemistry Department, Technische Universität München

1993 - 1998 Professor of Chemical Technology, University of Twente, The Netherlands

1990 - 1996 Head of the Christian Doppler Laboratory for Heterogeneous Catalysis

1989 - 1993 Head of the research group "Surface chemistry and Catalysis" at the Institute for Physical Chemistry, Technische Universität Wien

1989 - 1993 Associate Professor, Technische Universität Wien

1985 - 1989 Lecturer, Technische Universität Wien

1982 Research fellow and visiting lecturer, Yale University, Department of Chemical Engineering

1978 -1985 University Assistant at the Institute for Physical Chemistry, Technische Universität Wien

Service in professional organizations (selection)

2013 - 2017 President, European Federation of Catalysis Societies

2008 - 2014 Vice Chairman, German Catalysis Society

2007 - date German delegate, European Federation of Catalysis Societies

2007 - 2008 Member of DECHEMA Advisory board, Catalysis

2003 - 2015 Chairman of the Bavarian Section of the German Association of Gas, Coal and Petroleum

2001 - date Board of the German Association of Gas, Coal and Petroleum, Section petrochemistry

2001 - 2004 President, International Zeolite Association

Academy memberships

US National Academy of Inventors (2019 – date)

US National Academy of Engineering (2017 – date)

European Academy of Sciences (2015 – date)

Academia Europaea (2010 - date)

Austrian Academy of Sciences (2008 - date)

Awards, recognitions

David Trimm and Noel Cant Lectureship Award, Australian Catalysis Society (2017)

Hon. Professor, Tianjin University, China (2016)

ENI Award Hydrocarbons Downstream (2016)

R. B. Anderson Award, Canadian Catalysis Society (2015/16)

Francois Gault Lectureship Award (2013)

Kozo Tanabe Prize for Acid Base Catalysis (2013)

Hon. Professor, Dalian Institute of Chem. Physics, China (2012)

Hon. Professor, China University of Petroleum, China (2011)

Hon. Professor, CAS Qingdao Inst. of Bioenergy and Bioprocess Technology, China (2011)

Robert Burwell Lectureship in Catalysis, North American Catalysis Society (2011)

PE- Prof. R. Kumar CDS Award of the Indian Chemical Engineering Society (2005)

Shell – Center of Excellence Award (1998)

Christian Doppler Award (1989)

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. Lewis-Brønsted acid pairs in Ga/H-ZSM-5 to catalyze dehydrogenation of light alkanes
M.W. Schreiber, C. P. Plaisance, M. Baumgärtl, K. Reuter, A. Jentys, R. Bermejo-Deval, J. A. Lercher, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 140, 4849 (2018).
2. Design and synthesis of highly active MoVTaNb-oxides for ethane oxidative dehydrogenation
D. Melzer, G. Mestl, K. Wanninger, Y. Zhu, N. D. Browning, M. Sanchez-Sanchez, J. A. Lercher, *Nat. Comm.*, 10, 4012 (2019).
3. Hydrogen transfer pathways during zeolite catalyzed methanol conversion to hydrocarbons
S. Müller, Y. Liu, F. M. Kirchberger, M. Tonigold, M. Sanchez-Sanchez, J.A. Lercher, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 138, 15994 (2016).
4. Mechanism of phenol alkylation in zeolite HBEA using in situ solid state NMR spectroscopy
Z. Zhao, H. Shi, C. Wan, M. Y. Hu, Y. Liu, D. Mei, D. M. Camaioni, J. Z. Hu, J. A. Lercher, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 139, 9178 (2017).
5. Zeolite-catalyzed pathways for liquid-phase alkylation of phenol in apolar solvents and water
Y. Liu, E. Baráth, H. Shi, J. Hu, D. M. Camaioni, J.A. Lercher, *Nature Catalysis*, 1, 141 (2018).
6. Enhancing the catalytic activity of hydronium ions through constrained environments
Y. Liu, A. Vjunov, H. Shi, S. Eckstein, D. M. Camaioni, D. Mei, E. Barath, J. A. Lercher, *Nat. Comm.*, 8, 14113 (2017).
7. Influence of hydronium ions in zeolites on sorption
S. Eckstein, P. H. Hintermeier, R. Zhao, E. Baráth, H. Shi, Y. Liu, J. A. Lercher, *Angew. Chem.*, 58 3450 (2019).
8. Palladium catalyzed reductive insertion of alcohols in aryl ether bonds
M. Wang, O.Y. Gutiérrez, D. M. Camaioni, J.A. Lercher, *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.*, 57, 3747 (2018).
9. Nature of hydrogen adsorption on platinum in the aqueous phase
G. Yang, S.A. Akhade, X Chen, Y Liu, M.S. Lee, V. A. Glezakou, R. Rousseau, J.A. Lercher, *Angew. Chemie.*, 58, 3527 (2019).
10. Active sites catalyzing aromatics hydrogenation in Ni-promoted transition metal sulfides aromatics
W. Luo, H. Shi, E. Schachtl, O. Y. Gutiérrez, J. A. Lercher, *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.*, 57, 14555 (2018).

Prof. Dr. Walter Leitner

Director "Molecular Catalysis"

Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion

Stiftstraße 34-36

45470 Mülheim an der Ruhr

and

Lehrstuhl für Technische Chemie und Petrochemie

Institut für Technische Chemie und Makromolekulare Chemie (ITMC)

RWTH Aachen University

Worringerweg 2

52074 Aachen

Phone + 49-(0)208-306 3614

Email walter.leitner@cec.mpg.de

Education and Professional Experience

- | | |
|-------------|--|
| 1982-1987 | Studying Chemistry at the University of Regensburg (Dipl.-Chem. Univ.) |
| 1987 - 1989 | PhD (Dr. rer. nat.) with Prof. H. Brunner, Institute for Inorganic Chemistry at the University of Regensburg
(<i>Thesis</i> : Enantioselective Catalytic Transferhydrogenation using Formates) |
| 1990 | Postdoctoral Studies at the Dyson Perrins Laboratory for Organic Chemistry, University of Oxford, UK, with Prof. J. M. Brown |
| 1991 - 1992 | Liebig Fellow of the Fonds der Chemischen Industrie at the Institute for Inorganic Chemistry at the University of Regensburg |
| 1992 - 1995 | Research associate at the Max-Planck-Working Group „CO ₂ -Chemistry“ (Director: Prof. E. Dinjus) at the Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena. |
| 1995 | Habilitation (Dr. rer. nat. habil.) in Inorganic Chemistry and appointment as Privatdozent (lecturer) at the Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena
(<i>Thesis</i> : Catalytic Hydrogenation of Carbon Dioxide to Formic Acid) |
| 1995 - 1998 | Group leader at the Department of “Organic Synthesis” (Director: Prof. M. T. Reetz) at the Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Mülheim/Ruhr. |
| 1998 – 2002 | Head of the Technical Laboratories at the Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Mülheim/Ruhr |
| Since 2002 | Chair of Technical Chemistry and Petrochemistry, Institut für Technische and Makromolekulare Chemie, RWTH Aachen University |
| 2002-2017 | External Scientific Member of the Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Mülheim an der Ruhr |

- Since 2007 Scientific Director of CAT, the joint Catalytic Center of RWTH Aachen and Covestro
- Since 10/2017 Director for “Molecular Catalysis” at the Max-Planck-Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion (MPI CEC), Mülheim an der Ruhr

Other Current Professional Activities

- Since 2018 Member of the Editorial Board of the scientific journal “Angewandte Chemie”
- Since 2018 Member of the Board of the German Society for Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology, DECHEMA
- Since 2015 Member of the Scientific Council of the German Scientific Society of Oil, Gas, and Coal, DGMK
- Since 2019 Co-Speaker of the Cluster of Excellence “The Fuel Science Center” at RWTH Aachen University/MPI CEC
- Since 2016 Chairman of the Coordination Group of the Kopernikus Project “P2X: Exploration, Validation and Implementation of „Power-to-X“ Concepts”
- 2019 Chairman of the International Conference on Carbon Dioxide Utilization ICCDU
- 2019 Chairman of the 14th EuropaCat Conference
- 2019/2020 Chairman of the Gordon Conference on “Green Chemistry”

Selected Recognitions and Awards

- 1997 Gerhard-Hess-Award of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)
- 1998 Bennigsen-Foerder-Preis of Nordrhein-Westfalen (NRW)
- 1998 Carl-Zerbe-Award of the Deutsche Wissenschaftliche Gesellschaft für Erdöl, Erdgas und Kohle (DMGK)
- 2000 2nd International Messer Innovation-Award
- 2001 Otto-Roelen-Medal of DECHEMA
- 2003 Griess Lectureship of the Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)
- 2005 Guest Professorship at the Université de Bourgogne, Dijon, France
- 2008 CATSA Eminent Visitor Award of the South African Catalysis Society
- 2009 Wöhler Award of the Gesellschaft Deutscher Chemiker (GDCh)
- 2010 Fellow of the Royal Society of Chemistry (FRSC)
- 2011 Honorary Member of the Chemical Society of Ethiopia
- 2013 Visiting Lecturer for Promotion of Chemistry, National Science Foundation Taiwan
- 2014 European Sustainable Chemistry Award of the European Science Association of Chemical and Molecular Sciences (EuCheMS), jointly with Prof. Jürgen Klankermayer (RWTH Aachen)

- 2015 Nankai University Lectureship in Organic Chemistry, Nankai University, China
- 2015 Molecular Science Forum Lecture of Chinese Academy of Sciences and Chinese Chemical Society
- 2018 Casey Lecture of the University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA
- 2018 Evonik Lecture at the Biennial Meeting of the Chinese Chemical Society, Hangzhou, China
- 2019 Finalist for the “Deutsche Zukunftspreis” (German President's Award for Innovation in Science and Technology), together with Dr. Christoph Gürtler and Dr. Berit Stange (Covestro AG)

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. *Manganese-catalyzed hydroboration of carbon dioxide and other challenging carbonyl groups*
C. Erken, A. Kaithal, S. Sen, T. Weyhermüller, M. Hölscher, C. Werlé, W. Leitner
Nature Communications **2018**, *9*, 4521.
2. *Sustainable conversion of carbon dioxide: An integrated review of catalysis and life cycle assessment*
J. Artz, Jens, T.E. Müller, K. M. Thenert, J. Kleinekorte, R. Meys, A. D. Sternberg, André Bardow, W. Leitner
Chem. Rev. **2018**, *118*, 434–504.
3. *Bimetallic Nanoparticles in Supported Ionic Liquid Phases as Multifunctional Catalysts for the Selective Hydrodeoxygenation of Aromatic Substrates*
L. Offner-Marko, A. Bordet, G. Moos, S. Tricard, S. Rengshausen, B. Chaudret, K. L. Luska, W. Leitner
Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. **2018**, *57*, 12721-12726.
4. *Advanced Biofuels and Beyond: Chemistry Solutions for Propulsion and Production*
W. Leitner, J. Klankermayer, S. Pischinger, H. Pitsch, K. Kohse-Höinghaus
Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. **2017**, *56*, 5412-5452.
5. *Catalytic NH₃ Synthesis using N₂/H₂ at Molecular Transition Metal Complexes: Concepts for Lead Structure Determination using Computational Chemistry*
M. Hölscher, W. Leitner
Chemistry Eur. J. **2017**, *23*, 11992-12003.
6. *Selective Catalytic Synthesis Using the Combination of Carbon Dioxide and Hydrogen: Catalytic Chess at the Interface of Energy and Chemistry*
J. Klankermayer, S. Wesselbaum, K. Beydoun, W. Leitner,
Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. **2016**, *55*, 7296-7343.

7. *Harnessing Renewable Energy with CO₂ for the Chemical Value Chain: Challenges and Opportunities for Catalysis*
J. Klankermayer, W. Leitner
Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A, **2016**, 374, 20150315.
8. *Can Contemporary Density Functional Theory Predict Energy Spans in Molecular Catalysis Accurately Enough To Be Applicable for in Silico Catalyst Design? A Computational/Experimental Case Study for the Ruthenium-Catalyzed Hydrogenation of Olefins*
K. C. Rohmann, M. Hölscher, W. Leitner
J. Am. Chem. Soc. **2015**, 138, 433-443.
9. *Love at second sight for CO₂ and H₂ in organic synthesis*
J. Klankermayer, W. Leitner
Science **2015**, 350, 629-630.
10. *Hydrogenation of carbon dioxide to methanol using a homogeneous ruthenium–Triphos catalyst: from mechanistic investigations to multiphase catalysis*
S. Wesselbaum, V. Moha, M. Meuresch, S. Brosinski, K. M. Thenert, J. Kothe, T. vom Stein, U. Englert, M. Hölscher, J. Klankermayer, W. Leitner
Chem. Sci. **2014**, 6, 693-704.

Prof. Dr. Mehtap Özasan

Full (W3) Professor of Technical Electrocatalysis

Technical University Braunschweig

Institute for Technical Chemistry

D-38106 Braunschweig, Germany

Phone +49-531-391-65790

Email m.oezaslan@tu-braunschweig.de

Studies and Degrees:

- | | |
|-------------|--|
| 2000 | Abitur, Lise-Meitner-Schule, Oberstufenzentrum für Chemie, Physik und Biologie, Berlin |
| 2001 | Training as chemical-technical assistant, Lise-Meitner-Schule, Oberstufenzentrum für Chemie, Physik und Biologie, Berlin |
| 2001 - 2006 | Technische Universität Berlin, Study of Chemistry, Diploma in Technical Chemistry |
| 2012 | Technische Universität Berlin, PhD in Technical Chemistry (summa cum laude) |

Scientific Vita:

- | | |
|-----------------|---|
| 2012 | PostDoc, The Electrochemical Catalysis, Energy and New Materials Science Group, TU Berlin (Prof. Dr. P. Strasser) |
| 2012-2014 | Scientist, The Electrochemistry Laboratory, Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland (Prof. Dr. T. J. Schmidt) |
| 08/2017-05/2019 | Junior Professor for Electrocatalysis, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg |
| since 07/2016 | Group leader of the BMBF project "ECat-PEMFC" |
| since 06/2019 | Full (W3) Professor for Technical Electrocatalysis, Technische Universität Braunschweig |

Awards:

- | | |
|----------------|---|
| 2003/2004/2005 | Three times winner of the Klaus - Koch - scholarships |
| 2007 | Clara - von - Simson prize for best diploma thesis in Engineering and Natural Sciences at the TU Berlin |

2012-2014	Promotion on “Fast Track Program” of Robert-Bosch Foundation
2014	Umicore Scientific Award for the PhD thesis, awarded from FWO - Research Foundation Flanders

Official functions

since 2019	Member of The Executive Board, Division since 2019 Electrochemistry, GDCh
	Member of The Scientific Advisory Board Energy Research Field at KIT
2014	Co-chair of the 11. ECHEMS- Electrochemistry in Renewable Energy based on Molecular Mechanisms Conference

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. I.A. Safo, C. Dosche, M. Oezaslan*: Effects of Capping Agents on Oxygen Reduction Reaction Activity and Shape Stability of Pt Nanocubes., *ChemPhysChem*, 2019, just accepted, DOI: 10.1002/cphc.201900653.
2. I.A. Safo, M. Werheid, C. Dosche, M. Oezaslan*: The role of Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) as Capping and Structure-Directing Agent in the Formation of Pt Nanocubes *Nanoscale Advances*, 1 (2019) p. 3095-3106.
3. D. J. Weber, M. Janssen, M. Oezaslan*: Effect of monovalent Cations on the Hydrogen Oxidation/Evolution Reaktion (HOR/HER) for Pt in alkaline media., *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 166, **2019** (2), p. F66-F73.
4. B. Hecker, C. Dosche, M. Oezaslan*: Dealloying: Ligament evolution in nanoporous Cu films., *Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 122, **2018** (46) p. 26378-26384.
5. F. Muench,* R. Popovitz-Biro, T. Bendikov, Y. Feldman, B. Hecker, M. Oezaslan, I. Rubinstein, A. Vaskevich*: Nucleation-Controlled Solution Deposition of Silver Nanoplate Architectures for Facile Derivatization and Catalytic Applications, *Advanced Materials*, 30 (2018) 51, p. 1805179.
6. J. Quinson, M. Inaba, A. A. Swane, S. B. Simonsen, L. T. Kuhn, J. J. K. Kirkensgaard, K. M. Jensen, M. Oezaslan, S. Kunz*, M. Arenz*: Investigating Particle Size Effects in Catalysis by Applying a Size-Controlled and Surfactant-Free Synthesis of Colloidal Nanoparticles in Alkaline Ethylene Glycol: Case Study of the Oxygen Reduction Reaction on Pt, *ACS Catalysis*, 8 (2018) p. 6627-6635.
7. A. Safo, M. Oezaslan*: Electrochemical Cleaning of Polyvinylpyrrolidone-capped Pt Nanocubes for the Oxygen Reduction Reaction., *Electrochimica Acta*, 241, **2017**, p. 544-552.

8. M. Oezaslan*, W. Liu, M. Nachtegaal, A. I. Frenkel, B. Rutkowski, M. Werheid, A. K. Herrmann, C. Laugier-Bonnaud, H. C. Yilmaz, N. Gaponik, A. Czyska-Filemonowicz, A. Eychmuller, T. J. Schmidt*: Homogeneity and elemental distribution in self-assembled bimetallic Pd-Pt aerogels prepared by a spontaneous one-step gelation process, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 18 (2016) p. 20640-20650.
9. T. Reier*, M. Oezaslan, P. Strasser: Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER) on Ru, Ir and Pt Catalysts – A Comparative Study of Nanoparticles and Bulk Materials, *ACS Catalysis*, 2 (2012) 8, p. 1765-1772
10. M. Oezaslan*, M. Heggen, P. Strasser: Size-Dependent Morphology of dealloyed bimetallic Catalysts: Linking the Nano to the Macro Scale, *Journal of The American Chemical Society*, 134 (2012) 1, p. 514-524.

Prof. Dr. Regina Palkovits

RWTH Aachen University

Institut für Technische und Makromolekulare Chemie

Chair of Heterogeneous Catalysis & Chemical Technology

Worringerweg 2, D-52074 Aachen

Phone +49 241 80 26497,

Email palkovits@itmc.rwth-aachen.de

Current and previous positions

- Since 2015 Acting Director of the Institute of Chemical Technology & Makromolekulare Chemistry (ITMC), RWTH Aachen University/ Germany
- Since 2013 Full Professor for Heterogeneous Catalysis & Chemical Technology, ITMC, RWTH Aachen University/ Germany
- 2012 Offer of Chair positions at Wageningen University (NL) and Saarland University
- 2010 – 2013 Associate Professor for Nanostructured Catalysts, ITMC, RWTH Aachen University/ Germany
- 2008 – 2010 Group Leader, Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Mülheim/ Germany
- 2007 PostDoc with Prof. Bert Weckhuysen, Utrecht University/ The Netherlands

Education

- 2003 – 2006 PhD Student with Prof. Ferdi Schüth at Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Mülheim a.d. Ruhr/ Germany
- 1998 – 2003 Diploma of Chemical Engineering, Technical University Dortmund/ Germany
- 2002 Exchange Semester, Chemical Engineering of Lehigh University, Pennsylvania/USA

Fellowships and awards

- 2019 EFCATS Young Researcher Award
- 2019 Exxon Mobil Science & Engineering Award
- 2017 DECHEMA Award for outstanding scientific contributions, Dechema/Germany
- 2015 FAMOS for family (award for family-friendliness of RWTH Aachen University)
- 2013 Max-Buchner Research Fellowship
- 2011 Selected for the Capital-Project Young Elite “Four time forty below forty”
- 2011 Award „100 Women of tomorrow“ of the initiative „Germany – Country of Ideas“
- 2010 Innovation Award of North-Rhine-Westphalian Academy of Science/ Germany
- 2010 Robert Bosch Junior Professorship of Robert Bosch Foundation/ Germany

- 2010 Jochen-Block Award of the German Catalysis Society/ Germany
- 2009 Award for “Comprehensible Science” of GKSS, Helmholtz Society/ Germany
- 2008 „Fast-Track Fellowship” of Robert Bosch Foundation/ Germany
- 2006 Hendrik Casimir – Karl Ziegler Research Award of Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Science and North Rhine-Westphalia Academy of Science and Arts

Institutional responsibilities

- Since 2016 Section representative of JARA-Energy Processes an institutional collaboration of RWTH and Helmholtz Centre Juelich/ Germany
- 2014 – 2015 Chair of Examination Board, Chemistry Department, RWTH/ Germany
- Since 2013 Member of the Steering Committee of RWTH Profile Area “Energy, Chemical & Process Engineering” (ECPE), RWTH/Germany
- Since 2012 Equal Opportunity Commissioner, Chemistry, RWTH/ Germany

Large projects and memberships of scientific societies

- Since 2019 Core PI of the national Cluster of Excellence “Fuel Science Center”
- Since 2016 Cluster coordinator (FC-B3) of Kopernikus Project P2X (national flagship)
- 2017-2018 Member (PI) of the national Cluster of Excellence “Tailor-made fuels from biomass”
- 2008 – 2012 Member (PI) of NRW Research Cluster “NETZ - Nano Energy Technology Centre”
- Since 2012 Member (PI) of Erasmus Mundus Graduate School SinChem
- 2010 – 2015 Member (PI) of NRW Research Cluster SusChemSys
- Since 2014 Member, FPS COST Action FP1306
- Since 2014 Member of the Strategic Partnerships and Thematic Networks “ACalNet, the Aachen-California Network of Academic Exchange” (DAAD and BMBF)
- Since 2008 Member of German Catalysis Society, Dechema and GDCh

Selected most recent research publications:

1. J. Meyers, J. B. Mensah, F. J. Holzhäuser, A. Omari, C. C. Blesken, T. Tiso, S. Palkovits, L. M. Blank, S. Pischinger, **R. Palkovits***, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 12 (2019) 2406-2411: Electrochemical conversion of a bio-derivable hydroxy-acid to a drop-in oxygenate diesel fuel
2. L. Negahdar, F. Zeng, S. Palkovits, C. Broicher, **R. Palkovits***, *ChemElectroChem.* (2019) doi: 10.1002/celec.201901265: Mechanistic aspects of the electrocatalytic oxygen evolution reaction over Ni-Co oxides

3. **R. Palkovits**, S. Palkovits*, *ACS Catal.* 9 (2019) 9, 8383-8387: Using artificial intelligence to forecast water oxidation catalysts
4. M. O. Haus, Y. Louven, **R. Palkovits**, *Green Chem.* (2019) accepted: Extending the Chemical Product Tree: A Green Value Chain for the Production of N-Vinyl-2-Pyrrolidones from Biogenic Acids
5. J. Simböck, A. Khetan, N. Pegios, R. Iskandar, A. Schwedt, J. M. A. Harmsen, T. E. Weirich, H. Pitsch, **R. Palkovits***, *Appl. Catal. A*, (2019) 117178: Deactivation Reactions on a Commercial Lean NO_x-trap - Effect of Hydrocarbon Nature, Concentration and Operation Temperature
6. P. Hoang Ho, M. Jabłońska*, M. Nocuń, G. Fornasari, F. Ospitali, A. Vaccari, P. Benito, **R. Palkovits***, *ChemCatChem.* (2019) doi: 10.1002/cctc.201901394: Effect of neodymium in Co(Cu)-Al mixed oxides on their physico-chemical properties and activity in N₂O decomposition
7. P. Hoang Ho, M. Jabłońska, R. Palkovits, E. Rodríguez-Castellón, F. Ospitali, G. Fornasari, A. Vaccari, P. Benito, *Chem Eng. J.*, 2019, 379, 122259: N₂O catalytic decomposition on electrodeposited Rh-based open-cell metallic foams
8. C. Mebrahtu, S. Perathoner, G. Giorgianni, S. Chen, G. Centi, F. Krebs, **R. Palkovits**, S. Abate, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 2019, 9 (15), 4023-4035: Deactivation mechanism of hydrotalcite-derived Ni–AlO_x catalysts during low-temperature CO₂ methanation via Ni-hydroxide formation and the role of Fe in limiting this effect
9. L. Kipshagen, M. J. Lach, L. Vömel, M. A. Liauw, A. Klemmer, A. Schulz, C. Kropf, P. J. C. Hausoul*, **R. Palkovits***, *Green Chem.* 21 (2019) 3882-3890: Anionic surfactants based on intermediates of carbohydrate conversion
10. X. Wang, A. K. Beine, P. J. C. Hausoul, **R. Palkovits**, *ChemCatChem.* 11 (2019) 16, 4123-4129: Cu/C-catalyzed hydrogenolysis of sorbitol to glycols—on the influence of particle size and base

Dr. Sonja Schimmler

Fraunhofer-Institut für Offene Kommunikationssysteme FOKUS

Kaiserin-Augusta-Allee 31

10589 Berlin

Phone +49 30 3463-7159

Email sonja.schimmler@fokus.fraunhofer.de

Sonja Schimmler is research group lead of the group "Digitalisation and Scientific Value Creation" at the Weizenbaum Institute of the Networked Society since April 2018 and project lead at Fraunhofer FOKUS since April 2018. Before that, she was a senior lecturer at the Computer Science Department of the University of the Federal Armed Forces Munich. She holds a Ph.D. in Computer Science (2012) from the University of the Federal Armed Forces Munich and an M.Sc. in Computer Science (2005) from the Georgia Institute of Technology, USA. She studied Computer Science at the Georgia Institute of Technology, USA and at the Technical University Munich.

Her research interests range from data science to human computer interaction and model-driven software development. Currently, she has a special focus on Open Science and research data infrastructures. She has published more than 40 papers in these domains. She has served in over 60 program committees, and has co-organized more than 10 workshops & conferences.

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

Software

- [edp] H2020 project EDP (European Data Portal), <https://www.europeandataportal.eu>
- [piveau] piveau data management ecosystem, <https://www.piveau.de>

Publications

1. F. Kirstein, B. Dittwald, S. Dutkowski, Y. Glikman, S. Schimmler, M. Hauswirth. Linked Data in the European Data Portal: A Comprehensive Platform for Applying DCAT-AP. In Proc. of the Joint Conference EGOV-CeDEM-EPART 2019 (EGOV 2019), San Benedetto Del Tronto, Italy, 2019. Springer LNCS.
2. S. Schimmler, F. Kirstein, S. Urbanek, H. Wünsche, M. Hauswirth. Growing Open Science with the Combined Potential of Citizen Science and Auto Science. In Proc. of the Weizenbaum Conference 2019 "Challenges of Digital Inequality - Digital Education, Digital Work, Digital Life", Berlin, Germany, 2019. SSOAR.

3. S. Seidel, S. Schimmler, U. Borghoff. Understanding Neural Network Decisions by Creating Equivalent Symbolic AI Models. In Proc. of the Intelligent Systems Conference 2018 (IntelliSys 2018), London, United Kingdom, 2018. IEEE Computer Society Press.
4. C. Schenk, M. Minas, S. Schimmler. Investigating Uni-Stroke Gesture Input for Diagram Editors on Large Wall-Mounted Touch-Screens. In Proc. of the 2017 IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages and Human-Centric Computing (VL/HCC 2017), Raleigh, North Carolina, USA, 2017. IEEE Computer Society Press.
5. C. Schenk, S. Schimmler, U. Borghoff. Interoperable Access to Video Content as a Basis for Collaborative Video Editing. In Proc. of the 2016 International Conference on Collaboration Technologies (CTS 2016), Orlando, USA, 2016. IEEE Computer Society Press.
6. S. Maier, S. Roennau. A REST-based Document Model for Collaborative Editing of Documents. In Proc. of the Third International Workshop on Document Changes: Modeling, Detection, Storage and Visualization (DChanges 2015), Lausanne, Switzerland, 2015. ACM.
7. S. Maier, M. Minas. Recording, Processing, and Visualizing Changes in Diagrams. In Proc. of the 2015 IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages and Human-Centric Computing (VL/HCC 2015), Atlanta, USA, 2015. IEEE Computer Society Press.
8. S. Maier. A Pattern-based Approach for the Combination of Different Layout Algorithms in Diagram Editors. Universitaet der Bundeswehr Muenchen, 2012.

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Dr.h.c. Dr.h.c. Prof. E.h. Michael Resch

Institut für Höchstleistungsrechnen und Höchstleistungsrechenzentrum Stuttgart (HLRS)

Universität Stuttgart

Nobelstraße 19

70569 Stuttgart

Phone +49-711-685-8-7200

Email resch@hlrs.de

Professional Career

- 1990 Graduation in Tech. Mathematics (Dipl.-Ing.) TU Graz/Austria
- 1990 – 1993 Scientific Employee at Joanneum Research GmbH at Graz/Austria
- 1993 – 2001 Scientific Employee at University of Stuttgart
- 2001 Doctoral Degree (Dr.-Ing. “mit Auszeichnung”) at the University of Stuttgart, thesis on “Metacomputing in Engineering Applications”
- 2002 Ass. Professor at the Dept. of Comp. Science of the Univ. of Houston, TX
- since 2003 Director of the High Performance Computing Centre Stuttgart (HLRS)
- since 2003 Full Professor (C4) and director of the Institute of High Performance Computing (IHR) at the University of Stuttgart

Internal and External Positions

- since 2018 Elected member of the University Council of the University of Stuttgart
- since 2018 Member of the board of trustees of the Center for Art and Media (ZKM), Karlsruhe
- since 2018 Member of the board of the Media Solution Center, Stuttgart
- since 2018 Member of the board of trustees of the Fraunhofer-Institute for Interfacial Engineering and Biotechnology (IGB)
- since 2017 Chairman of the board of the Automotive Simulation Center Stuttgart
- since 2015 Member of the Consulting Committee of the Filmakademie Baden-Württemberg
- since 2007 Member of the board of the Gauss Center for Supercomputing
- since 2008 Member of the steering committee of the Hyperion HPC User Forum
- since 2007 Member of the board of trustees(since 2016 chairman) of the Stiftung Umwelt und Schadensvorsorge / Foundation Environment and Damage Prevention of the SparkassenVersicherung
- since 2004 Member of the advisory board of the Dr. Karl Eisele und Elisabeth Eisele foundation

Professional Offers, Awards and Recognitions

- 1999 NSF/US Award for High Performance Distributed Computing
- 2002 Offer of an Associate Professorship at University of Houston
- 2003 HPC Challenge Award for “Global Analysis of Arthropod Evolution”
- 2007 Invited Keynote Speaker at the Supercomputing 2007 Conference, Reno, NV
- 2009 Honorary doctoral degree, Donetsk National Technical University/Ukraine
- 2010 Offer of a Full Professorship (W3) and director IT, University of Darmstadt
- 2011 Honorary doctoral degree, Russian Academy of Science / Siberian Branch
- 2014 Honorary Professorship of the Russian Academy of Science / Siberian Branch

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. Tchipev Nicola, Seckler Steffen, Heinen Matthias, Vrabec Jadran, Gratl Fabio, Horsch Martin, Bernreuther Martin, Glass Colin, Niethammer Christoph, Hammer Nicolay, Krischok Bernd, Michael Resch, Kranzlmüller Dieter, Hasse Hans, Bungartz Hans-Joachim, Neumann Philipp, TweTriS: Twenty Trillion-atom Simulation, International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342018819741>
2. Michael M. Resch, Thomas Boenisch, Michael Gienger, Bastian Koller, High Performance Computing – Challenges and Risks for the Future, in Vinai K. Singh, David Gao, Andreas Fischer (Eds.), Advances in Mathematical Methods and High Performance Computing, Springer, 2019
3. Thomas Bönisch, Michael Resch, Thomas Schwitalla, Matthias Meinke, Volker Wulfmeyer, and Kirsten Warrach-Sagi, Hazel Hen – Leading HPC technology and its impact on science in Germany and Europe, Journal of Parallel Computing , Vol 64, May 2017, 3-11 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.parco.2017.02.002>
4. Natalia Melnikova, Stepan Orlov, Nikolay Shabrov, Vlad Kiev, Aleksey Kuzin, Michael Resch, Uwe Wössner and Martin Aumüller, CAVE 3D: software extensions for scientific visualization of large-scale models, Procedia Computer Science, Vol 66, 679 – 688, 2015
5. Thomas Baumann, Michael Resch, Parallel Parameter Identification in Industrial Biotechnology, International Journal of Parallel Programming, 42(3), 490 – 504 (2014)
6. Michael Neff, Dominik Oschetzki, Yuriy Yudin, Yevgen Dorozhko, Natalia Curre-Linde, Michael Resch and Guntram Rauhut, Efficient Calculation of Multi-dimensional Potential Energy Surfaces of Molecules and Molecular Clusters, in Wolfgang E. Nagel, Dietmar H. Kröner, Michael M. Resch (Eds.), High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering'13, pp 219 – 232, Springer, 2014
7. Ralf Schneider and Michael M. Resch, Calculation of the Discrete Effective Stiffness of Cancellous Bone by Direct Mechanical Simulations, in M.Garbey et al., Computational

Surgery and Dual Training , Pages 351-361, doi 10.1007/978-1-4614-8648-0_23, Springer New York, 2014

8. Marc C. Wiedemann, Julian M. Kunkel, Michaela Zimmer, Thomas Ludwig, Michael M. Resch, Thomas Bönisch, Xuan Wang, Andriy Chut, Alvaro Aguilera, Wolfgang E. Nagel, Michael Kluge, Holger Mickler: Towards I/O analysis of HPC systems and a generic architecture to collect access patterns, *Computer Science - R&D* 28(2-3): 241-251 (2013)

9. Y. Dorozhko, Y. Yudin, K. Kratzer, A. Arnold, C. W. Glass and M. Resch, Rare Event Sampling using the Science Experimental Grid Laboratory, 14th International Conference on Civil, Structural and Environmental Engineering Computing (CC 2013), Cagliari, Sardinia, Italy, September 3-6, 2013

10. Thomas Baumann, Michael Resch, Parallel Parameter Identification in Industrial Biotechnology, *Proceedings of the 10th IEEE International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Processing with Applications, CPS, 2012*, pp 127 – 134, DOI 10.1109/ISPA.2012.25

Prof. Dr. Kurt Wagemann

DECHEMA e. V.

Theodor-Heuss-Allee 25

60486 Frankfurt / Main

Phone +4969 75 64-2 90

Email kurt.wagemann@dechema.de

Professional Career

1978 – 1985 Diploma in chemistry at University of Munich

Thesis on Spectroscopic analysis of catalytic reactions

Group of Prof. Gerhard Ertl

1986 – 1989 PhD at Max-Planck-Institut für Quantenoptik

Department of Laser Chemistry, Head: Prof. Karl-Ludwig Kompa

Laserspectroscopic analysis of Gasphase and Surface Reactions

1989 Employment at the DECHEMA e.V. as Scientific Co-Ordinator for chemistry fundamentals: evaluation of the innovation potential in the field of chemistry, commissioned by the BMBF (Federal Ministry of Education and Research), research co-ordination and management of research projects

1992 – 2004 Head of the Research Planning Group:

- Evaluation of scientific technical trends
- Planning of the Programme on Chemical Technologies of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research
- Partnering activities (workshops and internet) for collaborative projects
- Project management
- Project evaluation

1994 – 2000 Head of the DECHEMA Congress Group

Deputy Head of the Department for Research Management and Administration

2000 – 2009 Head of the Department for Research Management and Administration

2005 – 2009 Executive Director of the Forschungsgesellschaft Messtechnik, Sensorik und Medizintechnik e.V. Dresden

2007 – 2009 Deputy Executive Director of DECHEMA e.V and Director of ProcessNet – an Initiative of DECHEMA and VDI-GVC

since 2006	Lectures at the University of Stuttgart
since 2010	Lectures at the University of Magdeburg
since 2010	Executive Director of DECHEMA e.V.
February 2011	Honorary Professor at the University of Stuttgart

Ten most important research contributions (publications, software, data sets, similar)

1. I.C. Bassignana, K. Wagemann, J. Küppers, G. Ertl, **Adsorption and Thermal Decomposition of Ammonia on a Ni(110) Surface: Isolation and Identification of Adsorbed NH₂ and NH**, Surface Science 175, 22-44 (1986)
2. K. Wagemann, X.R. Chen, J. Wanner, **IF(A,B) electronic excitation in F + I₂F induced by the surface reaction F(ad) + I₂(ad)**, Journal of Chemical Physics 95 No. 10, 7348-7355 (1991)
3. G. Wegner, K. Wagemann, **Polymers and the Environment – Current Problems and Future Research**, Advanced Materials 6, No. 9, 629-634 (1994)
4. J. Michels, K. Wagemann, **The German Lignocellulose Feedstock Biorefinery Project**, Biofuels, Bioproduct & Biorefining 4, Issue 3, 263-267 (2010)
5. K. Wagemann, **Bioraffinerien im Kontext der Überlegungen zu einer zukünftigen Bioökonomie**, Erdöl Erdgas Kohle, 128. Jg. 2012, Heft 10, 347-352
6. K. Wagemann, **Herstellung von Grundchemikalien auf Basis nachwachsender Rohstoffe als Alternative zur Petrochemie**, Chemie Ingenieur Technik 86, Heft 12, 2115-2134 (2014), DOI: 10.1002/cite.201400108
7. F. Ausfelder, C. Beilmann, M. Bertau, S. Bräuninger, A. Heinzl, R. Hoer, W. Koch, F. Mahlendorf, A. Metzeltin, M. Peuckert, L. Plass, K. Räuchle, M. Reuter, G. Schaub, S. Scchieban, E. Schwab, F. Schüth, D. Stolten, G. Teßmer, K. Wagemann, K.-F. Ziegahn, **Energiespeicherung als Element einer sicheren Energieversorgung**, Chemie Ingenieur Technik 87, Heft 1-2, 17-89 (2015)
8. F. Ausfelder, F.-D. Drake, M. Paschke, F. Schüth, M. Themann, K. Wagemann, H.-J. Wagner, **Wechselwirkungen im Energiesystem**, acatech Schriftenreihe, Februar 2015
9. K. Wagemann, **Production of Basic Chemicals on the Basis of Renewable Resources as an Alternative to Petrochemistry?**, DOI: 10.1002/cben.201500005
10. K. Wagemann, N. Tippkötter, **Biorefineries: A short introduction**, Adv. Biochem. Eng. Biotechnol. (2019) 16: 1-12 DOI: 10.1007/10_2017_4, Springer International Publishing AG

7.3 Letter of commitment by the participants

The following participants have sent a letter of commitment. The documents are provided in the order as given below:

1. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Bastian Etzold, Technische Universität Darmstadt
2. Prof. Dr. Klaus-Robert Müller, TU Berlin (BBDC) Berlin Big Data Center und (BZML) Berlin Zentrum für Maschinelles Lernen
3. Prof. Dr. Marcus Rose, Technische Universität Darmstadt